

Methodologies for reporting emissions to water under the Industrial Emission Portal Regulation

Final report

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Summary

The aim of this report is to propose a common methodology for all Member States to assess emissions to water for intensive livestock production and aquaculture. This objective aligns with the new Industrial Emissions Portal Regulation (IEPR) which requires a guidance on the calculation methods, including emission factors per abatement technology, for deliberate emissions from livestock production and aquaculture, within the scope of the Regulation (Article 13(g) of the IEPR).

Regarding emissions to water, this study is based on data from the Industrial Reporting Database, which provides information on pollutant releases from over 60,000 industrial sites from 65 economic activities across 33 countries in Europe. The database includes information on 94 pollutants ⁽¹⁾, and details the methodology used by reporters to quantify these releases. To supplement this data, complemented questionnaires and interviews with reporters from selected countries provided further insight into the methodologies employed.

A review of existing methodologies for calculating emissions to water was also carried out, highlighting calculation methods such as mass balance and emission factors. While most of these methods are applicable to aquaculture, relatively little data is available for intensive livestock production.

Ultimately, the methodologies implemented in Cyprus, Greece, Iceland, Norway, Spain and Sweden were found to be the most developed for intensive aquaculture. For sea-based facilities, all methodologies are based on mass balance and use coefficients related to the type of pollutant and/or fish species, as well as activity data such as the amount of feed. In particular, the methodologies of Estonia, Norway and Sweden are similar to those proposed in the guidelines of the Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission (Helsinki Commission, HELCOM, ⁽²⁾) and the Oslo and Paris Commissions' Action Plan (OSPAR, ⁽³⁾). Conversely, the recommended method for land-based facilities is measurement.

It is proposed to retain the HELCOM / OSPAR methodologies to calculate emissions into water from intensive aquaculture:

- Approach 1 should be used for sea-based installations for which information is available at installation level;
- Approach 2 is for sea-based installations for which some of the information is more readily available at a national level;
- Approach 3 is based on measurement and is intended for land-based installations.

Some of the coefficients in the approaches 1 and 2 are already available for nitrogen and phosphorus, and for different type of feed or fish species. However, it will be necessary for the Member States to carry out their own investigations to obtain applicable coefficients for their production/climate.

In contrast, due to insufficient precise data, no suitable methodology can currently be recommended for intensive livestock production. Indeed, most of the countries surveyed consider that livestock production does not generate direct emissions into water as all effluent is collected and either treated or spread on agricultural land. Bulgaria also noted that water discharges are only relevant for pig farms and not poultry farms. Based on feedback from the establishment of the IED's Uniform Conditions for

⁽¹⁾ The pollutants in Annex II may change via a delegated act as per Article 15 of the IEPR.

⁽²⁾ The Helsinki Convention was signed in 1974 by Denmark, Estonia, the European Union, Finland, Germany, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Russia and Sweden.

⁽³⁾ The OSPAR Convention was concluded at Paris on 22 September 1992 and ratified by Belgium, Denmark, the European Union, Finland, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, along with Luxembourg and Switzerland.

Operating Rules for Livestock (UCOL, ⁽⁴⁾), most countries consider that direct discharges of water from farms into water bodies are not permitted because wastewater are stored in waterproof tanks, sometimes treated, and then spread on agricultural land.

Finally, this report includes data sheets presenting all the data collected during the study: data from the Industrial Reporting Database (number of reported values from 2007 to 2023, type of methods used, etc.), details of the responses to the questionnaires sent to Member States, and details of the responses given in interviews.

⁽⁴⁾ The drawing up of the Uniform Conditions for Operating Rules for Livestock (pig and poultry rearing), which is in the scope of Article 70(i) of the IED, started at the end of 2024 and is currently still work in progress.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context

EU Regulation 2024/1244, also known as the Industrial Emissions Portal Regulation ⁽⁵⁾, was adopted by the European Union to enhance the monitoring and reporting of industrial emissions. It replaces the European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register Regulation (E-PRTR Regulation) which entered into force in 2006 with data collection beginning in 2007. The aim of the IEPR is to establish a more comprehensive and integrated industrial emissions system.

The IEPR was adopted on 24 of April 2024 and came into force on 22 of May 2024 (EU, 2024a). Over the following two years, the European Commission is tasked with developing implementing rules, including a standardised format for reporting on resource use and the integration of new sectors. The first reporting under the new regulation will cover releases and resource use data for the year 2027 and is expected to be published at the end of 2028.

The new portal will provide data on emissions to air, water and land for any pollutant listed in Annex II of the regulation, which currently covers 94 pollutants including greenhouse gases, heavy metals and others (Annex II will be updated with a delegated act in accordance with Article 15 of the IEPR). It will also include information on off-site transfers of waste and pollutants in wastewater, as well as detailed information on the installations concerned ⁽⁶⁾.

Please note, however, that the new IEPR regulation addresses reporting at the installation level, unlike the E-PRTR regulation, which required reporting at the facility level, that could encompass one or more installations located on the same site and operated by the same natural or legal person. Therefore, it is important to mention that in this report, references to E-PRTR reporting, including data from database, questionnaires and interviews, concern the facility level, whereas recommendations for methods are expressed at the installation level, as this is the entity required to report under the new legislation.

Reporters will be required to provide data on resource use applicable to all industrial activities listed in Annex I of the IEPR which includes installations undertaking activities covered by Annexes I and Ia to the Industrial Emissions Directive (IED, Directive 2010/75/EU). The Commission must adopt an implementing act by 31 December 2025.

The IEPR covers over 60,000 industrial sites across 65 economic activities in Europe. Only installations performing activities listed in Annex I of the regulation are required to report releases, and only when their emissions exceed the threshold defined in Annex II ⁽⁷⁾. Covered activities include energy; production and processing of metals; mineral industry; chemical industry; waste and wastewater management; paper and wood production and processing; intensive livestock production and aquaculture; and animal and vegetable products from the food and beverage sector.

Finally, the IEPR is designed to align the sectoral scope and reporting granularity with the revised Industrial and Livestock Rearing Emissions Directive (IED 2.0) ⁽⁸⁾ which includes updated provisions for livestock farming, to better support its implementation (EU, 2024b).

⁽⁵⁾ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/industrial-emissions-and-safety/industrial-emissions-portal-regulation-iepr_en

⁽⁶⁾ <https://industry.eea.europa.eu/about>

⁽⁷⁾ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R1244>

⁽⁸⁾ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32024L1785>

1.2 Purpose of this report

The aim of this report is to propose a common methodology across the Member States and to simplify the reporting of emissions to water from intensive aquaculture and intensive livestock production activities within the scope of the IEPR (EU, 2024a):

- Activities listed in Annex Ia to the IED (intensive rearing of pigs and poultry), designated 7.(a) in the former E-PRTR by Regulation (EC) No 166/2006 ⁽⁹⁾, and now defined as:
 1. Previously designated 7.(a).(i) in the E-PRTR ⁽¹⁰⁾; rearing of pigs representing 350 LSU or more, excluding:
 - a. Installations operating under organic production regimes in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2018/848;
 - b. Systems with a stocking density of less than 2 LSU/hectare, where land is used only for grazing or growing grazing or growing fodder, and the animals are reared outside for a significant amount of part of the year or seasonally;
 2. Previously designated 7.(a).(ii) in the E-PRTR¹⁰; rearing of poultry, specifically:
 - a. 300 LSU or more if rearing of only laying hens;
 - b. 280 LSU or more if rearing of only other poultry categories;
 - c. In installations rearing a mix of poultry including laying hens, the threshold is 280 LSU, laying hens weighted at 0.93 for calculation purposes;
 3. Previously designated 7.(a).(iii) in the E-PRTR¹⁰; mixed rearing of pigs or poultry amounting to 380 LSU or more, excluding:
 - a. Installations under organic production regimes in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2018/848, or with a stocking density less than 2 LSU/hectare and seasonal/outdoor rearing practices as defined above;
- Feed-based aquaculture, with an annual production capacity exceeding 500 tonnes, as defined in Annex I of the IEPR; previously designated 7.(b) in the E-PRTR¹⁰.

While EU level guidance is available for calculating air pollutant and GHG emissions, such as the *EMEP/EEA air pollutant emission inventory guidebook* (EEA, 2023a) from the European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme (EMEP) and European Environment Agency (EEA) and the IPCC methodology, such as the *2019 Refinement to the 2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories* (IPCC, 2019), there is currently no equivalent guidance for emissions to water. Therefore, this report recommends developing a calculation tool to support reporters in fulfilling their new reporting obligations for emissions into water. However, this tool is a separate piece of work, also achieved by ETC HE, but still in progress. The present report focuses solely on establishing a common methodology for assessing emissions to water.

This report presents the outcome of the task which includes proposing a methodology for calculating emissions to water, where feasible.

⁽⁹⁾ Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 166/2006 classified intensive livestock production and aquaculture in two categories: 7.(a) for Installations for the intensive rearing of poultry or pigs, with three sub-categories (i) With 40,000 places for poultry, (ii) With 2,000 places for production pigs (over 30 kg), (iii) With 750 places for sows; 7.(b) for Intensive aquaculture with a production capacity of 1 000 tonnes of fish or shellfish per year. It has been repealed by Regulation (EU) 2024/1244 but information in the Industrial Reporting Database from 2007 to 2023 used these activity codes and threshold.

⁽¹⁰⁾ The E-PRTR Regulation had different thresholds

A consultation with Member States on a provisional version of this report has been conducted.

1.3 Study methodology

To establish a common methodology for assessing emissions to water across Member States, the first step involved benchmarking existing methodologies used by relevant countries and identifying best practice in the literature.

Moreover, it was necessary to define the scope of the emissions to be covered by the methodology. This includes both feed-based aquaculture and intensive livestock production, covering both releases to the environment, the nature of the effluents and relevant pollutants.

To this end, emissions to water reported by facilities classified under Activity 7.(a), intensive rearing of poultry or pigs, in the and Activity 7.(b), intensive aquaculture ⁽¹¹⁾ were analysed using data from the Industrial Reporting Database (European Industrial Emissions Portal, 2025) between 2017 and 2023. The study focused on the 27 EU Member States, as well as from other countries covered by the portal: Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Serbia and Switzerland.

Based on the availability and relevance of the reported data, 29 countries ⁽¹²⁾ (Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden) were selected and contacted to obtain information on their current methodologies for assessing emissions to water. A complete list of contacts is provided in [Annex 1](#) ⁽¹³⁾.

First, tailored questionnaires were developed to address the different situations of each country and were subsequently distributed. The countries were grouped into five categories based on their reporting practices:

1. Reporting air emissions and emissions to water from 7.(a) facilities and emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities;
2. Reporting emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities but not from 7.(a) facilities;
3. Reporting air emissions and emissions to water from 7.(a) facilities;
4. Reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities;
5. Not reporting any emissions (air or water) from 7.(b) facilities.

Based on their feedback, interviews were organised with relevant national authorities in early 2025. These interviews aimed to gather a deeper understanding of their methodologies and to clarify aspects that were not fully captured in the questionnaires.

In parallel, a comprehensive review of existing methodologies for calculating emissions to water and associated emission factors was conducted. The results of this review, including key findings and limitations identified, are presented and discussed in the subsequent sections.

⁽¹¹⁾ Annex I of Regulation (EC) No 166/2006 classifies intensive livestock production and aquaculture in two categories: 7.(a) for Installations for the intensive rearing of poultry or pigs, with three sub-categories (i) With 40,000 places for poultry, (ii) With 2,000 places for production pigs (over 30 kg), (iii) With 750 places for sows; 7.(b) for Intensive aquaculture with a production capacity of 1 000 tonnes of fish or shellfish per year.

⁽¹²⁾ The E-PRTR includes certain non-EU countries such as Iceland, Norway, Liechtenstein, Switzerland and Republic of Serbia.

⁽¹³⁾ The public version of this report will not disclose personal data.

2 Review of the Industrial Reporting Database

The Industrial Reporting Database (European Industrial Emissions Portal, ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025, ¹⁴) provides environmental data for the largest industrial complexes in Europe. This includes releases and transfers of regulated substances into water and air, as well as waste transfers from 2007 to 2023. It also provides detailed data on the energy inputs and emissions of large combustion plants and waste (co-)incinerators (reported under IED Article 72) from 2016 to 2023.

Data are submitted by all 27 EU Member States, as well as by Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Serbia, Switzerland and the United Kingdom (^{15, 16}). However, for the purposes of this study, data from the United Kingdom have been excluded.

The analysis presented here focuses on data from installations that reported emissions to water between 2017 and 2023, and that are classified as follows:

- Activity 7.(a) 'Installations for the intensive rearing of poultry or pigs';
- Activity 7.(b) 'Intensive aquaculture'.

This chapter provides a statistical overview of the extracted data, broken down by country, pollutant and method.

2.1 Review by country

Table 2.1 and Figure 2.1 below provide an overview of the number of facilities that reported emissions to air or water between 2017 and 2023 for Activity 7.(a) and Activity 7.(b), along with the associated pollutants, for each country. A more comprehensive breakdown, showing the distribution of water and air emissions reporting from 2007 to 2023 for every country, is provided in [Annex 2](#).

⁽¹⁴⁾ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/datahub/datahubitem-view/9405f714-8015-4b5b-a63c-280b82861b3d?activeAccordion=>

⁽¹⁵⁾ UK data is only available until reporting year 2019 (reported in 2020) as a result of the Brexit withdrawal agreement

⁽¹⁶⁾ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/industrial-reporting-under-the-industrial-7/eu-registry-e-prtr-lcp>

Table 2.1: Number of facilities reporting emissions (2017-2023) by country, media (air or water), activity 7.(a) or 7.(b), and pollutant

Country	Number of facilities reporting emissions by media and pollutants (a)																	
	7.(a): Installations for the intensive rearing of poultry or pigs																7.(b): Intensive aquaculture (b)	
	(i) With 40 000 places for poultry				(ii) With 2 000 places for production pigs (over 30 kg)				(iii) With 750 places for sows				(?) Unspecified					
	Air emissions		Emissions to water		Air emissions		Emissions to water		Air emissions		Emissions to water		Air emissions		Emissions to water		Emissions to water	
Austria	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	2	NH ₃	0	-	0	-
Belgium	71	NH ₃	0	-	75	NH ₃	0	-	5	NH ₃	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Bulgaria	49	NH ₃ , N ₂ O	2	N, P, TOC	25	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O, PM ₁₀	2	N, P	2	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , PM ₁₀ , NO _x	0	-	4	NH ₃ , CH ₄	1	Cd, Pb, Zn	0	-
Croatia (c)	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Cyprus	18	NH ₃	0	-	24	NH ₃ , CH ₄	0	-	1	NH ₃	0	-	0	-	0	-	5	N, P
Czechia (d)	131	NH ₃	0	-	114	NH ₃ , PM ₁₀ , NO _x	0	-	37	NH ₃ , SO _x , NO _x , CO	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Denmark	67	NH ₃	0	-	135	NH ₃	0	-	44	NH ₃	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Estonia	10	NH ₃ , SO _x	0	-	23	NH ₃ , CH ₄	0	-	2	NH ₃	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Finland	113	NH ₃	0	-	27	NH ₃	0	-	16	NH ₃	0	-	2	NH ₃	0	-	0	-
France	338	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O, PM ₁₀	0	-	492	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O	0	-	39	NH ₃ , CH ₄	0	-	0	-	0	-	1	N, P, TOC
Germany	200	NH ₃ , N ₂ O, PM ₁₀	0	-	390	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O	0	-	122	NH ₃	0	-	8	NH ₃	0	-	0	-
Greece	2	NH ₃ , N ₂ O	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	3	N, P
Hungary	312	NH ₃ , CH ₄	1	Phenols	208	NH ₃ , CH ₄	1	P	30	NH ₃ , CH ₄	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Iceland	7	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , PM ₁₀	0	- (e)	1	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , PM ₁₀	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	13	N, P, Ni
Ireland	19	NH ₃	0	-	91	NH ₃ , CH ₄	0	-	12	NH ₃ , CH ₄	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Italy	222	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O, PM ₁₀ , NO _x	0	-	457	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O, NO _x	0	-	59	NH ₃ , CH ₄	0	-	690	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O	0	-	0	-
Latvia	6	NH ₃ , N ₂ O, PM ₁₀	0	-	18	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , NO _x	0	-	3	NH ₃	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Liechtenstein (f)	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Lithuania (g)	34	NH ₃ , PM ₁₀ , NMVOC	0	-	41	NH ₃	0	-	0	-	0	-	2	NH ₃	0	-	0	-
Luxembourg	1	NH ₃	0	-	8	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Malta (h)	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	3	N, P, TOC, Cu, Zn

Country	Number of facilities reporting emissions by media and pollutants (a)																	
	7.(a): Installations for the intensive rearing of poultry or pigs																7.(b): Intensive aquaculture (b)	
	(i) With 40 000 places for poultry				(ii) With 2 000 places for production pigs (over 30 kg)				(iii) With 750 places for sows				(?) Unspecified					
	Air emissions		Emissions to water		Air emissions		Emissions to water		Air emissions		Emissions to water		Air emissions		Emissions to water		Emissions to water	
Netherlands	88	NH ₃	0	-	33	NH ₃ , CH ₄	0	-	7	NH ₃ , CH ₄	0	-	2	NH ₃	0	-	0	-
Norway (i)	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	617	N, P, TOC, Cu, Zn
Poland	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	249	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O, PM ₁₀ , NO _x	0	-	1	As, Ni (j)
Portugal	159	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O, PM ₁₀ , NO _x , CO ₂	0	- (k)	96	NH ₃ , CH ₄	0	-	12	NH ₃ , CH ₄	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Romania	309	NH ₃ , PM ₁₀	0	-	164	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O	1	Phenols	24	NH ₃ , CH ₄	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Serbia	84	NH ₃	0	- (l)	66	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , PM ₁₀ , NMVOC	0	-	11	NH ₃	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Slovakia (m)	28	NH ₃	0	-	15	NH ₃	0	-	1	NH ₃	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Slovenia	16	NH ₃	0	- (n)	1	NH ₃	0	-	1	NH ₃	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-
Spain	491	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O	0	- (o)	2,100	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O	0	-	718	NH ₃ , CH ₄ , N ₂ O, PM ₁₀	0	-	0	-	0	-	25	N, P, TOC
Sweden	68	NH ₃	0	-	48	NH ₃	1	N	8	NH ₃	0	-	1	NH ₃	0	-	3	N, P
Switzerland (p)	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-	0	-

Note: (a) Per medium (i.e. air or water) and country. Not all facilities reported emissions for all pollutants listed in the table, but at least some of them. For example, 24 pig farms from Cyprus reported air emissions over the last seven years: either only ammonia (NH₃) values, only methane (CH₄) values, or both.

(b) Only emissions to water are shown in the table for 7.(b) facilities, even though two facilities from Italy and seven from Poland have probably mistakenly reported air emissions during the last seven years.

(c) Since 2007, Croatia did not report any air emission or emission to water from 7.(a) or 7.(b) facilities in the database, even though it contains some facilities classified as 7.(a). However, it reported emissions for other activities from 2014 to 2023.

(d) Data from Czechia for the year 2023 is not present in the database for any activity. Only information from 2017 to 2022 is considered in the present study.

(e) Data from Iceland for the year 2023 is not present in the database for any activity. Only information from 2017 to 2022 is considered in the present study. For the last seven years, Iceland only reported air emissions from 7.(a) facilities, but before that, it had reported emissions to water from them (last reporting year: 2010).

(f) Although Liechtenstein is supposed to report emissions from its facilities, no emissions are present in the database, for any activity.

(g) Data from Lithuania for the year 2023 is not present in the database for any activity. Only information from 2017 to 2022 is considered in the present study.

(h) Data from Malta for the year 2023 is not present in the database for any activity. Only information from 2017 to 2022 is considered in the present study.

- (i) Data from Norway for the years 2018 to 2023 is not present in the database for any activity. Only information from 2017 is considered in the present study.
- (j) It seems one facility from Poland classified as 7.(b) has been misclassified in the database since it has a manufacturing activity, not aquaculture.
- (k) For the last seven years, Portugal has only reported air emissions from 7.(a) facilities, but before that, it had reported emissions to water from them (last reporting year: 2012).
- (l) For the last seven years, Serbia has only reported air emissions from 7.(a) facilities, but before that, it had reported emissions to water from them (last reporting year: 2012).
- (m) Data from Slovakia for the year 2023 is not present in the database for any activity. Only information from 2017 to 2022 is considered in the present study.
- (n) For the last seven years, Slovenia has only reported air emissions from 7.(a) facilities, but before that, it had reported emissions to water from them (last reporting year: 2007).
- (o) For the last seven years, Spain has only reported air emissions from 7.(a) facilities, but before that, it had reported emissions to water from them (last reporting year: 2014).
- (p) Since 2007, Switzerland has not reported any air emission or emission to water from 7.(a) or 7.(b) facilities in the database. However, it has reported emissions from other activities between 2007 and 2022.

Source: Author's compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025.

Figure 2.1: Number of facilities reporting emissions to water (2017-2023) by country and activity: 7.(a) 'Installations for the intensive rearing of poultry or pigs' (left) and 7.(b) 'Intensive aquaculture' (right)

Note: The breakdown of intensive pig and poultry farming activities is as follows:

- In Bulgaria: two poultry farms, two pig farms and one unspecified farm ⁽¹⁷⁾,
- In Hungary: one poultry farm and one pig farm,
- In Romania: one pig farm,
- In Sweden: one pig farm.

Source: Author’s compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025.

7.(a) facilities (Intensive Rearing of Poultry or Pigs):

Over the past seven years, a total of 9,609 unique facilities classified under Activity 7.(a) across 27 countries reported air emissions:

- 2,843 poultry farms;
- 4,652 pig farms;
- 1,154 sow farms;
- 960 farms with unspecified types.

In contrast, only nine facilities from four countries — Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania and Sweden — reported emissions to water during the same period. This includes:

- Three poultry farms;
- Five pig farms;
- One unspecified farm.

Among these, Bulgaria had the most 7.(a) facilities reporting emissions to water, accounting for five out of the nine facilities.

⁽¹⁷⁾ Under the current reporting, Member States are allowed to define the main activity of the farm as “7(a)” only, which does not specify whether the farm handles pigs or poultry. Conversely, most Member States report the main activity more granularly – 7(a)(i), 7(a)(ii) and 7(a)(iii) where it is specified whether it is poultry, production pigs or sows, respectively (see annex I of the E-PRTR Regulation).

Of the remaining countries:

- 23 countries reported air emissions only from 7.(a) facilities;
- One country (Croatia) reported neither air nor water emissions from 7.(a) facilities;
- Four are reported as having no 7.(a) facilities (Liechtenstein, Malta, Norway and Switzerland).

It is also noteworthy that prior to 2017, some 7.(a) facilities from Iceland, Portugal, Serbia, Slovenia and Spain had intermittently reported emissions to water but have since stopped.

7.(b) facilities (Intensive Aquaculture):

A total of 671 unique facilities from nine countries (Cyprus, France, Greece, Iceland, Malta, Norway Poland, Spain and Sweden) reported emissions to water between 2017 and 2023. Among these, Norway stands out significantly. In 2017 alone, it reported emissions to water from 617 facilities classified 7.(b), making it the country with the most 7.(b) facilities reporting emissions to water among the nine.

Out of the remaining 23 countries:

- Two countries (Belgium and Italy) have aquaculture facilities but did not report any emissions to water from these facilities during the last seven years;
- 21 countries appear to have no 7.(b) facilities based on the available reporting data.

General remarks:

Across all reporting countries, six out of 32 have reported emissions to water exclusively from 7.(b) facilities with no such reporting from 7.(a) facilities: Cyprus, France, Greece, Iceland, Poland and Spain.

Moreover, there is a notable variation in the types of pollutants reported, depending on both the country and activity (7.(a) or 7.(b)). These differences are explored in greater detail in Section 2.2.

2.2 Review per pollutant

Table 2.2 and Figure 2.2 below present the number of facilities which reported emissions to water by pollutant between 2017 and 2023 (note: for Norway only data from 2017 are available). The data are categorised by activity type, either 7.(a) or 7.(b), and by reporting country.

A detailed breakdown of emissions to water reporting by country and pollutant between 2017 and 2023 is available in [Annex 3](#).

To maintain clarity and avoid overcrowding in Table 2.2, the two-letter ISO country codes (ISO 3166-1 alpha2 codes⁽¹⁸⁾) are used to represent each reporting country. A full reference [list of codes](#) is available at the end of this report.

⁽¹⁸⁾ <https://www.iso.org/iso-3166-country-codes.html>

Table 2.2: Number of facilities reporting emissions between 2017 and 2023, per pollutant, per activity 7.(a) or 7.(b) and from which country

Media	Pollutant	Threshold for releases (kg/year) (a)	Nb of facilities reporting emissions between 2017 and 2023 for each pollutant, and from which country			
			7.(a): Installations for the intensive rearing of poultry or pigs (b)		7.(b): Intensive aquaculture	
Emissions to water	As	5	0	-	1	PL (c)
	Cd	5	1	BG	0	-
	Cu	50	0	-	55	MT, NO
	N	50,000	5	BG,SE	482	CY,FR,GR,IS,MT,NO,ES,SE
	Ni	20	0	-	2	IS, PL
	P	50,00	5	BG, HU	669	CY,FR,GR,IS,MT,NO,ES,SE
	Phenols	20	2	HU, RO	0	-
	TOC	50,000	2	BG	621	FR, MT, NO, ES
	Pb	20	1	BG	0	-
Zn	100	1	BG	618	MT, NO	

Notes: (a) Reporting thresholds for each pollutant are presented in Annex II of the Regulation (EU) 2024/1244.

(b) The breakdown of intensive pig and poultry farming activities is as follows:

- For cadmium: one unspecified farm¹⁷ from Bulgaria
- For nitrogen: two poultry farms and two pig farms from Bulgaria, one pig farm from Sweden
- For phosphorus: two poultry farms and two pig farms from Bulgaria, one pig farm from Hungary
- For phenols: one poultry farm from Hungary, one pig farm from Romania
- For total organic carbon: two poultry farms from Bulgaria
- For lead: one unspecified farm from Bulgaria
- For zinc: one unspecified farm from Bulgaria

(c) It seems one facility from Poland classified as 7.(b) has been misclassified in the database since it has a manufacturing activity, not aquaculture.

Source: Author's compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025. and Regulation (EU) 2024/1244

Figure 2.2: Number of facilities reporting emissions to water from 2017 to 2023 per pollutant, and per activity: 7.(a) 'Installations for the intensive rearing of poultry or pigs' (poultry in orange, pigs in light blue, sows in green and unspecified in pink) or 7.(b) 'Intensive aquaculture' (in dark blue)

Source: Author's compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025.

Pollutants reported by 7.(b) facilities:

Among aquaculture facilities, the most frequently reported pollutants over the past seven years are:

- **Total phosphorus (P):** reported by 669 facilities;
- **Total organic carbon (TOC):** reported by 621 facilities;
- **Zinc (Zn):** reported by 618 facilities;
- **Total nitrogen (N):** reported by 669 facilities.

These figures represent by facilities in eight countries: Cyprus, France, Greece, Iceland, Malta, Norway, Spain and Sweden.

Additionally, Copper (Cu) was reported by a significant number of 7.(b) facilities: 55 facilities in total, specifically from Malta and Norway.

Less frequently reported pollutants include:

- Nickel (Ni): reported by two facilities from Iceland and Poland;
- Arsenic (As): reported by one facility from Poland.

Pollutants reported by 7.(a) facilities:

Over the last seven years, the most frequently reported pollutants from 7.(a) facilities are:

- **Total N and Total P,** each reported by five facilities, located in Bulgaria, Hungary or Sweden.

Other pollutants have been reported by an even smaller number of facilities, including:

- Phenols;
- Total Organic Carbon (TOC);
- Cadmium (Cd);
- lead (Pb);
- Zinc (Zn).

These pollutants were reported by facilities in Bulgaria, Hungary and Romania. Notably, TOC was only reported by poultry farms, and not by any pig or sow farms, suggesting potential differences in waste composition or monitoring practices across livestock types.

General remarks:

A few pollutants show a clear distinction in terms of sector-specific reporting.

- Reported exclusively by 7.(b) facilities:
 - Arsenic (As);
 - Copper (Cu);
 - Nickel (Ni).
- Reported exclusively by 7.(b) facilities:
 - Cadmium (Cd);
 - Phenols;
 - Lead (Pb).

2.3 Review per method

In the Industrial Reporting Database (European Industrial Emissions Portal, 2025), countries must provide information on the method used to assess air and water emissions on a per facility, per year and per pollutant basis. This reporting is structured across three levels of methodological detail:

- **Method**

This is the general category used to determine how emissions are assessed:

- Measured (analytical method used);
- Calculated (calculation method used);
- Estimated (i.e. based on expert judgement or general assumptions).

- **Method classification**

This level provides more details about the method, for example:

- Mass balance method.

The full list of available classifications is provided in [Annex 4](#).

- **Further details on the method**

This optional field allows free-text clarification. The level of details varies widely:

- For measurement methods, it may include the exact standard used (e.g. ISO or national binding reference);
- For calculation methods, it might reference the source of the calculation (e.g. the scientific article publication or guideline);
- In some cases, no additional detail is provided.

Overview of Method reporting for 7.(a) facilities

Between 2017 and 2023, a total of 34 emissions to water values were reported from 7.(a) facilities.

These represent emissions from:

- Seven poultry farms;
- 24 pig farms;
- Three unspecified farms.

Among the 34 values:

- 30 values have a method specification (Measurement, Calculations or Estimation);
- Only 18 provide further detail on the method.

This limited level of detail, particularly at the third reporting level, hampers a consistent understanding and comparison of emission assessment approaches across countries. Moreover, the lack of harmonisation in the level and quality of the information reported suggests that national interpretation and application of reporting requirements may vary considerably.

For 7.(b) facilities, a total of 2,817 emissions to water values were reported for the last seven years. Of these:

- 2,613 values (circa 93%) specify the type of method (Measurement, Calculations or Estimation);
- However, only 197 values, (circa 7%) include any further detail on the method used.

Figure 2.3 below shows the distribution of method types used by each country to assess emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities over the last seven years:

- By country;
- By pollutant;
- By method type:
 - Calculations - shown in blue;
 - Estimation - shown in in pink;
 - Measurement - shown in in yellow.

Additionally, a comprehensive historical overview of method used from 2007 to 2023 for all countries reporting, is provided in [Annex 5](#).

Figure 2.3: Distribution of responses on the method used by facilities to assess emissions to water from 2017 to 2023, per activity, per country and per pollutant

		Distribution of responses on the method used by facilities, according to the country and the pollutant concerned (a)									
		N	P	TOC	Phenols	Zn	Cu	As	Ni	Cd	Pb
7.(a)(i) facilities	Bulgaria	2	2	2							
	Hungary				1						
7.(a)(ii) facilities	Bulgaria	8	2	9	2						
	Hungary		1								
	Romania				1						
	Sweden	1									
7.(a)(?) facilities	Bulgaria					1				1	1
7.(b) facilities	Cyprus	28	5	29	5						
	Spain	13	10	65	14	1	2	1			
	France	1	1	2	1	1	1				
	Greece	1	10	1	10						
	Iceland	24	19	25	19				1		
	Malta	3	2	13	3	2	13	1	5		
	Norway	431		617	617		617	54			
	Poland								3	3	
	Sweden	12	4	12	2						

Legend: Calculated: calculation method used
 Measured: analytical method used
 Estimated
 ND: no data on the method

Notes: (a) Each number represents the number of times a facility responded using this method.
 Source: Author’s compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025.

Based on the available data, **the majority of pollutants are assessed through calculations**, although it seems that some facilities, e.g. from Iceland, Spain and Sweden, rely also on measurements or estimations. Interestingly, all the facilities from Norway, which includes 617 facilities, used only calculations to assess emissions to water for five different pollutants: N, P, TOC, Zn and Cu.

For further details, the use of terms ‘calculations’, ‘estimation’ and ‘measurement’ need to be analysed. To do this, it is also necessary to examine the chosen ‘method classification’ and the ‘further details’ given by the reporters in the database.

Figure 2.4 below shows the distribution of details given towards the methodology used to assess emissions to water during the last seven years, per country and per activity.

Figure 2.4: Distribution of details on the method used by facilities to assess emissions to water from 2017 to 2023, per country and per activity

Notes: E= Estimated, M= Measured, C= Calculated, ND=No data on the method used.
 Source: Author’s compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025.

Regarding the 7.(a) facilities:

Only Romania and Bulgaria provided further details on their methods. Romania specified the exact measurement standard and the use of a European-wide sector specific calculation method. However, Bulgaria did not specify what their ‘specific calculation method’ entails, which reveals a gap. This has been addressed in the questionnaire and is explained further in Section 3.4.

Regarding the 7.(b) facilities:

Responses were more varied, with several countries referring to different calculation methods:

- Cyprus and Poland use mass balance;
- Spain uses emission factors;
- Malta uses food conversion ratio;
- France and Spain use measurement data (e.g. measured flow);
- Some references to scientific sources were made.

Only France and Spain mentioned the use of direct measurements. It is worth noting that detailed information on method was provided by only 7% of the total emissions to water reported over the last seven years.

Swedish 7.(b) facilities referenced only one source, *Fiskodling, planering, tillstånd, tillsyn (Fish farming, planning, permits, supervision)* which was published in 1993 by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency.

Iceland cited a Norwegian scientific study by Wang X. et al., *Discharge of nutrient wastes from salmon farms: environmental effects, and potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture*, published in *Aquaculture Environment Interactions* in 2013. Interestingly, this article is not cited by Norway, despite the country providing method details for its 617 facilities.

Further information on both these sources is provided in the Section 4.3 of this report.

The same analytical approach can be applied for each pollutant. Figure 2.5 below shows the level of detail provided on the methods used to assess emissions into water over the last seven years, broken down by pollutant and activity.

Figure 2.5: Distribution of details on the method used by facilities to assess emissions to water from 2017 to 2023, per pollutant and per activity

Note: E= Estimated, M= Measured, C= Calculated, ND=No data on the method used.
 Source: Author’s compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025.

For most pollutants, the information provided on the methods used was limited. This is part because emissions to water have been reported infrequently. Interestingly, Zn and TOC have each been reported approximately 600 times over the last seven years, yet there is almost no accompanying detail on the methodologies used by either 7.(a) or 7.(b) facilities.

Regarding 7.(a) facilities:

For 7.(a) facilities, method details are only available for phenols, P and N. Even then, the information provided is not particularly detailed. For instance, the reporting for P and N often refers vaguely to a "European-wide sector specific calculation method". The lack of clarity has been investigated further through the questionnaires.

Regarding 7.(b) facilities:

For 7.(b) facilities, particularly with regard to N and P, the responses include a broader mix of methods. These range from mass balance and emission factors to food conversion ratio and flow-based

calculations from measurement data. Additionally, Sweden and Iceland referenced two scientific studies. However, it is important to note that over 90% of the N and P emissions reported by 7.(b) facilities have no accompanying method details. Therefore, the available information likely does not represent the range or prevalence of methodologies actually used.

2.4 Conclusion

Despite the known presence of relevant facilities, the limited reporting of emissions to water raises important questions about the consistency and completeness of the data. Notably, more than half of the countries with 7.(a) and 7.(b) facilities do not report emissions to water, despite most of these facilities reporting emissions to air. This raises important questions:

- Are emissions to water genuinely below the reporting thresholds?
- If so, how have facilities verified this?
- Is the absence of data due to a lack of an established method or other reasons?

From 2007 to 2023, only nine countries reported emissions to water from both poultry, pig and sow farms, and from aquaculture facilities. In the last seven years, this number has dropped to just four countries for 7.(a) facilities while remaining the same for 7.(b) facilities. This decline highlights the need to better understand current reporting practices and determine whether it reflects real changes in emissions, shifts in methodology, or changes in how facilities operate.

Details on how emissions are calculated remain scarce. Although aquaculture facilities generally provide more information than pig and poultry farms, transparency remains widespread across these activities.

The Industrial Reporting Database categorises the methods used to assess emissions to water into three groups:

- **Measurements and analysis:**
This includes emissions based on direct measurement using national or EU standards. These approaches tend to be the most robust, yet they appear to be underused or underreported.
- **Estimations:**
Some emissions are reported as estimates, but the database does not explain the basis for these figures. Without knowing what these estimates rely on, it is difficult to assess their reliability.
- **Calculations:**
A variety of calculation methods have been referenced, including:
 - Mass balance;
 - Emission factors;
 - Food conversion ratio (which often includes an excretion component);
 - Calculations from measurement data such as flow and concentration;
 - Scientific studies, particularly those using mass balance approaches.

It seems that emissions to water from aquaculture facilities are mainly assessed by calculation methods. In contrast, based on the limited number of values within the database - only nine poultry, pig and sow farms have reported emissions in the last seven years, from these three countries: Bulgaria, Hungary and Romania- the few data points for poultry, pig and sow farms, are based on measurements. However, both Bulgaria and Sweden have also reported using estimates or calculation methods.

This variation suggests that a single, common methodology for both types of activities may not be practicable or appropriate.

Even within the same country and activity, the methods used can differ. Currently, it is supposedly up to the operators to report their emissions to the competent authorities in their country, and this data is then transmitted by each country. The method used to determine emissions is therefore specific to each operator. The variability of responses within the same country suggests that there is likely no national guidance or regulation requiring a specific methodology. Only Sweden cited a guide called Fiskodling, planering, tillstånd, tillsyn (Fish farming, planning, permits, supervision), which was published by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency but has since been officially repealed.

Furthermore, the scope of the emissions in the database remains unclear, specifically which sources are included. It is not specified whether emissions from sources such as wash water from cleaning buildings and storages, wastewater treatment of exhaust gases, manure run-off, excess nutrients or animal faeces are covered. This level of detail is essential for accurately interpreting the data and must be clarified by the reporters in each country.

In conclusion, as detailed in Chapter 3, additional information and, most importantly, more precise information has been requested from the Member States reporting emissions to water from aquaculture facilities and/or poultry, pig and sow farms. This will help to ensure greater transparency, consistency and comparability of the data reported under the Industrial Reporting framework for these activities.

3 Feedback from Member States

3.1 Questionnaire

3.1.1 Selection of countries

Following a review of the Industrial Reporting Database (European Industrial Emissions Portal, 2025), it was decided to contact all 27 EU Member States as well as two non-EU countries: Iceland and Norway, regarding their reporting of emissions to water.

Based on the information available in the database, the 29 countries were grouped into five categories according to whether they have 7.(a) and/or 7.(b) facilities, and whether these facilities reported emissions to air and/or water:

- Group 1: Countries reporting both air and water emissions from 7.(a) facilities and emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities;
- Group 2: Countries reporting emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities but not from 7.(a) facilities;
- Group 3: Countries reporting both air and water emissions from 7.(a) facilities;
- Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities;
- Group 5: Countries not reporting any emissions (air or water) from 7.(b) facilities.

Table 3.1 below shows which countries are included in each group.

Table 3.1: Countries included within each group

Group	Countries
Group 1	Iceland, Spain, Sweden
Group 2	Cyprus, France, Greece, Malta, Norway, Poland
Group 3	Bulgaria, Hungary, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia
Group 4	Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Slovakia
Group 5	Croatia

In order to gather more detailed and consistent information, a questionnaire was sent to each of the 29 countries. The questionnaire covered a range of topics, including:

- Methodologies used to assess emissions;
- Scope of emissions;
- Use of national guidance;
- Use of emission factors databases;
- Treatment of uncertainties in reported data;
- Reasons for not reporting emissions to water where applicable.

Separate sets of questions were provided for poultry, pig and/or sow farms and for aquaculture facilities, to reflect the differences in practices between these activities.

For countries that had already provided some methodological details in the Industrial Reporting Database, targeted questions were added to clarify and expand on the information provided.

The full list of questions can be found in [Annex 6](#).

19 of the 29 countries contacted responded to the questionnaire (65.5%). These included:

- Group 1: Sweden;
- Group 2: Cyprus, France, Greece, Norway;
- Group 3: Bulgaria, Romania;
- Group 4: Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Slovakia;
- Group 5: Croatia.

Section 3.4 provides an analysis of the responses to the questionnaire, and [Annex 7](#) contains the statistical data.

3.2 Interviews

In-depth interviews were conducted with stakeholders from Iceland and Norway, based on the responses to the questionnaire, in order to gain a clearer understanding of the methodologies used to calculate emissions to water from aquaculture facilities.

An interview with Sweden was deemed unnecessary as their responses to the questionnaire were already sufficient. Although an interview with Malta had been planned, this was not possible as Maltese reporters did not respond to the request.

No interviews were conducted regarding emissions to water from intensive livestock production, although Romania and Bulgaria provided additional inputs when requested by email in September 2025.

The information gathered during the interviews and additional inputs from Romania and Bulgaria are included in the analysis of Section 3.4 and statistical data in [Annex 7](#).

3.3 Consultation with Member States on this report

A provisional version of this report was submitted to Member States for consultation between 23 July and 5 September 2025, gathering feedback from the following countries: Austria, Czechia, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Poland, Romania, Spain and Sweden.

Details of the consultation feedback, the author's responses and the resulting amendments to the report can be found in [Annex 8](#).

In particular, the following countries provided additional details on the methods used to calculate emissions into water from intensive aquaculture and intensive livestock production activities: Estonia, Finland, Spain and Sweden.

The information gathered during the consultation is included in the analysis of Section 3.4 and statistical data in [Annex 7](#).

3.4 Analysis of data from questionnaires, interviews and consultation

Taking into account the feedback from the questionnaires, the interviews and the consultation with Member States, a total of 21 countries provided data on their methodology:

- Group 1: Iceland, Spain, Sweden;
- Group 2: Cyprus, France, Greece, Norway;

- Group 3: Bulgaria, Romania;
- Group 4: Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Slovakia;
- Group 5: Croatia.

Most responses came from countries that had **not** reported any emissions to water over the last seven years, likely because their version of the questionnaire contained only one question whereas others received a more detailed set of questions.

Of the four countries that have previously reported or currently report emissions to water from their poultry and pig farms, three countries — Bulgaria, Romania and Sweden — provided data. For aquaculture facilities, seven out of nine countries responded: Cyprus, France, Greece, Iceland, Norway, Spain and Sweden.

Overall, there was significant variation in responses between countries for both intensive livestock production and aquaculture. Even the reasons given for not report emissions to water varied widely.

Regarding 7.(a) facilities:

- **Method used:**
Emissions to water are mainly calculated using measured concentrations and volumes (Bulgaria and Romania). In Sweden, calculations are based on expert judgement rather than direct measurements.
- **Regulatory framework:**
None of the responding countries indicated the existence, let alone use, of a national guide or regulation for calculating emissions into water.
- **Uncertainty of emissions:**
Bulgaria and Romania, where emissions are calculated using sampling and analysis, reported that uncertainties come from these measurement processes. In Sweden, the level of uncertainty is not specified.
- **Scope of emissions:**
The type and scope of emissions to water differ across countries:
 - Bulgaria and Romania only report point source emissions;
 - Sweden reports only diffuse emissions.

Similarly, the source of emission varies:

- Emissions often originate from water used for cleaning buildings (Bulgaria and Romania);
- Manure run-off is a common source in all three countries (Bulgaria, Romania and Sweden);
- In Romania, emissions are also linked to slaughter activities, as the reporting facility includes this process;
- In Bulgaria, rainwater and domestic sewage are also sometimes taken into account.

The fate of liquid effluents produced on site varies:

- Liquid effluents are either pumped to an on-site treatment facility (Romania) or sent to a lagoon or watertight tank and then to an off-site water treatment facility (Romania) or a biogas production plant (Bulgaria).
- Solid manure is spread on agricultural land.
- Wastewater from cleaning can be collected through sewage system, stored in tanks and spread with manure on agricultural land (Bulgaria and Romania).

- **Reporting of emissions:**

In Romania, natural or legal persons independent of the facility operator certified by professional associations in the field of environmental protection, may complete emission reports on behalf of operators.

In Bulgaria, some operators outsource emissions calculations to external companies, while others carry out their own calculations.

The reported data may include a wide range of information depending on the country and activity type, such as volume of water discharged, number of hours of operation, and pollutant quantities released.

- **Reasons for not reporting emissions:**

The main reason provided by Member States for not reporting emissions to water is that facilities consider they have no direct emissions to water, as all wastewater from cleaning is collected and mixed with slurry and manure via watertight floors, conveyor belts (for poultry), pre-pits (for pigs), gutters and piping. It is then stored in watertight tanks or lagoons before being sent to either a biogas production plant or a wastewater treatment plant (either on-site or off-site) or spread on land as fertiliser. The scope of water releases reporting under Article 5 of the E-PRTR Regulation (EU, 2006) as well as the guidance for the implementation of United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE)'s PRTR protocol focus on direct releases (with diffuse emissions covered by Article 8). Article 6 and recital 9 of the original Regulation excluded land spreading of manure from the scope. Therefore, it seems to be the understanding of Member States reporters that the way wastewater is managed would not lead to emissions reportable as "water releases" as per Article 5 and 7 of the Regulation.

Bulgaria further noted that water discharges are only relevant for pig farms and not poultry farms.

Bulgaria has specified that both pig and poultry farms could transport effluent to a biogas production plant, whereas Estonia and Italy did not specify the type of farm.

Bulgaria has also specified that both pig and poultry farms could transport effluent to a wastewater treatment plant. Romania only mentioned this for pig farms, while Latvia and Slovakia did not specify the type of farm.

Regarding 7.(b) facilities:

- **Method used:**

The most frequently reported method for calculating emissions to water from aquaculture facilities is mass balance. This method was cited by Cyprus, France, Greece, Norway and Sweden, as well as by Estonia and Finland.

- **Source/reference of the method:**

Several of the countries surveyed provided literature references for their methods. These references are analysed in Sections 4.2 and 4.3 as well as in [Annex 9](#).

- Cyprus and Greece cited the same paper: Tsapakis, M., et al., 2006, Nutrients and fine particulate matter released from sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) farming., Aquatic Living Resources.
- Iceland confirmed that the method cited by several Icelandic aquaculture facilities in the Industrial Reporting Database is still in use: Wang, X., et al., 2012, Discharge of nutrient wastes from salmon farms: environmental effects, and potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture, Aquaculture Environment Interactions.
- Spain cited two documents used by Spanish facilities:

- Lupatsch I., et al., 1998, Predicting aquaculture waste from gilthead seabream culture using a nutritional approach, Aquatic Living Resources.
- Vergara Martín, J.M., et al., 2005, Evaluación de impacto ambiental de acuicultura en jaulas en Canarias, Oceanográfica.
- Norway explained that it drew its method from the following document: Borgvang et al., 2000, Development of HARP Guidelines: Harmonised quantification and reporting procedures for nutrients.
- Sweden mentioned the guidelines of the HELCOM.
- Ireland provided two references, which were used by one operator in 2024:
 - Wang, X, et al., 2013, Chemical composition and release rate of waste discharge from an Atlantic salmon farm with an evaluation of IMTA feasibility, Aquaculture Environment Interactions.
 - Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC), 2025, ASC Farm Standard.

- **Regulatory framework:**

Only Sweden referred to having a national guide to support the calculation of emissions to water. The general guidance is titled *Fish Farming - Planning, Permits, Supervision (AR 93:10)*, and is also mentioned in the Industrial Emissions Database (see Section 2.3). Even though this guidance has been repealed since 2019, it is analysed in Section 4.2 as well as in [Annex 9](#).

- **Uncertainty of emissions:**

None of the responding countries provided information regarding the uncertainty associated with their emissions data. Norway and Sweden assume that uncertainty is extremely high, but do not know to what extent.

- **Scope of emissions:**

The type and scope of emissions to water varies by country and activity:

- France reports only point sources emissions;
- Greece reports only diffuse emissions;
- Norway reports both point source and diffuse emissions.

Emission sources typically include: excess nutrients, animal faeces and feed.

- **Reporting of emissions:**

In France, Greece and Norway, aquaculture facility operators are responsible for reporting their own emissions. In Norway, the data used to assess discharges includes the quantity of feed used, fish biomass and stock levels.

- **Reasons for not reporting:**

Croatia stated that its aquaculture facilities do not report emissions to water because they lack the necessary methodology to do so. Conversely, Estonia explained that although they have a methodology in place, none of their aquaculture facilities currently exceed the reporting thresholds for emissions into water.

3.5 Synthesis of feedback from Member States and from the Industrial Reporting Database

[Annex 10](#) provides data sheets for all 32 countries covered by this study, i.e. the EU 27 as well as Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, Serbia and Switzerland. The data sheets summarise information from the Industrial Reporting Database, as well as the full responses submitted by the countries through the questionnaires and interviews.

This section focuses specifically on countries that have reported emissions to water from at least one of their poultry farms, pig farms or aquaculture facilities over the last seven years. These countries are Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania, and Sweden (for poultry and pig farms), and Cyprus, France, Greece, Iceland, Malta, Norway, Poland, Spain and Sweden (for aquaculture facilities). Table 3.2 and Table 3.3 below summarise the methods used by these countries, based on the information from the Industrial Reporting Database, as well as questionnaire responses and interview data. In addition, although these two countries have not reported any emissions to water from their aquaculture facilities in the last seven years due to the thresholds, Estonia and Finland have been included in Table 3.3 as they have provided relevant information for comparison with the methods used by other countries.

Table 3.2: Synthesis of method used to assess emissions to water for poultry and/ or pig farms

Country	Facilities reporting emissions to water (2017-2023)	Feedback (questionnaire, interview and/or consultation)	Main method used to assess emissions to water?	Details provided?	Possibility of proposing the method to all Member States
Bulgaria	2 poultry farms, 2 pig farms and 1 unspecified farm	Yes: questionnaire	Measurement and calculations based on measurement	<p>Formula: $P = D \times Q \times 10^{-3}$</p> <p>Where: P (kg/year) – emissions in wastewater, D (m³/year) – wastewater flow rate for the given year, measured with a flowmeter; Q (mg/dm³) – measured amount of pollutant during own monitoring /average value of the indicator from all measurements.</p>	Not relevant since based on a measurement rather than a calculation methodology
Hungary	1 poultry farm and 1 pig farm	No	Measurement	No	Not possible due to lack of details
Romania	1 pig farm	Yes: questionnaire and consultation	Measurement of concentrations of target substances in wastewater streams and volume of wastewater	<p>Formula: $M_r = V_r \times C_r \times 10^{-6}$</p> <p>Where: M_r (kg) – real mass of pollutant, V_r (mL)– real volume of wastewater, C_r (mg/mL) – real concentration of pollutant in wastewater. The facility that has reported emissions to water also carries out slaughtering activities, the emissions to water are also due to this activity.</p>	Not relevant since based on a measurement rather than a calculation methodology
Sweden	1 pig farm	Yes: questionnaire	Expert judgement	No	Not possible due to lack of details

Besides measurement, no relevant methodology has emerged from the database or the questionnaires to assess emission to water for poultry and pig farms.

Table 3.3: Synthesis of method used to assess emissions to water for aquaculture facilities

Country	Facilities reporting emissions to water (2017-2023)	Feedback (questionnaire, interview and/or consultation)	Main method used to assess emissions to water?	Details provided?	Possibility of proposing the method to all Member States
Cyprus	5 facilities	Yes: questionnaire	Mass balance involving composition of feed	Source provided but not the formula or the default values. See Section 4.3.1 for more details.	Not possible due to lack of details
Estonia	0 facility	Yes: questionnaire and consultation	Mass balance involving composition of feed and fish	Formula: Discharge = [(Nfeed × Mfeed) – (Nfish × Mfish)] / 100% Where: Nfeed – the % of N in the feed; Nfish – the % of N in the fish; Mfeed – the used amount of feed (kg); Mfish – the amount of produced fish (kg) No default value has been provided. See Section 4.3.2 for more details.	Possible
Finland	0 facility	Yes: questionnaire and consultation	Equation involving composition of feed and fish	No formula has been provided. Default values provided for N and P for feed composition, fish composition and food conversion ratio in Annex 9 .	Not possible due to lack of details
France	1 facility	Yes: questionnaire	Mass balance involving the proportion of nutrients excreted/rejected, feed ratio and body retention associated with zootechnical performance	No, neither the formula, nor the default values	Not possible due to lack of details
Greece	3 facilities	Yes: questionnaire	Mass balance involving composition of feed	Source provided but not the formula or the default values. See Section 4.3.1 for more details.	Not possible due to lack of details
Iceland	13 facilities	Yes: interview	Mass balance involving composition of feed	Formula: Discharge = Feed × W × Y × F1 + Feed × W × Y × F2 Where: Discharge is the total loss of pollutant (N or P) to the environment (kg/year), Feed is the amount of feed used (kg/year), W is the Dry weight of feed (%), Y is the percentage of pollutant in feed, F1 is the percentage of particulate pollutant and F2 is the percentage of dissolved pollutant Default values provided for N and P for parameters F1 and F2 in Annex 9 . See Section 4.3.1 for more details.	Possible

Country	Facilities reporting emissions to water (2017-2023)	Feedback (questionnaire, interview and/or consultation)	Main method used to assess emissions to water?	Details provided?	Possibility of proposing the method to all Member States
Malta	3 facilities	No	Food conversion ratio	No, neither the formula, nor the default values	Not possible due to lack of details
Norway	617 facilities	Yes: questionnaire and interview	For sea-based aquaculture: Mass balance involving composition of feed and fish For land-based aquaculture: Measurement	Formula: Discharge = C1 × Feed - C2 × Feed / FCR Where: Discharge is the total loss of pollutant (N or P) to the environment (kg/year), C1 is the feed composition (% of pollutant in feed), C2 is the fish composition (% of pollutant in fish), Feed is the amount of feed used that year (kg/year) and FCR is a food conversion ratio. Default values provided for N, P and TOC for parameters C1 and C2, and for salmon and trout for parameter FCR in Annex 9 . See Section 4.3.2 for more details.	Possible
Poland	1 facility	No	Mass balance	No, neither the formula, nor the default values	Not possible due to lack of details
Spain	25 facilities	Yes: consultation	For land-based aquaculture: Mainly measurements For sea-based aquaculture: Equation involving feed composition	Sources provided but not the formula or the default values. See Section 4.3.1 for more details.	Not possible due to lack of details
Sweden	3 facilities	Yes: questionnaire and consultation	Mass balance involving composition of feed and fish	Formula: Discharge = P × (FK × CP - CR) Where: Discharge is the total loss to the environment of phosphorus or nitrogen (kg × 10 /year), P is net fish production (tonne/year), FK is the feed conversion ratio (feed used in tonnes / fish production in tonnes), CP is the pollutant concentration in the feed (%), and CR is the pollutant concentration in fish biomass (%). Default values provided for N and P for parameters FK, CP and CR in Annex 9 . See Section 4.3.2 for more details.	Possible

Norway and Spain were the only countries to differentiate between land-based and sea-based aquaculture facilities in their responses.

For land-based installations, the only method mentioned was measurement.

For sea-based facilities, most countries that have reported emissions to water from aquaculture facilities over the last seven years use a mass balance / equation method, typically based on feed composition and in some cases, fish composition.

However, only Iceland, Norway and Sweden provided detailed methodological information, including source, formula and default values, through the questionnaire and/or interviews. Cyprus, Greece and Spain provided the source, Finland only the default values and Estonia only the formula.

Therefore, the following chapter focuses on the methodology used in Cyprus, Estonia, Greece, Iceland, Norway, Spain and Sweden, providing a comparative analysis of their approaches to support the selection of a common methodology to be proposed.

4 Review of methodologies for calculating releases to water

This chapter provides a review of existing guidance and methodologies for estimating emissions into water from the livestock and aquaculture activities. The analysis is based on information in the Industrial Reporting Database, as well as on responses to the questionnaire and interviews with Member States.

Section 4.1, which addresses atmospheric emissions, has been included for comparative purposes, to provide context for emissions to water and to highlight relevant insights from the literature. Atmospheric emissions are not the main focus of this study, as the EEA's approach is to recommend the already existing methodologies in the EMEP/EEA air emissions inventory guidebook (air pollutants, EEA, 2023a) and the IPCC methodologies (GHG).

The objective of this chapter is to identify the available data and methodologies related to emissions to water from livestock farming and aquaculture, with a particular focus on outlining the methodological limitations.

4.1 Comparison with guidance for calculating air emissions and lessons learned

Unlike emissions to water, atmospheric emissions from livestock farms have been monitored and documented for many years. Several guides exist for estimating air emissions, the most notable of which is the EMEP/EEA air emissions inventory guidebook (EEA, 2023a, ¹⁹) which is widely used in the EU. The guidebook is structured into sector-specific sections, including agriculture (3.B Manure management) and aims to support countries in compiling national inventories of air pollutant emissions.

It provides pollutant-specific emission factors for different industrial activities and categorises estimation methodologies into three tiers:

- Tier 1 is a basic approach using default emission factors based on livestock numbers and standard management practices;
- Tier 2 is a more refined method incorporating specific data on animal management systems, distinguishing between slurry and solid manure systems, to estimate emissions (this can be country-specific);
- Tier 3 is an advanced installation-level modelling approach that accounts for detailed variables such as climate and livestock behaviour, providing the highest level of accuracy.

Based on feedback from the establishment of the IED's UCOL, most countries use Tier 3 to estimate air emissions from pig and poultry farms. The common European approach involves an integrated assessment at each stage of the manure/slurry management chain, combining emission factors and activity data such as the number of animals and the type of housing. Several Member States have developed tools to enable farmers to calculate these emissions.

Other scientific documents, such as the Guidance on the Conversion of Gaseous Emission Units to Standardised Emission Factors (Webb et al., 2021), highlight the importance of using standardised emission factors, particularly in terms of units. They also emphasise the need for validated references, such as scientific studies, to define emission factors.

⁽¹⁹⁾ The EEA will always recommend the use of the latest version of the guidebook. At the time of writing this was the 2023 version, but it is updated every 4-5 years.

4.2 Existing guidance for calculating emissions to water: literature review

A review was conducted to identify documents describing emissions from livestock farms and aquaculture facilities, as well as guidebooks outlining methods and emission factors.

The following four documents were deemed relevant for further analysis:

- The 2022 report by the European Topic Centre on Inland, Coastal and Marine Waters: *'Calculating emissions to water – a simplified method'* ⁽²⁰⁾,
- The 2022 guidelines report by HELCOM: *'HELCOM Guidelines for the annual and periodical compilation and reporting of waterborne pollution inputs to the Baltic Sea'* ⁽²¹⁾,
- The 2015 guidelines report by OSPAR: *'Guidelines for Harmonised Quantification and Reporting Procedures for Nutrients (HARP-NUT) - Guideline 2: Quantification and Reporting of Nitrogen and Phosphorus Discharges/losses from Aquaculture Plants'* ⁽²²⁾,
- The 2025 report by the Aquaculture Stewardship Council: *'ASC Farm Standard'* ⁽²³⁾.

4.2.1 Review of the document *'Calculating emissions to water – a simplified method'*

The 2022 report by the European Topic Centre on Inland, Coastal and Marine Waters, *'Calculating emissions to water – a simplified method'*, aims to provide methodologies for those preparing inventories of emissions to water, in the same way that the EMEP guidebook does for air emissions. Thus, it covers both direct and diffuse releases. The report covers several economic activities including agriculture, and proposes calculation and modelling methods, such as emission factors, depending on the emission source and type. However, its applicability may be limited to poultry or pig farms, with no relevance to aquaculture facilities.

The report describes 13 primary pathways through which pollutants are emitted to surface waters. Each pathway is linked to specific pollutant and sources and provides a calculation method. These methods typically involve multiplying an activity rate (e.g. population, agricultural land area, vehicle kilometres, etc.) by an emission factor to estimate pollutant load per unit of activity.

Unlike the EMEP/EEA guidebook, this document does not provide a standardised set of emission factors that countries could use for national inventories.

Also, in the case of “agriculture” the methodology focuses on diffuse sources of emissions from farms such as run-off from unsealed surfaces or erosion, similarly to what was done in the 2013 project report from Deltares *'Diffuse water emissions in E-PRTR'* ⁽²⁴⁾ for the estimation of diffuse emissions to water under E-PRTR.

Moreover, based on the findings from Chapters 2 and 3, the majority of countries report that pig and poultry farms do not discharge directly to water. Therefore, this report provides limited practical value in developing a harmonised approach to estimating emissions to water in the context of this study.

⁽²⁰⁾ <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-icm/products/etc-icm-reports/calculating-emissions-to-water-a-simplified-method>

⁽²¹⁾ <https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/HELCOM-PLC-Water-Guidelines-2022.pdf>

⁽²²⁾ <https://www.ospar.org/documents?d=32688>

⁽²³⁾ <https://programme-centre.asc-aqua.org/app/uploads/2025/08/ASC-STD-001-ASC-Farm-Standard-V1.0.1-Aug-2025.pdf>

⁽²⁴⁾ https://industry.eea.europa.eu/files/report_diffuse_water.pdf/@@download/file

4.2.2 Review of the documents ‘HELCOM Guidelines for the annual and periodical compilation and reporting of waterborne pollution inputs to the Baltic Sea’ and ‘Guidelines for Harmonised Quantification and Reporting Procedures for Nutrients (HARP-NUT) - Guideline 2: Quantification and Reporting of Nitrogen and Phosphorus Discharges/losses from Aquaculture Plants’

The 2022 report by the Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission, ‘HELCOM Guidelines for the annual and periodical compilation and reporting of waterborne pollution inputs to the Baltic Sea’, aims to provide a framework for national monitoring, quantification and reporting of total waterborne inputs of nitrogen, phosphorus and selected hazardous substances, as well as their sources, in order to obtain a harmonised and comparable dataset covering the entire Baltic Sea region.

The report covers several point sources, including municipal wastewater treatment plants, industrial plants and aquaculture plants. It is not relevant to poultry or pig farms. The chapter on aquaculture proposes three approaches to quantify discharges from aquaculture plants. These focus on discharges of undigested nitrogen and phosphorus, which come from the feed supplied to the farming system and are excreted via gills and urine. Thus, the cultivation of mussels and other species that are not given feed by the operators are not covered in this guideline. It should be noted that this omission does not affect the proposed methodology of this report, since the scope of the aquaculture activity in the IEPR refers to “feed-based aquaculture”, excluding other species that are not fed by their operators such as mussels.

The report includes a chapter (5.3) dedicated to the quantification of load from point sources in aquaculture facilities. This chapter and the three mathematical approaches described are derived from the OSPAR guidelines, in particular the 2015 report ‘Guidelines for Harmonised Quantification and Reporting Procedures for Nutrients (HARP-NUT) - Guideline 2: Quantification and Reporting of Nitrogen and Phosphorus Discharges/losses from Aquaculture Plants’.

Thus, the two reports distinguish between the following:

- Plants without treatment (e.g. plants where the sludge is not collected or where the sludge is collected, but discharged into the aquatic environment untreated);
- Plants with treatment e.g. plants with permanent removal of sludge), where the N and P contents (and organic matter) in the removed sludge are quantified.

The three proposed approaches are as follows:

- Approach 1 is based on calculations from production parameters. The starting point is that information on both production and feed consumption is available at plant level. The quantification method is based on mass balance equations. This approach is valid for both marine and freshwater aquaculture plants.
- Approach 2 is also based on calculations from production parameters, but in this case, only information on either production or feed is available at national level. This approach is valid for both marine and freshwater aquaculture plants.
- Approach 3 is based on monitoring the discharge. It is feasible for ponds or other land-based production systems where the discharges are distinct point discharges (such as end of pipe/channel). The quantification of losses is also based on mass balance equations, but in this case on monitoring results. This approach is only valid for freshwater aquaculture plants.

For approach 1, the formula is:

$$\text{Discharge} = (0.01 \times (I \times C_i - G \times C_f)) - M - T - S$$

Where:

- Discharge is the total discharge of N or P to water body (kg/year);
- I is the amount of feed used for feeding of fish (kg/year);
- C_i is the P or N content in feed (%);
- G is the net growth of fish including dead fish (kg/year), calculated as $G = D + O + E + (S_f - S_i)$, where:
 - D is the quantity of dead organisms collected during the year (kg/year);
 - O is the quantity of organisms taken out of the water for slaughter (alternatively the sum of slaughter weight and slaughter offal) or sold alive (kg/year);
 - E is the quantity of escaped organisms (kg/year);
 - S_f and S_i are respectively the standing stock by the end of the year and the beginning of the year (kg/year).
- C_f is the P or N content in fish (%);
- M is the nutrient losses due to metabolism in fish (kg/year);
- T is the nutrient removal processes on the fish farm not related to sludge removal (e.g. nutrient turnover, denitrification etc.) (kg/year);
- S is the amount of P or N removed with the sludge (kg/year), only applicable for plants with treatment.

The total nitrogen and phosphorus content of the feed can be obtained from the feed manufacturers.

According to approach 2, if national registers on feed use and production on individual plants are unavailable, national sales statistics could be used instead.

Moreover, if either I or G are unavailable at plant level, it can be calculated using the feed conversion ratio (FCR), according to the following formula and then used in the formula from the first approach.

$$\text{FCR} = \frac{I}{G}$$

The FCR is species dependent and varies by water temperature, as the fish metabolism is temperature dependent. Hence, it is preferred to use FCRs specific for the actual catchment or region based on estimates obtained from literature or determined from experimental work.

Like the EMEP/EEA guidebook, these two documents provide a set of values that countries could use for national inventories: C_i and C_f for several types of feed or fish, as well as FCR for salmonid fish production only. These default values are presented in [Annex 9](#).

Unlike approach 1, this formula is better suited to determining emissions based on national data, so it can only be used by national reporters in the Industrial Emissions Portal.

Finally, approach 3 proposes a formula based on measurements:

$$L = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_i \times C_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_i} \times Q_t \times 10^{-6}$$

Where:

- L is the annual load (kg/year);
- Q_i is the wastewater volume of the period i (m^3);
- C_i is the concentration of sample i ($\mu g/L$);
- Q_t is the total wastewater volume of the year ($m^3/year$);
- N is the number of sampling periods.

Approach 3 is specific to land-based facilities, and aligns with the feedback from Norway and Spain, which specified in their questionnaires that their land-based facilities use measurement to determine their emissions into water, in contrast to sea-based facilities.

The HELCOM guidelines are updated whenever a new Pollution Load Compilation project begins, with no fixed frequency. National experts then meet to discuss various issues, including whether the quantification of inputs from aquaculture is still sufficient or whether newer, better methods are available.

4.2.3 Review of the document 'ASC Farm Standard'

The 2025 report by the Aquaculture Standard Council, 'ASC Farm Standard', aims to provide a global sustainability standard that defines the requirements for seafood production in aquaculture grow-out farms. The standard applies to various farming systems (cages, ponds, recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS)) and types of water (freshwater, brackish water, marine water). It provides a detailed list of eligible species (fish, molluscs and crustaceans).

The report includes several appendices, one of which is dedicated to calculating nitrogen and phosphorus emissions in water: Appendix 8.2.

This appendix provides four formulas for calculating the load of nitrogen and phosphorus into waterbodies:

- Formula 1 is based on mass balance and applies to sites releasing diffuse source effluents;
- Formula 2 is based on measurements and applies to pond-based sites with point-source effluents discharging directly to waterbodies;
- Formula 3 is also based on measurements and applies to pond-based sites that have some form of effluent treatment;
- Formula 4 is based on default values and applies to some land-based sites that discharge to waterbodies that do not need to record effluent water quality.

Formula 1 is based on mass balance:

$$\text{Discharge} = 0.01 \times F \times C_f - (S_f + H + R - S_i - S_d) \times C_a$$

Where:

- Discharge is the total discharge of N or P to water body (kg/year);
- F is the amount of feed used in dry weight (kg/year);
- C_f is the P or N content in feed (%);

- H is the harvested volume of animals during the year (kg/year);
- R is the other removed volume of animals (kg/year);
- S_f and S_i are respectively the standing stock by the end of the year and the beginning of the year (kg/year);
- S_d is the stocked volume during the year (kg/year);
- C_a is the P or N content in animals (%).

The formula 1 from the ASC Farm Standard appears to be similar to approach 1 from the HELCOM / OSPAR guidelines. However, the ASC document did not provide default values for C_f or C_a.

Formula 2 applies to measurements:

$$\text{Discharge} = (C_e \times V_e - C_i \times V_i) \times 0.001$$

Where:

- Discharge is the total discharge of N or P to water body (kg/year);
- C_e and C_i are respectively the concentration of N or P in effluent and influent (mg/L);
- V_e and V_i are respectively the total annual volume of effluent and influent (m³/year).

Formula 3 applies to measurements:

$$\text{Discharge} = (C_e - C_i) \times V \times E \times d$$

Where:

- Discharge is the total discharge of N or P to water body (kg/year);
- C_e and C_i are respectively the concentration of N or P in effluent and influent (mg/L);
- V is the water volume of all ponds on days in which ponds were operational (m³);
- E is the daily water exchange, i.e. the percentage of the total pond volume of all ponds in production at the site that is renewed each day divided by 100;
- d is the number of days in a year in which ponds were operational.

Finally, formula 4 is based on default values:

$$\text{Discharge} = I \times C$$

Where:

- Discharge is the total discharge of N or P to water body (kg/year);
- I is the total amount of N or P used for feed and fertiliser combined over the year (kg/year);
- C are default values: 0.3 for nitrogen and 0.2 for phosphorus.

The formula 4 is specific to land-based facilities, but unlike approach 3 of the HELCOM / OSPAR guidelines, and information from Norway and Spain, which have indicated that they use measurements to determine emissions into water from these facilities, this document recommends using default percentages of N / P used in feed and fertiliser (20% for P and 30% for N). Furthermore, it is not clear with this approach what is included in emissions into water.

4.3 Existing methodologies used by Member States for calculating emissions to water

This section outlines the methodologies currently used by Member states to calculate emissions to water from aquaculture facilities, based on information from the Industrial Reporting Database, responses to the Member State questionnaire, and interviews conducted with Iceland and Norway. All methodologies rely on mass balance calculations.

However, two different methods emerge for sea-based aquaculture:

- A methodology involving feed, particulate nutrient, biomass and dissolved/excreted nutrient;
- A methodology involving feed, feed composition and fish composition.

The **methodology involving feed, particulate nutrient, biomass and dissolved/excreted nutrient** is used by at least the following countries:

- Cyprus and Greece: Their methodology is based on the document '*Nutrients and fine particulate matter released from sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) farming*': a paper by M. Tsapakis, P. Pitta and I. Karakassis, published in 2006 in Aquatic Living Resources. This method estimates nitrogen and phosphorus emissions from sea bass farms into water and was cited by Cyprus and Greece.
- Iceland: The methodology is based on the paper '*Discharge of nutrient wastes from salmon farms: environmental effects, and potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture*': a paper by X. Wang, L. Olsen, K. Reitan and Y. Olsen, published in 2012 by Aquaculture Environment Interactions. This method estimates the emissions of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus from Norwegian salmon farms into water and has been cited by several Icelandic aquaculture facilities in the Industrial Reporting Database. This was further explained during the interview with Iceland.
- Spain: Spanish operators use two documents to estimate nitrogen and phosphorus excretions:
 - One is for sea bream farming and is titled '*Predicting aquaculture waste from gilthead seabream culture using a nutritional approach*', a paper by I. Lupatsch and G. Wm. Kissil, published in 1998 in Aquatic Living Resources.
 - The other is for both sea bass and sea bream farming: '*Evaluación de impacto Ambiental de acuicultura en jaulas en Canarias*', a paper by J.M. Vergara Martín, R. Haroun Tabraue, M.N. González Henríquez, L. Molina Domínguez, M.O. Briz Miquel, A. Boyra López, L. Gutiérrez Martínez de Marañón and A. Ballesta Méndez, published in 2005 by Oceanográfica.

The **methodology involving feed, feed composition and fish composition** is used by at least the following countries:

- Estonia: The source was not provided but the given formula allows Estonian facilities to assess N and P emissions into water.
- Norway: The methodology is based on the 2000 document by S.-A. Borgvang and J.R. Selvik: '*Development of HARP Guidelines: Harmonised quantification and reporting procedures for nutrients*', which provides formulas for calculating emissions to water from fish farms, based on guidelines from HELCOM and OSPAR.
- Sweden: Sweden used the guide '*Fiskodling, planering, tillstånd, tillsyn*', published by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency (Naturvårdsverket) in 1993, but was repealed in 2019. This regulatory guideline covers fish farm planning, licensing and environmental compliance. It was cited by several Swedish aquaculture facilities and detailed in Sweden's questionnaire response.

4.3.1 Methodology involving feed, particulate nutrient, biomass and dissolved/excreted nutrient (Cyprus, Greece, Iceland, Spain)

The four documents cited by Cyprus and Greece (Tsapakis et al., 2006), by Iceland (Wang et al., 2012) and by Spain (Lupatsch et al., 1998; Vergara et al., 2005) emphasise that nutrient waste from fish farms is released as dissolved inorganic compounds (e.g. CO₂, NH₃) or particulate organic matter originating from uneaten feed and faecal matter, as illustrated in Figure 4.1. These documents provide methodologies for assessing nitrogen and phosphorus discharges into water from fish farming, involving feed, particulate nutrient, biomass and dissolved/excreted nutrient.

The general formula is:

$$I = A + F = G + E + F$$

Where:

- I is food intake;
- A is assimilated food (the part that is digested by fish and taken up in tissues);
- F is defecation (the part from food waste that is not digested and eliminated from the digestive tract as faeces);
- G is growth (retention in biomass);
- E is excretion (metabolic waste products: urine (NH₃), breathing (CO₂)).

Figure 4.1: Flow and fate of nutrient components from a salmon cage system

Note: Dissolved inorganic nitrogen and phosphorus (DIN and DIP, respectively) are released through excretion, and inorganic carbon (CO₂) through respiration. Particulate organic C, N and P (POC, PON and POP, respectively) are released through defecation and feed loss. Dissolved organic C, N and P (DOC, DON and DOP, respectively) are resuspended from faeces and feed particles.

Source: Wang, X., et al., 2012, Discharge of nutrient wastes from salmon farms: environmental effects, and potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture, *Aquaculture Environment Interactions*, Vol. 2: 267-283.

Through measurements, the four documents provided percentages of nitrogen and phosphorus from feed that: either end up in particulate form, are retained in biomass, or are excreted in dissolved form (both organic and inorganic).

The Table 4.1 shows the percentages given by each document for N and P, specifying the species for which the results were provided.

Table 4.1: Distribution of nutrient flows from feed according to method, species and nutrient

Country using the method	Method / Source	Fish species	Nutrient	Percentage of nutrient supplied through feed			
				Fish retention / Biomass	Particulate (uneaten feed and faeces)	Excretion / Dissolved inorganic	Dissolved organic
Cyprus/Greece	Tsapakis et al., 2006	Sea bass	N	N/A	5-7	N/A	-
Cyprus/Greece	Tsapakis et al., 2006	Sea bass	P	N/A	N/A	13-16	-
Iceland	Wang et al., 2012	Salmon	N	37	15	45	3
Iceland	Wang et al., 2012	Salmon	P	30	44	18	8
Spain	Lupatsch et al., 1998	Sea bream	N	22	10	61	7
Spain	Lupatsch et al., 1998	Sea bream	P	29	44	19	8
Spain	Vergara et al., 2005	Sea bream	N	21	15	65	-
Spain	Vergara et al., 2005	Sea bream	P	30	47	23	-
Spain	Vergara et al., 2005	Sea bass	N	18	20	61	-
Spain	Vergara et al., 2005	Sea bass	P	33	48	20	-

Notes: In the following formula, F1 = Particulate (%), F2 = Dissolved inorganic (%) + dissolved inorganic (%)
N/A means "Data not available / provided in the document"

The main differences between these documents are as follows:

- Fish species: salmon for Iceland, sea bass for Cyprus and Greece, and both sea bass and sea bream for Spain. While the study cited by Iceland (Wang et al., 2012) specifically focuses on salmon farms, Icelandic facilities reportedly apply the methodology to all species of fish, not just salmon, due to the lack of a formula / methodology for other species. This practice was confirmed during the interview with Iceland.
- Climate: mediterranean for Cyprus, Greece and Spain, and oceanic for Iceland.

The formula used by Icelandic facilities and coming from this approach is:

$$\text{Discharge} = 0.01 \times (\text{Feed} \times W \times Y \times F1 + \text{Feed} \times W \times Y \times F2)$$

Where:

- Discharge is the total loss of pollutant (N or P) to the environment (kg/year);
- Feed is the amount of feed used (kg/year);
- W is the dry weight of feed (%);
- Y is the percentage of pollutant in feed (%);
- F1 is the percentage of particulate pollutant (%);
- F2 is the percentage of dissolved pollutant (both organic and inorganic) (%).

With regard to Cyprus, Greece and Spain, it can only be assumed that the same formula is used to calculate emissions from marine aquaculture facilities, the only difference being the default values used for F1 and F2, for each species.

This formula only applies to phosphorus and nitrogen and is not suitable for calculating emissions of metals or TOC.

The default values used by Icelandic facilities for F1 and F2, from the study, are provided in Table 4.1.

Thus, the formula can be used both for nitrogen and phosphorus, for several fish species, in different climates and water bodies. However, the default values for F1 and F2 vary for each parameter.

4.3.2 Methodology involving feed, feed composition and fish composition (Estonia, Norway, Sweden)

The three methods cited by Estonia, Norway and Sweden provide formulas for calculating emissions to water from fish farms. These formulas take into account factors such as feed, feed composition and fish composition.

Formula of Estonia:

The formula used by Estonian facilities is:

$$\text{Discharge} = 0.01 \times [(N_{\text{feed}} \times M_{\text{feed}}) - (N_{\text{fish}} \times M_{\text{fish}})]$$

Where:

- Discharge is the total annual pollutant loss (N or P) (kg/year);
- N_{feed} is the concentration/percentage of pollutant in the feed (%);
- N_{fish} is the concentration/percentage of pollutant in the fish (%);
- M_{feed} is the total amount of feed used during the year (kg/year);
- M_{fish} is the amount of produced fish (kg/year).

No default value has been provided by Estonia for N_{feed} and N_{fish}.

Formula of Norway:

The formula used by Norwegian facilities is an adjusted version of a mass balance formula.

The original formula is:

$$\text{Discharge} = 0.01 (C1 \times \text{Feed} - C2 \times \text{Biomass})$$

Where:

- C1 is the concentration/percentage of pollutant in the feed;
- C2 is the concentration/percentage of pollutant in the fish;
- Feed is the total amount of feed used during the year;
- Biomass is the annual biomass production based on fish production (slaughtering), adjusted for starving, bleeding and byproducts, dead fish, fish moved into the facility from another facility, fish moved out the facility to another facility ⁽²⁵⁾ and fish that escape.

However, obtaining accurate biomass data at plant level is often challenging in Norway, which may lead to unreliable results. To address this, an alternative formula is used:

$$\text{Discharge} = 0.01 \times (C1 \times \text{Feed} - C2 \times \text{Feed} / \text{FCR})$$

Where:

- Discharge is the total annual pollutant loss (N or P) (kg/year);
- C1 is the feed composition (% of pollutant in feed);
- C2 is the fish composition (% of pollutant in fish);

⁽²⁵⁾ Note that this refers to how this is used at the moment. For IEPR reporting, the reporting entity will be the “installation” as opposed to the “facility” (which was the case with E-PRTR)

- Feed is the total quantity of feed used during the year (kg/year);
- FCR (food conversion ratio) is calculated nationally for salmon and trout, based on the total amount of feed (input) and biomass (output) across Norway. The same FCR is used by all facilities.

This formula is similar to approach 2 from HELCOM / OSPAR, since the representatives of Norway specified that the source of their method was the 2000 document '*Development of HARP Guidelines Harmonised Quantification and Reporting Procedures for Nutrients*', which cites exactly the same three approaches of HELCOM / OSPAR presented in part 4.2.2. Indeed, both HELCOM and OSPAR participated in the HARP project, the results of which were reported in the aforementioned report. In particular, the section of the HARP project about calculating nutrient discharges into the water from aquaculture facilities is based on existing work by HELCOM and OSPAR.

Default values for C1, C2 and FCR were provided by Norway during the interview and are available in [Annex 9](#).

However, the study does not address whether the methods are applicable to climates other than that of Norway. While the formula itself appears to be climate-independent, the default values for C1, C2 and FCR may vary from one climate to another. In fact, for a climate other than Norway's, it would be necessary to determine different values while using the same formula.

Formula of Sweden:

The Swedish guideline document *Fiskodling, planering, tillstånd, tillsyn* (Naturvardsverket, 1993) which translates to *Fish farming, planning, permits, supervision*, served as a regulatory guideline covering various aspects of fish farming, including planning, licensing, environmental protection, disease control, and compliance with local and international standards. Although it was officially repealed by the Swedish Environmental Protection Agency on 1 April 2019, its nutrient calculation model is still occasionally referenced in existing aquaculture permits.

The guideline details a method for estimating nutrient emissions, such as phosphorus and nitrogen based on a mass balance approach. This method calculates emissions by assessing inputs (mainly from feed) and outputs (fish biomass and waste), using parameters such as feed conversion ratio (FCR), and nutrient concentration/percentage in both feed and fish tissue.

The formula used is as follows:

$$\text{Discharge} = 0.01 \times P \times (\text{FK} \times \text{CP} - \text{CR})$$

Where:

- Discharge is the total annual loss of phosphorus or nitrogen to the environment (kg/year);
- P is net fish production (kg/year);
- FK is the feed conversion ratio (feed used in tonnes / fish production in tonnes);
- CP is the pollutant concentration in the feed (%);
- CR is the pollutant concentration in fish biomass (%).

The formula is specifically designed to estimate discharges of nutrients (phosphorus and nitrogen). It is unclear whether it can be reliably applied to other pollutants such as heavy metals or TOC. Default values for C1, C2 and FCR were provided by Sweden in the questionnaire and are available in [Annex 9](#).

The guideline does not specify whether the method is restricted to certain species, nor whether it is suitable for use in freshwater fish and marine environments. Furthermore, it does not explain its applicability to climates outside of Sweden. While the formula itself appears to be climate-independent, the default values for C1, C2 and FCR may vary from one climate to another. In fact, for a climate other than Sweden's, it would be necessary to determine different values while using the same formula.

The formulas of Estonia, Norway and Sweden are very similar to those proposed by HELCOM / OSPAR (Approaches 1 and 2) and ASC (Formula 1), as shown in Table 4.2.

The following four parameters are used in the five formulas:

- **Fish composition:** the percentage of N or P in fish, which varies depending on the pollutant and sometimes the fish species (HELCOM / OSPAR);
- **Feed composition:** the percentage of N or P in feed, which varies depending on the pollutant;
- **Amount of feed;**
- **Fish Biomass / Net growth of fish / Net production of fish:** this consists of the amount of fish that escaped, died, or were slaughtered, added to the difference between the standing stock at the end of the year and beginning of the year.

Both HELCOM / OSPAR, Norway and Sweden use a **food conversion ratio (FCR)** in their formula. HELCOM / OSPAR proposes using FCR if either the amount of feed or fish biomass is not available at plant level but rather at national level, and precisely Norway uses FCR in order to avoid calculating the fish biomass at plant level but rather at a national level. In addition, Finland should also, in principle, use a variant of these formulas, since they have communicated their national values of fish composition and feed composition for N and P, as well as FCR.

Three parameters are only present in the first approach of HELCOM / OSPAR and should probably be considered negligible in the other formulas:

- Nutrient losses due to metabolism in fish;
- Nutrient removal processes on the fish farm that are not related to sludge removal;
- Amount of pollutant removed with the sludge.

Table 4.2: Comparison of formula to assess emissions to water for aquaculture facilities involving feed, feed composition and fish composition

Country using the method	Method / Source	With or without treatment	Pollutants	Fish species	Formula	Information on parameters			
						Code	Parameter	Unit	Source of input data for the formula
-	HELCOM, 2022 & OSPAR, 2015 Approaches 1 and 2	With or without treatment	N P	All fish species	Discharge = $0.01 \times (I \times C_i - G \times C_f) - M - T - S$	I	Amount of feed used that year	kg/y	Data to be given by each installation
						C _i	Percentage of pollutant in feed	-	Default values available for N and P Different per pollutant, same for each fish species
						G	Net growth of fish = Amount of fish escaped, dead, slaughtered + difference between the standing stock by the end of the year and the beginning of the year Where $G = I / FCR$ and $FCR = \text{Food conversion ratio}$	kg/y	Data to be given by each installation
						C _f	Percentage of pollutant in fish	-	Default values available for N and P Different per pollutant and fish species
						M	Nutrient losses due to metabolism in fish	kg/y	Data to be given by each installation
						T	Nutrient removal processes on the fish farm not related to sludge removal	kg/y	Data to be given by each installation
						S	Amount of pollutant removed with the sludge	kg/y	Data to be given by each installation
-	ASC, 2025	Without treatment	N P	All: fish, molluscs, crustaceans	Discharge (kg/year) = $0.01 \times (\text{Feed} \times C_f - P \times C_a)$	Feed	Amount of feed used that year	kg/y	Data to be given by each installation
						C _f	Percentage of pollutant in feed	-	No default values available
						P	Net production = Amount of fish escaped, dead, slaughtered + difference between the standing stock by the end of the year and the beginning of the year	kg/y	Data to be given by each installation
						C _a	Percentage of pollutant in fish	-	No default values available
Estonia	No specified source	Unspecified	N P	Unspecified	Discharge(kg/year) = $0.01 \times [(N_{\text{feed}} \times M_{\text{feed}}) - (N_{\text{fish}} \times M_{\text{fish}})]$	N _{feed}	Percentage of pollutant in feed	-	No default values provided
						N _{fish}	Percentage of pollutant in fish	-	No default values provided
						M _{feed}	Amount of feed used that year	kg/y	Data to be given by each installation
						M _{fish}	Amount of produced fish	kg/y	Data to be given by each installation

Country using the method	Method / Source	With or without treatment	Pollutants	Fish species	Formula	Information on parameters			
						Code	Parameter	Unit	How to get it
Norway	Borgvang et al., 2000	Unspecified	N P TOC Metals	Salmon Trout	Discharge (kg/year) = 0.01 x (C1 x Feed - C2 x Feed / FCR)	C1	Feed composition = Percentage of pollutant in feed	-	Default values available for N, P and TOC Different per pollutant, same for each fish species
						C2	Fish composition = Percentage of pollutant in fish	-	Default values available for N, P and TOC Different per pollutant, same for each fish species
						FCR	Food conversion ratio = Feed used / Fish biomass where Biomass = Amount of fish escaped, dead, slaughtered, moved from or to another facility	-	Default values available for salmon and trout Different per fish species and generation of fish, same for each pollutant
						Feed	Amount of feed used that year	kg/y	Data to be given by each installation
Sweden	Naturvar dsverket, 1993	Unspecified	N P	At least trout, unclear if also other fish species	Discharge (kg/year) = 0.01 x P x (FK x CP - CR)	P	Net fish production = Amount of fish escaped, dead, slaughtered + difference between the standing stock by the end and the beginning of the year	kg/y	Data to be given by each installation
						FK	Feed coefficient = Feed used / Fish production	-	Data to be given by each installation
						CP	Percentage of pollutant in feed	-	Default values available for N and P Different per pollutant, same for each fish species
						CR	Percentage of pollutant in fish biomass	-	Default values available for N and P Different per pollutant, same for each fish species

5 Proposed methodology for emissions to water

5.1 Proposed methodology for intensive livestock production

For intensive livestock production, no applicable methodology could be identified through the Industrial Emissions Database or Member State questionnaires.

Indeed, most of the countries surveyed consider that livestock production does not generate direct emissions into water because all liquid effluents produced in farms (e.g. liquid manure, slurry or cleaning water) are collected and stored in storage tanks or lagoons. These effluents are then either treated (onsite or delivered to wastewater treatment plants or biogas production plants by truck) and/or spread on agricultural land as fertiliser (Austria, Belgium, Czechia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Slovakia). As noted above, manure land spreading has not been in the scope of E-PRTR reporting since its inception and the E-PRTR Regulation had a recital excluding it from the reporting of land releases.

In farms, the bottom structures of animal shelters and manure storage facilities must be waterproof to prevent the contamination of surface and groundwater (Finland). Therefore, in some countries, the direct discharge of wastewater from intensive livestock farming is not legally permitted (Germany, Italy, Slovakia), or is simply not covered by the environmental permit: neither monitoring nor reporting (Belgium, Finland).

Figure 5.1 below is derived from information provided by Member States in the questionnaires, consultations and interviews, and illustrates what happens to the liquid effluent produced by an intensive livestock production facility.

Figure 5.1: Distribution of information provided by Member States on the subject of liquid effluent disposal on intensive farms

Notes: Bulgaria has specified that both pig and poultry farms may transport effluent to a biogas production plant, whereas Estonia and Italy did not provide any details. Bulgaria has specified that both pig and poultry farms may transport effluent to a wastewater treatment plant, while Romania only mentioned it for pig farms and Latvia and Slovakia did not provide any details.

Source: Author's compilation based on responses to questionnaire and consultation.

Among the countries that have recently reported emissions into water to the portal, most of the values were determined by measuring the flow rate and concentration by an accredited laboratory (Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania), or were based on expert judgement (Sweden), which makes it impossible to propose a common methodology.

Lastly, the scope of emissions into water from livestock farms does not appear to be entirely the same among the countries that have recently reported emissions. According to Bulgaria, emissions into water from intensive pig farming installations include water from washing pig houses and storage

areas, as well as manure runoff. In some cases, domestic sewage and contaminated rainwater are also included. However, Bulgaria consider that no wastewater is generated in intensive poultry farming installations as dry cleaning is used in poultry houses, manure is scraped or removed by conveyor belts from poultry houses and then spread on agricultural land. In Sweden only the handling and spreading of manure is taken into account. In Romania, the only facility that has recently reported emissions to water also carries out slaughtering activities, so the emissions to water are also due to this activity.

Figure 5.2 below is derived from information provided by Member States in the questionnaires, consultations and interviews, and illustrates the types of liquid effluent is produced by an intensive livestock production facility.

Figure 5.2: Distribution of information provided by Member States on the subject of liquid effluent produced by intensive farms

Source: Author’s compilation based on responses to questionnaire and feedback.

Based on information from Member States, Figure 5.3 and Figure 5.4 below illustrate how liquid effluents are managed on respectively an intensive pig farm and an intensive poultry farm. However, this only applied in an ideal scenario with no leaks, i.e. no loss of containment from tanks, pipes or storage facilities. However, a leak would be an accidental release and would also not be directly released to water bodies (note that the scope of the methodology refers to deliberate releases). Moreover, the scope of reporting of land releases does not include leaks (EC, 2006, ²⁶).

In some cases, water can also be shipped off-site, so it would not be a release of water, but rather a transfer of pollutants.

In conclusion, no suitable methodology can currently be recommended for intensive livestock production. For this, more monitoring data should be available and a common definition of the boundaries of the reporting, if applicable.

⁽²⁶⁾ The guidance will be superseded by a new Commission’s guidance as per Article 13 of the IEPR

Figure 5.3: Liquid effluent management in intensive pig farming

Notes: The dotted arrows show the two options for disposing of rainwater, domestic water and cleaning water: either mixed with manure / slurry or separated. This varies depending on the installation and the country. Depending on the installation, contaminated rainwater, domestic wastewater and cleaning water can be collected, stored and treated via separate or shared networks. It seems that the most common approach is to mix cleaning water with manure and slurry, while separating it from domestic wastewater and contaminated rainwater. Numbers 1 to 4 show the several types of animal housing / flooring on an intensive pig farm, and the associated manure / slurry disposal method.

Figure 5.4: Liquid effluent management in intensive poultry farming

Notes: Numbers 1 to 4 show the several types of animal housing / flooring on an intensive pig farm, and the associated manure disposal method. Depending on the installation, contaminated rainwater, domestic wastewater and cleaning water can be collected, stored and treated via separate or shared networks.

5.2 Proposed methodology for intensive aquaculture

Conversely, for intensive aquaculture, several methodologies were identified and analysed during the study.

For land-based facilities:

Based on approach 3 of the HELCOM / OSPAR guidelines and taking into account feedback from Norway and Spain, the proposed method for land-based facilities is conversion of measurement values to annual load. Though not a calculation per se, land-based systems are much easier to measure than sea systems which provides a more accurate result.

The formula proposed for assessing emissions into water based on measurements is that from approach 3 of the HELCOM / OSPAR guidelines:

$$L = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_i \times C_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n Q_i} \times Q_t \times 10^{-6}$$

Where:

- L is the annual load (kg/year);
- Q_i is the wastewater volume of the period i (m^3);
- C_i is the concentration of sample i ($\mu g/L$);
- Q_t is the total wastewater volume of the year ($m^3/year$);
- N is the number of sampling periods.

This formula does not require any reference data; all parameters must be provided by the installation.

For sea-based facilities:

Two mass balance-based methods have emerged for assessing emissions into water in sea-based aquaculture:

- A methodology involving feed, particulate nutrient, biomass and dissolved/excreted nutrient, used in Cyprus, Greece, Iceland and Spain;
- A methodology involving feed, feed composition and fish composition, used in Estonia, Norway and Sweden, and recommended by HELCOM, OSPAR and ASC.

Default values for both methodologies, relating to N and P, and for different fish species or feed are provided in the document, as well as in information supplied by the Member States mentioned above, and are included in [Annex 9](#) for reference.

The proposed method for sea-based facilities involved using a calculation methodology that takes into account feed, feed composition and fish composition. Both approaches 1 and 2 of HELCOM / OSPAR guidelines should be adopted as:

- It is suitable for all fish species;
- A large number of reference values have been provided;
- The formulas can be used both when effluent treatment is present or absent;
- A large number of installations use these approaches. Indeed, data from the Industrial Reporting Database show that Norwegian and Swedish facilities account for respectively 617 and three out of 671 aquaculture facilities in Europe (92 %) that have reported emissions to water over the last seven years; making it the most widely used calculation method in Europe for aquaculture emissions reporting.

Approach 1 is more appropriate if information is available for each installation.

$$\text{Discharge} = (0.01 \times (I \times C_i - G \times C_f)) - M - T - S$$

Where:

- Discharge is the total discharge of N or P to water body (kg/year);
- I is the amount of feed used for feeding of fish (kg/year);
- C_i is the P or N content in feed (%);
- G is the net growth of fish including dead fish (kg/year), calculated as $G = D + O + E + (S_f - S_i)$, where:
 - D is the quantity of dead organisms collected during the year (kg/year);
 - O is the quantity of organisms taken out of the water for slaughter (alternatively the sum of slaughter weight and slaughter offal) or sold alive (kg/year);
 - E is the quantity of escaped organisms (kg/year);
 - S_f and S_i are respectively the standing stock by the end of the year and the beginning of the year (kg/year).
- C_f is the P or N content in fish (%);
- M is the nutrient losses due to metabolism in fish (kg/year);
- T is the nutrient removal processes on the fish farm not related to sludge removal (e.g. nutrient turnover, denitrification etc.) (kg/year);
- S is the amount of P or N removed with the sludge (kg/year), only applicable for plants with treatment.

On the other hand, approach 2 should be prioritised if certain data is only available at national level: fish biomass (G in the previous formula) or amount of feed used (I in the previous formula). This can then be calculated using the feed conversion ratio (FCR), according to the following formula and then used in the formula from the first approach.

$$\text{FCR} = \frac{I}{G}$$

The FCR is species dependent and varies by water temperature, as the fish metabolism is temperature dependent. Hence, it is preferable to use FCR that are specific to the actual catchment or region based on estimates obtained from literature or determined through experimental work.

As a reminder, the HELCOM guidelines are updated whenever a new Pollution Load Compilation project begins, with no fixed frequency, which includes the methods to quantify nutrients releases to water. Therefore, it is recommended to use the latest available version of the HELCOM guidelines for the three approaches mentioned above.

Limitations and adaptability

While these approaches have proven effective in Norway and Sweden, and are likely to be suitable for northern and western European climates, since HELCOM consists of the nine Baltic Sea countries (Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Russia and Sweden), and OSPAR includes Belgium, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Iceland, Ireland, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Spain, Sweden and Switzerland, they have not been validated in other climatic regions.

However, several southern European countries, including Cyprus, France, Greece, Malta and Spain, also report emissions from aquaculture. According to the Industrial Reporting Database and questionnaire responses, these countries also use a mass balance approach, albeit not the same

formula as that recommended by HELCOM and OSPAR. In theory, the HELCOM / OSPAR formulas can be used for other climatic regions as long as country-specific or at least climatic-specific input data is available for the formulas.

Therefore, although HELCOM, OSPAR, Norway, Finland and Sweden have provided reference values for several coefficients in the formulas, countries with different climates will likely need to rely on literature or conduct their own studies to obtain coefficients specific to their region / climate.

5.3 Overview of the future tool

Based on the results of this report, a calculation tool in the form of an Excel file is currently being developed by ETC HE as a separate work. It will only be relevant to intensive aquaculture.

The tool will enable reporters to select the most appropriate approach for their situation among the three approaches recommended by HELCOM and OSPAR, whether they have data available at a national or installation level, and whether they report for land-based and sea-based installations.

To accommodate national or species-specific differences in feed and fish composition, the tool will allow users to adjust the coefficients. However, these values should only be accepted if they are supported by scientific literature or other reliable sources, in order to ensure consistency and robustness in emissions reporting.

6 Conclusions

While emissions to air from livestock farms have been monitored and assessed for many years, supported by established methodologies such as those in the EMEP/EEA Guidebook (EEA, 2023a), the same cannot be said about emissions to water from either livestock farms or aquaculture facilities. There is currently no harmonised methodology in this area.

This study aimed to explore the possibility of proposing a methodology for calculating emissions to water from these two activities, based on feedback from different countries gathered through questionnaires and interviews.

The findings highlight notable discrepancies in the Industrial Emissions Database (European Industrial Emissions Portal, 2025) regarding data availability and methodological approaches among countries activities, and pollutant types (e.g. N, P, heavy metals).

Key observations:

- **Intensive livestock production:**
Reporting of emissions to water from pig and poultry farms is extremely limited. Over the last seven years, only nine facilities from four countries (Bulgaria, Hungary, Romania and Sweden) have reported emissions. These emissions are mostly nitrogen and phosphorus, and very rarely organic carbon, phenols, zinc, cadmium and lead. By contrast, air emissions were reported by 9,609 facilities from across 27 countries during the same period.
- **Intensive aquaculture:**
Reporting is more prevalent for aquaculture, with 671 facilities from nine countries (Cyprus, France, Greece, Iceland, Malta, Norway, Poland, Spain and Sweden) reporting emissions during the last seven years. Note that Norwegian facilities represent 92% of these 671 facilities. Seven pollutants were reported by aquaculture facilities, with nitrogen, phosphorus, total organic carbon, zinc and copper being the most widely documented. Other pollutants, e.g. arsenic and nickel, are rarely reported and do not appear to be key pollutants.

Methodological trends:

- **Intensive livestock production:**
 - Facilities in Bulgaria, Hungary and Romania primarily use measurement-based approaches.
 - In Sweden, expert judgement is employed.
- **Intensive aquaculture:**
 - **Sea-based:** Most facilities in Cyprus, France, Greece, Iceland, Malta, Norway, Poland and Sweden use mass balance approaches to estimate emissions to water, based on nutrient fate and conversion ratios. Some facilities in France use direct measurement.
 - **Land-based:** Facilities in Norway and Spain use direct measurement.
- **Across all facilities:**
 - The main pollutants (N, P, TOC, Zn and Cu) are generally assessed through calculation.
 - Other pollutants are mostly by measurement, however, details on the method used are often lacking.

Methods classified as ‘calculation’ include mass balance, emission factors and food conversion ratios. One objective of this study was to assess whether the methodological references cited by facilities could be adapted for use in a harmonised reporting tool.

Drawing lessons from the literature, particularly from air emission methodologies such as the EMEP guidebook, highlights the importance of multi-tiered calculation methods and using standard units for emission factors.

In terms of emissions to water, literature on livestock farming is sparse, whereas literature on aquaculture is comparatively richer. For instance, the guide published by ETC ICM ⁽²⁷⁾ *Calculating emissions to water – a simplified method* (Roovaart et al., 2022) offers a general framework for pathways to water including those relating to agriculture, focusing mostly on diffuse emissions. However, it lacks detail on methodologies specific to livestock farming, let alone direct emissions for this specific sector.

Three documents (HELCOM, 2022; OSPAR, 2015; ASC, 2025) provide several formulas for calculating N and P emissions into water for aquaculture facilities in various scenarios: land-based or sea-based facilities, with or without effluent treatment, data available at a national or installation level.

Aquaculture methodology insights

Sea-based facilities:

Two mass balance methodologies have emerged from the country feedback and interviews:

- A methodology involving feed, particulate nutrient, biomass and dissolved/excreted nutrient, used in Cyprus, Greece, Iceland and Spain;
- A methodology involving feed, feed composition and fish composition, which is used in Estonia, Norway and Sweden, and recommended by HELCOM, OSPAR and ASC.

These methodologies primarily apply to nitrogen and phosphorus, and sometimes to TOC and metals. Each model requires specific input data such as the amount of feed, as well as coefficients for which several countries have provided default values.

Land-based facilities:

Only the implementation of measurement seems appropriate for land-based installations, according to inputs from HELCOM / OSPAR, Norway and Spain.

Recommendations

- Intensive aquaculture

A standardised calculation tool for emissions to water from intensive aquaculture farms, should be developed based on the HELCOM / OSPAR methodologies:

- For sea-based facilities, approaches 1 and 2 involving feed, feed composition and fish composition should be used, as these are suitable for all fish species and a large number of reference values are available. These approaches are also widely used among Norwegian and Swedish facilities.

Approach 1 is more appropriate when information is available for each installation. On the other hand, approach 2 should be prioritised if certain data is only available at a national level, e.g. fish biomass or the amount of feed used.

The tool should allow country specific adjustments to coefficients to reflect local feed formulations, environmental conditions (climate) and conversion rates.

- For land-based facilities, approach 3 involving measurement should be used.

- Intensive livestock production:

Due to the lack of available data and consistent methodologies, no standard calculation method for emissions to water from intensive livestock production can currently be proposed. More data is needed to aspire to the possibility of proposing such standard method.

⁽²⁷⁾ European Topic Centre on Inland, Coastal and Marine waters

List of 2-letter country codes

2-letter country code	Country
AT	Austria
BE	Belgium
BG	Bulgaria
CH	Switzerland
CY	Cyprus
CZ	Czechia
DE	Germany
DK	Denmark
EE	Estonia
ES	Spain
FI	Finland
FR	France
GR	Greece
HR	Croatia
HU	Hungary
IE	Ireland
IS	Iceland
IT	Italy
LI	Liechtenstein
LT	Lithuania
LU	Luxembourg
LV	Latvia
MT	Malta
NL	Netherlands
NO	Norway
PL	Poland
PT	Portugal
RO	Romania
RS	Serbia
SE	Sweden
SI	Slovenia
SK	Slovakia

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronym	Name
As	Arsenic and compounds
C	Total carbon
Cd	Cadmium and compounds
CH ₄	Methane
CO	Carbon monoxide
Cu	Copper and compounds
DIC	Dissolved inorganic carbon
DIN	Dissolved inorganic nitrogen
DIP	Dissolved inorganic phosphorus
DOC	Dissolved organic carbon
DON	Dissolved organic nitrogen
DOP	Dissolved organic phosphorus
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Environment Agency
EMEP	European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme
E-PRTR	European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register
EU	European Union
Hg	Mercury
IED	Industrial and Livestock Rearing Emissions Directive
IEPR	Industrial Emissions Portal Regulation
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LSU	Livestock Unit
N	Total nitrogen
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
NH ₃	Ammonia
Ni	Nickel and compounds
NMVOCs	Non-methane volatile organic compounds
NO	Nitric oxide
NO ₂	Nitrogen dioxide
NO ₃ ⁻	Nitrates
NO _x	Nitrogen oxides
P	Total phosphorus
PAHs	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
Pb	Lead and compounds
PCB	Polychlorinated biphenyls
PM	Particulate matter
POC	Particulate organic carbon
PON	Particulate organic nitrogen
POP	Particulate organic phosphorus
POPs	Persistent organic pollutants
RAS	Recirculating Aquaculture Systems
SO ₂	Sulphur dioxide
SO _x	Sulphur oxides
TOC	Total organic carbon
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
Zn	Zinc and compounds

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Annex 1 Contacts

Table A1.1: List of countries contacted and contact information

Group	Country	Organisation	Answer to questionnaire	Interview
Group 1	Iceland	Environment Agency of Iceland	No answer	Yes: 30/04/2025
	Spain	Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico	Partial responses provided during the consultation on the draft report, in an email sent on 15/09/25	No
	Sweden	Swedish Environmental Agency	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 31/01/2025 + Additional information provided during the consultation on the draft report on 09/09/2025	No
Group 2	Cyprus	Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment	Partial answers given in an email sent on 27/05/2025	No
	France	Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 02/12/2024	No
	Greece	Ministry of Environment and Energy	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 18/12/2024	No
	Malta		No answer	No
	Norway	Norwegian Environment Agency	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 30/10/2024	Yes: 25/03/2025
Group 3	Poland		No answer	No
	Bulgaria	Environmental Executive Agency	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 20/03/2025 + Additional information provided in an email sent on 16/09/2025	No
	Hungary		No answer	No
	Portugal		No answer	No
	Romania	National Environmental Protection Agency and National Administration Romanian Waters	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 26/11/2024 + Additional information provided in an email sent on 15/09/2025	No
Group 4	Slovenia		No answer	No
	Belgium	<i>Service Public de Wallonie (Walloon) & Vlaamse Milieumaatschappij (Flanders)</i>	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 29/11/2024	No
	Italy	Italian National Institute for Environment Protection and Research	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 28/11/2024	No
	Austria	Environment Agency Austria	Answers given in an email sent on 06/11/2024	No
	Czechia	Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 08/01/2025	No
	Denmark	Ministry of Environment and Gender Equality	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 18/12/2024	No
	Estonia	Estonian Environment Agency	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 28/11/2024 + Additional information provided during the consultation on the draft report on 01/08/2025	No

Group	Country	Organisation	Answer to questionnaire	Interview
	Finland	Ministry of the Environment of Finland and Finnish Environment Institute	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 09/11/2024 + Additional information provided during the consultation on the draft report on 05/09/2025	No
	Germany	German Environment Agency	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 27/01/2025	No
	Ireland	Environmental Protection Agency	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 29/11/2024	No
	Latvia	SLLC "Latvian Environment, Geology and Meteorology Centre"	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 30/10/2024	No
	Lithuania		No answer	No
	Luxembourg		No answer	No
	Netherlands		No answer	No
	Slovakia	Slovak Environment Agency	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 29/11/2024	No
Group 5	Croatia	Ministry of Environmental Protection and Green Transition	Questionnaire completed and sent back on 25/11/2024	No

Annex 2 Distribution of emissions to water and air reporting from 2007 to 2023, for every country

Figure A2.1: Number of facilities classified 7.(a) or 7.(b) reporting emissions to air or water for each year from 2007 to 2023, for every country included in the Industrial Reporting Database

- 7.(a) facilities reporting emissions to water
- 7.(a) facilities reporting emissions to air
- 7.(b) facilities reporting emissions to water
- 7.(b) facilities reporting emissions to air

- 7.(a) facilities reporting emissions to water
- 7.(a) facilities reporting emissions to air
- 7.(b) facilities reporting emissions to water
- 7.(b) facilities reporting emissions to air

Note: There is no information for 7.(a) or 7.(b) facilities for the three following countries: Croatia, Liechtenstein and Switzerland.

Source: Author's compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025.

Annex 3 Distribution of emissions to water reporting from 2017 to 2023, per pollutant and per country

Figure A3.2: Number of facilities classified 7.(a) reporting emissions to water from 2017 to 2023 per pollutant and per country

Source: Author’s compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025.

Figure A3.3: Number of facilities classified 7.(b) reporting emissions to water from 2017 to 2023 per pollutant and per country

Source: Author’s compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025.

Annex 4 Lists of ‘Method’ and ‘Method classification’ choices in the Industrial Reporting Database

Table A4.2: List of ‘Method’ choices in the Industrial Reporting Database

Method	Method name
C	Calculated: calculation method used
E	Estimated
M	Measured: analytical method used

Source: Author’s compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025.

Table A4.3: List of ‘Method classification’ choices in the Industrial Reporting Database

Method classification	Method classification name
ALT	Alternative measurement methodology in accordance with existing CEN/ISO measurement standards
CEN-ISO	Internationally approved measurement standard
CRM	Measurement methodology for the performance of which is demonstrated by means of certified reference materials and accepted by competent authority.
ETS (a)	Guidelines for the monitoring and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions under the Emission Trading Scheme.
IPCC	IPCC Guidelines
MAB	Mass balance method which is accepted by the competent authority
NRB	National or regional binding measurement/calculation methodology prescribed by legal act for the pollutant and facility concerned.
OTH	Other measurement/calculation methodology
PER	Measurement/Calculation Methodology already prescribed by the competent authority in a licence or an operating permit for that facility
SSC	European-wide sector specific calculation method
UNECE-EMEP (b)	UNECE/EMEP EMEP/CORINAIR Emission Inventory Guidebook

Notes: (a) Not relevant for emissions to water, never used by 7.(a) or 7.(b) facilities to assess emissions to water from 2007 to 2023.

(b) Guidebook for atmospheric emissions inventories, not relevant for emissions to water, but still quoted by some 7.(a) or 7.(b) facilities to assess emissions to water from 2007 to 2023.

Source: Author’s compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025.

Annex 5 Distribution of method used to assess emissions to water from 2007 to 2023, for every country

Figure A5.4: Number of emissions to water value assessed according to the methodology (calculations, estimation or measurement) from 2007 to 2023

Source: Author's compilation based on data from Industrial Reporting Database ver. 14.0 Mar. 2025.

Annex 6 List of questions in the questionnaire sent to selected countries about their methodology to assess emissions to water

Table A6.4: List of questions in the questionnaire sent to selected countries about their methodology to assess emissions to water

❖ For intensive rearing of poultry or pigs:	
Question theme	Question
Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Could you provide us more details on the method used? How is it done? <input type="checkbox"/> Mass balance <input type="checkbox"/> Emission factors <input type="checkbox"/> Equations <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
Regulatory framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? ○ Could you send it to us or provide a link?
Emissions factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If emissions are based on emission factors, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Are they tier 1, 2 or 3? ○ Where do these factors come from? <input type="checkbox"/> Database <input type="checkbox"/> Measurement <input type="checkbox"/> Other: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?
Uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?
Scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the scope of the emissions? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What kind of water emissions are included in the results? <input type="checkbox"/> Channelled emissions <input type="checkbox"/> Diffuse emissions <input type="checkbox"/> Other: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which sources of water emissions are included? <input type="checkbox"/> Wash water from cleaning buildings and storages <input type="checkbox"/> Wastewater from exhaust air treatment <input type="checkbox"/> Manure run-off <input type="checkbox"/> Other source: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which pathways are included in the scope (i.e. atmospheric deposition, spreading, irrigation, ...)? ○ Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions (% of reduction)?
Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf? • What kind of information required to calculate wastewater discharges have to be reported? • Why do facilities in this sector don't report water emissions? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Water emissions are below the threshold <input type="checkbox"/> Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions. In this case please elaborate: <input type="checkbox"/> Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide <input type="checkbox"/> Other reason: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If water emissions are below the threshold: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How are water emissions determined? <input type="checkbox"/> Measurement <input type="checkbox"/> Estimation <input type="checkbox"/> Calculations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If a calculation method is used, can you describe the methodology?

❖ For intensive aquaculture:	
Question theme	Question
Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Could you provide us more details on the method used? How is it done? <input type="checkbox"/> Mass balance <input type="checkbox"/> Emission factors <input type="checkbox"/> Equations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <input type="checkbox"/> Other:
Regulatory framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? ○ Could you send it to us or provide a link?
Emissions factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If emissions are based on emission factors, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Are they tier 1, 2 or 3? ○ Where do these factors come from? <input type="checkbox"/> Database <input type="checkbox"/> Measurement <input type="checkbox"/> Other: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?
Uncertainty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?
Scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the scope of the emissions? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What kind of water emissions are included in the results? <input type="checkbox"/> Channelled emissions <input type="checkbox"/> Diffuse emissions <input type="checkbox"/> Other: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which sources of water emissions are included? <input type="checkbox"/> Excess nutrients <input type="checkbox"/> Faeces from animals <input type="checkbox"/> Equipment <input type="checkbox"/> Chemicals used (e.g. medication, treatments, antifoulants) <input type="checkbox"/> Other source: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Which pathways are included in the scope? ○ Are abatement techniques considered for the water emissions (% of reduction)?
Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf? • What kind of information required to calculate wastewater discharges have to be reported? • Why do facilities in this sector don't report water emissions? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Water emissions are below the threshold <input type="checkbox"/> Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions. In this case please elaborate: <input type="checkbox"/> Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide <input type="checkbox"/> Other reason: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If water emissions are below the threshold: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How are water emissions determined? <input type="checkbox"/> Measurement <input type="checkbox"/> Estimation <input type="checkbox"/> Calculations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ If a calculation method is used, can you describe the methodology?

Note: Country-specific questions are not included in this list.

Annex 7 Detailed statistical data from questionnaire, interview and consultation with Member States

- Questions on methods:

Question 1: Could you provide us more details on the method used by the facilities from your country to assess water emissions? How is it done?

Figure A7.5: Distribution of responses to question 1

Notes: Norway cited both ‘emission factors’ and ‘mass balance’, stating that they did not know which of the two categories their method fell into. Based on their explanations, it is more likely to be a mass balance, so the ‘emissions factors’ response has not been taken into account in the graph. The equation Sweden refers to for their aquaculture facilities is actually a mass balance equation so even though this answer was not selected in the questionnaire, it has been added here.

Source: Author’s compilation based on responses to questionnaire sent to selected Member States.

- Questions on regulatory framework:

Question 2: Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?

Figure A7.6: Distribution of responses to question 2

Source: Author’s compilation based on responses to questionnaire sent to selected Member States.

- Questions on emission factors:

Question 3: If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from?

Figure A7.7: Distribution of responses to question 3

Source: Author's compilation based on responses to questionnaire sent to selected Member States.

Question 4: What kind of activity data is used to calculate emissions?

Figure A7.8: Distribution of responses to question 4

Source: Author's compilation based on responses to questionnaire sent to selected Member States.

- Questions on the uncertainty of emissions:

Question 5: What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?

Figure A7.9: Distribution of responses to question 5

Source: Author's compilation based on responses to questionnaire sent to selected Member States.

- Questions on the scope of emissions:

Question 6: What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results?

Figure A7.10: Distribution of responses to question 6

Source: Author's compilation based on responses to questionnaire sent to selected Member States.

Question 7: Which sources of water emissions are included?

Figure A7.11: Distribution of responses to question 7

Source: Author's compilation based on responses to questionnaire sent to selected Member States.

Question 8: Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions (% of reduction)?

Figure A7.12: Distribution of responses to question 8

Source: Author's compilation based on responses to questionnaire sent to selected Member States.

Question 9: Which pathways are included in the scope (i.e. atmospheric deposition, ...)?

Figure A7.13: Distribution of responses to question 9

Source: Author's compilation based on responses to questionnaire sent to selected Member States.

- Questions on the reporting of emissions:

Question 10: Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?

Figure A7.14: Distribution of responses to question 10

Source: Author's compilation based on responses to questionnaire sent to selected Member States.

Question 11: What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?

Figure A7.15: Distribution of responses to question 11

Source: Author's compilation based on responses to questionnaire sent to selected Member States.

Question 12: Why do facilities report no emissions to water?

Figure A7.16: Distribution of responses to question 12

Source: Author's compilation based on responses to questionnaire sent to selected Member States.

Annex 8 Feedback from consultation with Member States on draft report, responses provided and resulting amendments to final report

Table A8.5: Feedback from consultation with Member States on draft report, responses provided and resulting amendments to final report

MS	Date	Feedback	Response provided	Change made
Estonia	01/08/2025	<p>1. Do I understand correctly, that it won't be compulsory for aquaculture farms to start using methodology of Norway? Is it rather meant for Member states in case they have to calculate the emissions for aquaculture farms as indicated in IEPR Article 6(9)?</p> <p>2. In Estonia permits given to aquaculture farms regulate the N and P emissions to water (no TOC or metals are regulated) according to our aquaculture regulation. In this regulation there is a calculation method: Emission of N (or P) to the water= $[(N_{feed} \times M_{feed}) - (N_{fish} \times M_{fish})] / 100\%$, where N_{feed} – the % of N in the feed; N_{fish} – the % of N in the fish M_{feed} – the used amount of feed (kg); M_{fish} – the amount of produced fish (kg)</p> <p>3. Until now in Estonia there have not been aquaculture farms big enough to exceed the E-PRTR threshold, but in coming years some of them will probably exceed the threshold, so my question is: can these Estonian farms calculate the emissions to water according to our regulation I mentioned above and we can consider the method of Norway when we start to change our aquaculture regulation in the future?</p>	<p>The Estonian methodology will be added in the final report.</p> <p>In the final version of this report, it is proposed to use HELCOM / OSPAR methodologies, with include three approaches depending on the type of aquaculture facilities (land-based or sea-based) and if data is rather available at facility or national level.</p> <p>In fact, the Estonian approach mentioned below is the same as approach 1 of HELCOM / OSPAR, so there is no need to change your methods as they are in line with those proposed.</p> <p>The future tool we recommend could simply facilitate calculations and reporting in the Industrial Portal for your installations if they exceed the thresholds.</p>	Information added in Annex 10 and chapter 3
Italy	04/09/2025	<p>1. did I get it right that aquaculture in the document is only related to fish rearing? It is not clear to me if shellfish is included in the IEPR activity "feed-based aquaculture" or not, since the suggested formula is developed for salmon and trouts while shellfish is not explicitly addressed in the document. (The E-PRTR activity 7.b includes fish and shellfish rearing)</p> <p>I found that "intensive" shellfish rearing does exist as an option and, in that case, it could also be a type of "feed-based aquaculture" practice, but I still haven't found information about feed-based shellfish rearing carried out in Italy. I'm coming back on this just because I want to make sure to provide operators with correct information on what is in the scope of the IEPR and what is not in.</p> <p>2. Would it be possible to expand the paragraphs "Limitations and adaptability" and "Flexibility in the tool" in order to provide more guidance on how to adjust parameters and conversion factors to the Member states' national circumstances? It is very important to have a common estimation technique, but it would be more valuable to guide the implementation of the formula at the reporting level e.g. Tier1: use default</p>	<p>Juan Calero answered by e-mail on the 22/09/2025:</p> <p>1. Very good point – here we focus on fish because of the 'feed-based' that is added to the scope in the IEPR compared to E-PRTR. This means that shellfish such as mussels, clams and so on are not in the scope since they do not need to be fed.</p> <p>2. Yes, this is a good idea, we can expand this explanation. In some way, the formula proposed is a simple mass balance. The formula can be expanded slightly to calculate FCR. From what we have seen, the formula (or its expanded version) relies on inputs and outputs of feed and fish, and it</p>	Explanation of the scope of the study (fish/shellfish) added Extension of the paragraph "Limitations and adaptability"

MS	Date	Feedback	Response provided	Change made
		<p>values for salmon/trout (i.e. Iceland/Norway/Sweden values) if country specific values are not available for different fish species and feed/FCR; Tier 2: apply average country/fish specific values for feed and FCR; Tier 3: use installation specific values for fish/feed/FCR if available.</p> <p>3. do you know if there is literature about how the composition of feed or the values for FCR and substances/pollutants concentrations can be affected by fish species and climate zone? If literature about ranges of values related to macro-climate zones (e.g. boreal, temperate and tropical) exists it would be great to have it referenced in the document.</p>	<p>could be used for all countries. Then the key is to have the right values to use in each situation. In that case we have gotten more default values from the Nordic countries because they have been using them for years and they also have reported this for longer and for more facilities (especially Norway). But I would expect that other MS would need other default values. I also assume it would be possible to have even installation specific values in a similar way to tier 3 as you mention below.</p> <p>3. We do not have specific data on this but the studies we have seen talk about water temperature, pH and so on, and there should be changes to FCR depending on the environment. I am guessing also species have different values similarly to how salmon and trout differ themselves. We are aware that some countries which used a formula based the values used in a study from some years ago based on a single experiment and use it for all their species. FCR is also calculated and applied at national level in e.g. Norway so that they would not necessarily take into account larger or smaller species and characteristics. Sweden has another similar formula. What we found is that these countries found references that were relevant for their species and more or less comparable geographical areas, and are still using these formulas changing a couple of variables but relying on these studies which are now over 10 years old, sometimes much older.</p> <p>I have also attached 2 references we have recently received from Spain – Apparently, they are used by members of their main aquaculture industrial association to calculate emissions by sea-cage aquaculture facilities in Spain. As you can see, one of them focused on Sparus aurata and Dicentrarchus labrax in the Canary Islands and the other one also Sparus aurata in Israel – these correspond to branzino and orata in Italian. I believe these methodologies are used as proxies for a Mediterranean Sea type of climate (and maybe a bit more subtropical) and for these two popular species in Europe. We have not analysed yet how</p>	

MS	Date	Feedback	Response provided	Change made
			similar they are to each other but they have in common that they are old yet still used/representative.	
Austria	04/09/2025	<p>1. We assume that no aquacultures with a capacity of over 500 tonnes exist or are planned in Austria.</p> <p>No waste water is produced in Austria when keeping poultry or pigs.</p> <p>As it has no relevance for Austria, we do not comment on ‘Methodologies for reporting emissions to water’</p> <p>2. Regarding emissions to air:</p> <p>In Austria, we are planning to develop a tool for calculating pollutant emissions into the air from livestock production (dust, NH3, N2O and CH4) that operators can use to calculate pollutant emissions in a manageable way. We want to integrate this tool into the national electronic reporting application.</p> <p>The European Environment Agency (EEA) has proposed the application of the methodology according to the EMEP/EEA air inventory guidebook 2023 (in particular chapter 3 agriculture) for the calculation of releases to air. The inventory guidebook serves as an international set of rules for the preparation of national emission inventories and is also used in Austria in the Austrian Air Pollutant Inventory (OLI) as a basis for calculating emissions to air.</p> <p>Based on this guidebook, the EEA has developed a standardised Excel-based calculation tool for livestock production (manure management N-flow Excel-tool), which is also intended for national emission inventories. This model is primarily developed for the calculation of ammonia, but is also able to balance N2O.</p> <p>For the purpose of reporting in the industry emissions portal calculations of dust and methane emissions need to be included in the model. For the calculation of dust and methane, standardised emission factors (at the best provided in the EU-guidance according to Article 13 IEP-R) will be used.</p> <p>The EEA manure management N-flow Excel-tool is designed for national reporting, but can be adapted to be applicable at installation level.</p> <p>Austria plans to use this N-flow Excel-tool with some adaptations for reporting under IEPR :</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - where necessary, implementation of climate region-specific factors, if available (e.g. from national inventory), instead of default factors from the Guidebook - Implementation of abatement factors - simplified input options for farm-specific measures/techniques/practices - calculation of dust and methane according to emission factors provided from EEA/EC needs to be included in the tool - <p>For the following issues we ask EEA/EC for clarification, e.g. in the EU-guidance according to Article 13 of the IEP-Regulation:</p>	<p>1. No changes required</p> <p>2. Not relevant to the report</p>	None

MS	Date	Feedback	Response provided	Change made
		<p>Which abatement factors (reduction potentials) should be used e.g. for</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Nitrogen reduced feeding o Different housing techniques (e.g. manure belt) o Emission techniques like biofilter, scrubber o Storage of manure (different kind of covers, like natural crust, flexible covers,..) 		
Finland	05/09/2025	<p>We would like to point out an important comment what comes to the document for emission to water in aquaculture. In Finland, the calculation is only made on the last year's (food fish) production, but we couldn't figure out what was in this proposal. For smaller fish, the pollutant levels and food conversion ratio are different. The presentation only dealt with salmon and trout. Rainbow trout is a different fish, and we don't think it should be presented with the figures given for salmon or trout. For example, we have advanced feeds and rainbow trout farming, which have led to lower food conversion ratio than in this draft. The pollutants contained in the Norwegian feeds are also confusingly high (could it be because they also involve raising fry?).</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Comparison between Finland and Norway:</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Feed composition In Finland In Norway P = 0.7% 0.96% N = 6% 5.84%</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Fish composition In Finland In Norway P = 0.4% 0.45% N = 2.75 2.96%</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Food conversion ratio In Finland In Norway 1.10 1.18 (salmon) 1.37 (trout)</p>	<p>The Finnish methodology for aquaculture will be added in the final report.</p> <p>If you already have values for FCR, feed composition and fish composition, then these are the values you should use. Those for Norway are an example, but they can be adapted for each country/climate.</p>	Information added in Annex 10 and chapter 3
Germany	05/09/2025	<p>1. We have no further comments and remarks on the ETC/HE draft report „method for top-down calculation of water releases under IEPR“. The answers to the questionnaire as submitted from the German UBA to the EEA on 27 January 2025 remain valid and up-to-date.</p> <p>We currently have no aquacultures in DE falling under the reporting obligation.</p> <p>2. Concerning the recommendation of the EEA using the emission factors (EF) of the “EMEP/EEA air pollutant emission inventory guidebook 2023” for the calculation of air emissions from intensive livestock farming, we are still in the working process of comparing the national EF versus the EF of the “EMEP/EEA air pollutant emission</p>	<p>1. No changes required</p> <p>2. Not relevant to the report</p>	None

MS	Date	Feedback	Response provided	Change made
		inventory guidebook 2023” with a subsequent detailed analysis. This will still take some more time.		
Poland	05/09/2025	In response to the message below, please correct the Polish flag on page 96. It is upside down.	It will be corrected in the final report.	Flag updated in Annex 10
Romania	05/09/2025	Regarding methodology for intensive aquaculture, we have concerns about its application in our case because northern European models would not be suitable in our case and the elaboration of specific studies for national conditions would involve quite high costs and at national level there are a small number of installations according to the new threshold.	In the final version of this report, it is proposed to use HELCOM / OSPAR methodologies, with include three approaches depending on the type of aquaculture facilities (land-based or sea-based) and if data is rather available at facility or national level. Some default values are provided and seems relevant for any climate / geographical areas.	None
Czechia	05/09/2025	<p>Following your request for feedback on the draft document Methodologies for reporting emissions to water under the Industrial Emission Portal Regulation, please find below the comments from the Czech Republic.</p> <p>First of all, we would like to thank you for preparing the draft, which we consider very useful. We regret, however, that in the case of intensive livestock production and water releases, the document did not lead to the desired conclusions or a harmonised reporting approach, which seems to have been achieved for intensive aquaculture.</p> <p>Let us briefly comment on the part concerning intensive aquaculture. As the Czech Republic is a landlocked country, we have no remarks, suggestions or comments on this section. We only operate ponds and similar artificial reservoirs, which are not covered by the activity under the IEPR.</p> <p>The more important area for the Czech Republic is undoubtedly intensive livestock production. Unfortunately, as shown by the information collected from Member States, there are significant differences in the approach to reporting water releases. We would like to point out that in the Czech Republic, such releases are practically not present for this activity. We would welcome a common reporting approach, but it remains uncertain whether this will be feasible.</p> <p>We have only one comment regarding Table 6.1 and the related text. As we have already indicated, we support reporting only of key raw materials. In this case, we consider feed to be the only key raw material, not detergents or disinfectants. It is also questionable whether this part should be included in the document at all.</p>	After consideration, the chapter concerning raw materials has been removed.	Chapter deleted
Sweden	09/09/2025	<p>1. part 1.2 Concerning aqua culture: Please consider to make use of the Helcom GL as this approach would be comparable</p>	The HELCOM methodologies will be added in the final report and compared with Norwegian methodology.	Information added in chapter 4.2 and 4.3

MS	Date	Feedback	Response provided	Change made
		<p>of making use of EMEP/EEA GB for air emissions. The HELCOM GL is reviewed on a regular basis. See section 5 in: Microsoft Word - HELCOM_PLC-Water_Guidelines_final_for_layouting.docx</p> <p>By using the Helcom GL you could assure comparable data as well as minimise the administrative for MS that are subject for reporting under both initiatives.</p> <p>2. part 2.1 Have you compared the Norwegian method to the Helcom method?</p> <p>3. part 4.2 Related to aquaculture, HELCOM GL is missing. See survey answer from SE and and: Microsoft Word - HELCOM_PLC-Water_Guidelines_final_for_layouting.docx</p>	In fact, in the final version of this report, it is proposed to use the three approaches of HELCOM methodologies.	
Spain	15/09/2025	<p>They have consulted with APROMAR (https://apromar.es/, the Spanish aquaculture industrial association):</p> <p>1- Aquaculture based on pens/cages in the sea: It is not feasible to perform direct measurements, therefore N and P emissions are calculated. They used the following two models [I am trying to get the exact references, the first one is likely https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0990744098800107, but I don't have access with the EEA credentials. The other one is probably about tuna]: a. Lupatsch & Kissil (1998). b. Vergara et al. (2005). Both models get similar results. They are based on feed composition and they have been used for a long time.</p> <p>2- Terrestrial aquaculture (either sea water or fresh water): Direct measurement. Operators are required to measure and notify these measurements to the competent authority. With regard to E-PRTR, these land installations should not use the models outlined above. These are estimations that are not suitable for quantifying emissions from land installations. Since the IEPR establishes that direct measurements should be the norm wherever this is possible, and considering that these installations are required to do so by law, the industrial association prefers that direct measurements are used for PRTR reporting. They only agree that direct measurements are used and not calculations.</p> <p>The reason for this, according to this difference between 1 and 2 is, according to this industrial association:</p>	The Spanish methodologies for sea-based and land-based aquaculture will be added in the final report.	Information added in Annex 10 and chapter 3, and 2 models explained in chapter 4

MS	Date	Feedback	Response provided	Change made
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aquaculture farms in land apply abatement techniques such as filters and decantation which reduce notably water emissions, to sea and freshwater. - There are over 200 land aquaculture farms which routinely perform direct measurements in Spain (again, no need for calculations). - There are land aquaculture farms in Spain with Recirculating Aquaculture Systems. These are land-based aquaculture systems in which water is reused and filtered, rather than flowing freely through the system. According to the industrial associations, this reduces water emissions to negligible [they do not provide an independent verification for this claim] - Calculation models like those from Lupatsch and Vergara, although they use as input to the formula the composition of the feed, they do not take into account the efficiency and improvements during the manufacturing of the feed. [I guess this means the assumptions of losses and so on are not correct or not in line with the current state of the art. For example a feed composition with e.g. 5% nitrogen would lose more nitrogen 30 years ago than currently]. - For land aquaculture, this industrial association is not aware of any calculation method used. - Depending on where the emissions occur, dispersion modelling should consider the impact of currents, intertidal zones and so on, which would have an impact on emissions [I guess here I do not entirely agree because we are talking about excretion or emissions, whereas the impact is a different story. I am assuming they mean impact would differ due to these factors but I guess emissions produced by x animals with x feed would be the same?] 		
Ireland	19/09/2025	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The proposal for the tool is to use the Norwegian formula for salmon and trout; will the calculation tool also be applicable to shellfish? 2. Page 35 of the document states that the Norwegian methodology is based on the document “SEPA, 2004, Scottish pollutant release inventory (SPRI) Marine fish farm emission Calculation consultation part 2”. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Here we focus on fish because of the ‘feed-based’ that is added to the scope in the IEPR compared to E-PRTR. This means that shellfish such as mussels, clams and so on are not in the scope since they do not need to be fed. 2. After clarification with representatives from Norway, their method is based more on that of HELCOM and OSPAR. 	<p>Information added in Annex 10 and chapter 3</p> <p>2 methods explained in chapter 4</p> <p>Explanation of the scope of the study (fish/shellfish) added</p>

MS	Date	Feedback	Response provided	Change made
		<p>3. Data for the United Kingdom was not included in the study.</p> <p>4. 2017 data for Norway was included in the study; data for the years 2018 to 2023 is not present. Would the same methods used for 2017 also have been used for the period 2018 to 2023?</p> <p>5. The proposal is based on data reported by Member States up to 2023. Would aquaculture industry representatives or aquaculture operators have additional information on methods or industry standards?</p> <p>6. We are aware of two other methods for measuring total nitrogen and total organic carbon:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Aquaculture Stewardship Council (ASC): Section 8.2 of ASC-STD-001-ASC-Farm-Standard-V1.0-May 2025. o Wang, Xinxin & Andresen, Kjersti & Handå, Aleksander & Jensen, Bjorn & Reitan, Kjell Inge & Olsen, Yngvar. (2013). Chemical composition and release rate of waste discharge from an Atlantic salmon farm with an evaluation of IMTA feasibility. Aquaculture Environment Interactions. 4. 147-162. 10.3354/aei00079. 	<p>3. Since the UK is no longer one of the countries required to report emissions on the portal, we have decided not to take their data into account, as it would have been difficult to obtain additional information from them, as was the case with the other countries.</p> <p>4. Norway has not reported data in the Portal after 2017 despite being an EEA member and their obligation to do so. They do complete their national Norway and confirmed to us both in their questionnaire and during the interview that the method most frequently cited in 2017 is still used to calculate emissions from Norwegian installations.</p> <p>5. For some countries (mainly Spain), it is actually the industry representatives that gave us input on the methods.</p> <p>6. Thank you for the two additional methods, we will take them into account in the final report.</p>	

Annex 9 List of default values available for some parameters in formula used by countries to assess emissions to water from aquaculture facilities

Table A9.6: List of default values available for some parameters in the formula involving feed composition, fish composition, feed and fish biomass (Finland, Norway, Sweden, HELCOM and OSPAR) to assess emissions to water

Country using the method	Parameter code	Parameter	Default value	Fish species concerned	Pollutant concerned	Type of feed	Source of values	Last update	
Finland	-	Feed composition	6%	-	N	-	Given by Finland during the consultation with Member States	Unspecified	
			0.7%	-	P	-		Unspecified	
	-	Fish composition	2.75%	-	N	-		Unspecified	
			0.4%	-	P	-		Unspecified	
	-	Food conversion ratio	1.10	-	-	-		Unspecified	
Norway	C1	Feed composition	5.84%	-	N	-	Average C1 and C2 factors were calculated by Norwegian authorities from questionnaires sent to Norwegian fish feed companies about different feed-types and fish composition	2015	
			0.96%	-	P	-		2015	
			49%	-	TOC	-		2011	
	C2	Fish composition	2.96%	-	N	-		Given by Norway after the interview	2011
			0.45%	-	P	-			2011
			37%	-	TOC	-			2011
	FCR	Food conversion ratio	1.18	Salmon	-	-	FCR is calculated nationally by Norwegian authorities from reports on feed and fish production received from Norwegian aquaculture facilities	2022	
			1.37	Trout	-	-		2022	
Sweden	FK	Feed coefficient	0.8 – 1.2	Small fish (< 1 kg)	-	-	Naturvårdsverket, 1993, Fiskodling, planering, tillstånd, tillsyn. Almäna råd 93:10, Naturvårdsverket. Also given by Sweden in its questionnaire	1993	
			1.0 – 1.5	Large fish	-	-		1993	
	CP	Percentage of pollutant in feed	5 – 8%	-	N	-		1993	
			0.8 – 1%	-	P	-		1993	
	CR	Percentage of pollutant in fish biomass	2.5 – 3.5%	-	N	-		1993	
			0.4%	-	P	-		1993	

Country using the method	Parameter code	Parameter	Default value	Fish species concerned	Pollutant concerned	Type of feed	Source of values	Last update
HELCOM / OSPAR	FCR	Feed conversion ratio	1.1	Big fish over 800g	-	-	HELCOM, 2022, HELCOM Guidelines for the annual and periodical compilation and reporting of waterborne pollution inputs to the Baltic Sea. / OSPAR, 2015, Guidelines for Harmonised Quantification and Reporting Procedures for Nutrient (HARP-NUT), Guideline 2: Quantification and Reporting of Nitrogen and Phosphorus Discharges/Losses from Aquaculture Plants.	2022
			0.8 – 1.0	Fish between 30g and 800g	-	-		2022
			0.6	Fingerlings	-	-		2022
	Cf	Percentage of pollutant in fish	0.4%	Trout	P	-		2022
			0.43%	Freshwater fish up to 800g	P	-		2022
			0.414%	Freshwater fish over 800g	P	-		2022
			2.5%	Trout	N	-		2022
			2.75%	Freshwater fish up to 800g	N	-		2022
			2.95%	Freshwater fish over 800g	N	-		2022
			Ci	Percentage of pollutant in feed	0.9%	-		P
	0.5%	-			P	Semi-moist feed (dry matter 35-80%)		2022
	0.45%	-			P	Moist feed (dry matter < 35%)		2022
	7.0%	Big fish			N	Dry feed (dry matter > 80%)		2022
	7.5%	Small fish, fingerlings and fry			N	Dry feed (dry matter > 80%),		2022
	5.0%	-			N	Semi-moist feed (dry matter 35-80%)		2022
2.5%	-	N			Moist feed (dry matter < 35%)	2022		

Table A9.7: List of default values available for some parameters in the formula involving feed, particulate nutrient, biomass and dissolved/excreted nutrient (Cyprus, Greece, Iceland and Spain) to assess emissions to water

Country using the method	Fish species concerned	Pollutant concerned	Percentage of nutrient supplied through feed				Method / Source	Last update
			Fish retention / Biomass	Particulate (uneaten feed and faeces)	Excretion / Dissolved inorganic	Dissolved organic		
Cyprus / Greece	Sea bass	N	Unspecified	5%-7%	Unspecified	-	Tsapakis, M., et al., 2006. Nutrients and fine particulate matter released from sea bass (<i>Dicentrarchus labrax</i>) farming., <i>Aquatic Living Resources</i> , 19, 69–75.	2006
	Sea bass	P	Unspecified	Unspecified	13%-16%	-		2006
Iceland	Salmon	N	37%	15%	45%	3%	Wang, X., et al., 2012, Discharge of nutrient wastes from salmon farms: environmental effects, and potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture, <i>Aquaculture Environment Interactions</i> , 2, 267–283.	2012
	Salmon	P	30%	44%	18%	8%		2012
Spain	Sea bream	N	22%	10%	61%	7%	Lupatsch, Y., et al., 1998, Predicting aquaculture waste from gilthead seabream (<i>Sparus aurata</i>) culture using a nutritional approach, <i>Aquatic Living Resources</i> , 11, 265–268.	1998
	Sea bream	P	29%	44%	19%	8%		1998
	Sea bream	N	21%	15%	65%	-	Vergara Martín, J.M., et al., 2005, Evaluación de impacto Ambiental de acuicultura en jaulas en Canarias, <i>Oceanografía</i> .	2005
	Sea bream	P	30%	47%	23%	-		2005
	Sea bass	N	18%	20%	61%	-		2005
	Sea bass	P	33%	48%	20%	-		2005

Annex 10 Country data sheets

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	AUSTRIA	
EU member ?	EU member	
Contact organization	Environment Agency Austria	
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	2 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	-	-	-	-	-	-	2023	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	-	-	-	-	-	-	NH3	-	-	-

<i>Review per pollutant and method</i>	Data available on emissions into water? No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review
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Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

Legend: - 7.(a) facilities reporting water emissions - 7.(a) facilities reporting air emissions - 7.(b) facilities reporting water emissions - 7.(b) facilities reporting air emissions	- Measurement - Calculations - Estimation - No data	- Measurement - Calculations - Estimation - No data
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INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Yes in an email: 06/11/2024
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology/ guide - Other reason	In Austria, facilities in the sector poultry and pigs consider they don't have any water emissions. Waste waters from cleaning pig houses and poultry houses go to the slurry and are as a last step land spread.

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	BELGIUM	
EU member ?	EU member	
Contact organization	(Walloon) Service Public de Wallonie / (Flanders) Vlaamse Milieumaatschappij	
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

<i>Review per activity</i>										
Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	71 facilities	0 facilities	75 facilities	0 facilities	5 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	-	2023	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3	-	NH3	-	NH3	-	-	-	-	-

<i>Review per pollutant and method</i>	Data available on emissions into water? No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review
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Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Yes: 29/11/2024
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	<p>X Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions</p> <p>Answer Walloon region: The facilities consider themselves to have no emissions to water. In fact, emitted liquid effluents are directly recovered into controlled storage tanks. Those tanks are then managed under waste legislation.</p> <p>Answer Flemish region: In Flanders, air emissions from installations with E-PRTR activities 7.(a) are obtained on the basis of model results. For water emissions, installations with E-PRTR activities 7.(a) are considered out of scope. In most cases they do not have a discharge permit. It is assumed that industrial waste water from stables disappears into the manure pits, after which it is spread or removed for processing, and is therefore not registered as discharge or transfer of waste water.</p> <p>Answer Brussels capital region: There are no poultry, pigs and/or sow farms in the Brussels capital region who fall under IED.</p>

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	BULGARIA (1/2)	
EU member ?	EU member	
Contact organization	Environmental Executive Agency	
Group	Group 3: Countries reporting air emissions and emissions to water from 7.(a) facilities	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	49 facilities 2023	2 facilities 2018	25 facilities 2023	2 facilities 2023	2 facilities 2023	0 facilities	4 facilities 2023	1 facilities 2022	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year			NH3,CH4,N2O, PM10	N,P	NH3,CH4,PM10 ,NOx	-	NH3,CH4	Cd,Pb,Zn	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3,N2O	N,P,TOC								

Review per pollutant and method

Activity	Specific method	Nb of facilities reporting emissions into water for this pollutant between 2017 and 2023, and according to which specific method									
		N	P	TOC	Phenols	As	Cd	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
7.(a).(i): poultry farms	M: No further details	2	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7.(a).(ii): pig farms	C: Use of an european-wide sector specific calculation method	8	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	ND: No data on the method used	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7.(a): unspecified farms	M: No further details	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1

Legend: C=Calculated, calculation method used E=Estimated M=Measured, analytical method used ND=No data on the method

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send?	Answer to questionnaire?
Yes: 29/10/2024	Yes: 20/03/2025 and supplement on 16/09/2025

- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR data, for the last 4 years, 81% of total reporting water emissions from this sector by your country has been based on calculations. Most of these facilities used the following method "European-wide sector specific calculation method". We would like to get more details on this methodology and the way emissions are assessed. If this is based on a guide or national text, could you send it to us or provide a link?	Most Regional Inspectorates of Environment and Water, which are involved in verifying the data submitted by operators on emissions from their installations, indicate that the reported emissions are calculated on the basis of "wastewater volume" and "concentration of a pollutant per unit volume of water". The indicator "concentration of a pollutant per unit volume of water" represents average values of a given pollutant per unit volume of water, obtained through emission control (own and/or control) carried out by an accredited laboratory. The average value of the respective pollutant is obtained as the arithmetic mean of all measurements of emissions in wastewater during the year. The calculation of emissions in water by accredited laboratories is carried out using various methods and in accordance with the established requirements of the selected method (European standards, national standards, etc.). To calculate emissions to water from the installation, operators most often use the following equation: $P \text{ [kg/y]} = D \text{ [m}^3\text{/y]} \times Q \text{ [mg/dm}^3\text{]} \times 10^{-3}$ Where: P [kg/y] – emissions in wastewater in tons per year, D [m ³ /y] – wastewater flow rate for the given year, measured with a flowmeter; Q [mg/dm ³] – measured amount of pollutant during own monitoring /average value of the indicator from all measurements/. There are no generally applicable or sectoral national documents/methodologies developed on the basis of which emissions from installations can be calculated, therefore they are not used. A guidance document for the implementation of Regulation (EC) № 166/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 January 2006 concerning the establishment of a European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register is available on the website of the Executive Environment Agency. (https://eea.government.bg/forms/files/EPTR_guidance.pdf)
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	There are no national documents, methodologies and/or manuals to help operators calculate the emissions generated in water from the installations they operate, which are for a specific sector. A guidance document for the implementation of Regulation № 166/2006 (in Bulgarian) is available on the website of the Executive Environment Agency: (https://eea.government.bg/forms/files/EPTR_guidance.pdf) A methodology for inventorying emissions of harmful substances into the air (according to EMEP/CORINAIR 2006) is also used, which is also uploaded to the website of the Executive Environment Agency: https://eea.government.bg/bg/legislation/air/methodology/

BULGARIA (2/2)

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	<p>Could you also provide us more details on the method(s) used by the other facilities using calculations? How is it done?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mass balance - Emission factors - Equations - Other 	<p>According to the information provided by one of the RIEW: the annual load of pollutants in kg/y is calculated using a mass balance; a laboratory analysis of chemical oxygen demand (COD) is performed using emission factors; total organic carbon is calculated using equations using the formula: COD divided by 3 and then the annual load is calculated.</p> <p>Another RIEW indicates that operators calculate emissions to water from their installations using a balance method and emission factors according to BAT 3 and BAT 4 of the Commission implementing decision (EU) 2017/302 of 15 February 2017 establishing best available techniques (BAT) conclusions, under Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council, for the intensive rearing of poultry or pigs.</p> <p>We draw your attention to the fact that, as described above, a large part of operators calculate emissions from their installations using the above formula, with some of them defining it as a "measurement" method, and others as a "calculation" method, since the formula takes values from water emission measurement protocols carried out by an accredited laboratory, but at the same time a calculation is performed to obtain an average value of the pollutant on an annual basis and the amount of emissions generated by the installation for the relevant year.</p>
Emissions factors	<p>If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Database - Measurement - Other 	<p align="center">X Measurement</p> <p>According to the information provided by RIEW, which are responsible for verifying the data submitted by operators on emissions from their installations, the emission factors used to calculate emissions from installations are based on measurements carried out by an accredited laboratory. One of the RIEW indicates that some of the operators carry out the calculations based on the emission factors in BAT 3 and BAT 4 of the Commission implementing decision (EU) 2017/302 of 15 February 2017 establishing best available techniques (BAT) conclusions, under Directive 2010/75/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council, for the intensive rearing of poultry or pigs.</p>
Emissions factors	<p>What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?</p>	<p>Depending on the frequency of monitoring of emissions into water set in the operators' permits. For some installations, for example, the frequency is once a month, i.e. 12 protocols from an accredited laboratory for the year.</p>
Uncertainty	<p>What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?</p>	<p>According to the information provided by the RIEW, which are responsible for verifying the data submitted by operators on emissions from their installations, most of the reported values were obtained on the basis of water monitoring carried out by an accredited laboratory and subsequent use of these values to calculate emissions from a given installation for the relevant year. When measuring emissions in water by accredited laboratories, the probability of deviations in measurements is minimal. Given this, the calculations made on the basis of the measured values have a minimal probability of deviations. The uncertainty is within the framework of the method used by the accredited laboratory to determine the amount of pollutant</p> <p>One of the RIEW indicates that the uncertainty in reporting the test results of samples taken at the outlet of the wastewater treatment plant is about 4% for the COD indicator and 3.5% for the total phosphorus indicator in this particular case.</p>
Scope	<p>What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions 	<p align="center">X Channelled emissions</p> <p>Most of the emissions to water included in the final results are channelled emissions – from a sewer system, which may include different types of water streams (e.g. production water, domestic sewage, rainwater, etc.) or may cover only one water stream. Which wastewater streams are taken into account depends on the specifics of the installation and the wastewater streams that are formed by it.</p>
Scope	<p>Which sources of water emissions are included?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wash water from cleaning buildings and storages - Wastewater from exhaust air treatment - Manure run-off - Other source 	<p align="center">X Wash water from cleaning buildings and storages X Manure run-off</p> <p>In pig farms in Bulgaria, most often the production wastewater from washing the pig houses, together with the manure and slurry is taken to basin for manure. Then the manure, slurry and production wastewater are used to fertilize agricultural land or are taken to biogas production plants. In some pig farms the biogas plant is in the immediate vicinity of the pig farm and the production wastewater from cleaning the pig houses and the manure and slurry are directly fed into the separation and treatment plant in order to obtain fertilizer for agricultural land and biogas.</p> <p>In some cases, the manure, slurry and production wastewater also include domestic wastewater from the personnel. In other cases, the domestic wastewater from the personnel are stored in a storage tank and are transferred to licensed companies for their purification. Usually, rainwater is not captured and treated, but is directly absorbed into the site, as it is not considered polluted due to the type of activity performed and the fact that it is carried out in closed houses.</p> <p>In most cases, poultry farms do not have production wastewater, as dry cleaning is used in the poultry houses, usually with a steam jet, where only steam is released during cleaning. Manure is removed from the poultry houses by conveyor belts or is being scraped. The manure is usually taken away for fertilizing agricultural land or for biogas production.</p> <p>In most poultry farms, there is also a flow of domestic wastewater from the personnel who service the site. This water is usually collected and stored in storage tank, and then transferred to licensed companies for purification.</p> <p>Rainwater is usually not captured and treated, but is directly absorbed into the site, as it is not considered polluted due to the type of activity carried out and the fact that it is carried out in closed halls.</p>
Scope	<p>Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?</p>	<p>In some installations, water treatment is not taken into account, since the monitoring of emissions is carried out before their discharge into the urban sewer and before the water treatment in the wastewater treatment plant. In other installations, water treatment is taken into account, but it is not possible to calculate the % of emission reduction, since water monitoring is carried out only at the exit of the wastewater treatment plant, but not at the entrance.</p>
Scope	<p>Which pathways are included in the scope?</p>	<p>When reporting emissions from intensive poultry and/or pig farming installations, the wastewater flow from the installation is taken into account, such as from washing of the animal housing, manure runoff, etc. – that is, the production wastewater flow. In some installations, the flow of domestic sewage and rainwater is also taken into account. Which wastewater flows are taken into account depends on the specifics of the particular installation and the wastewater flows generated by it.</p>
Reporting	<p>Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?</p>	<p>Some operators hire external companies to calculate emissions from their installations on their behalf, while other operators carry out their own calculations.</p>
Reporting	<p>What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?</p>	<p>Operators must report information in the annual environmental reports and in the national reporting system on PRTR on the quantities of wastewater discharged from the installation, on the monitoring of emissions into wastewater for the pollutants regulated in the permit, as well as information on the quantities of pollutants discharged into water or pollutants transferred into wastewater off-site, intended for processing or treatment, or the transfer of water through sewers and other means on the site.</p>

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?	Date of interview?
No	-

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	CROATIA
EU member ?	EU member
Contact organization	Ministry of Environmental Protection and Green Transition
Group	Group 5: Countries not reporting any emissions (air or water) from 7.(b) facilities

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Additional informations	Since 2007, Croatia did not report any air emission or emission to water from 7.(a) or 7.(b) facilities in the database, even though it contains some facilities classified 7.(a). However, it reported emissions for other sectors from 2014 to 2023.									

Review per pollutant and method

Data available on emissions into water?
No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Yes: 25/11/2024
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- For 7.(b) facilities: aquaculture facilities

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	X Other reason Facilities need a detailed guide on how to assess water emissions. Additionally, further clarification is needed on whether these emissions are considered point source emissions or diffuse emissions to water. All aquaculture facilities under the scope of EPRTR in Croatia are marine aquaculture. We look forward to receiving further guidelines and recommendations.

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	CYPRUS	
EU member ?	EU member	
Contact organization	-	
Group	Group 2: Countries reporting emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities but not 7.(a) facilities	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

<i>Review per activity</i>										
Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	18 facilities	0 facilities	24 facilities	0 facilities	1 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	5 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	-	2023	-	-	-	-	2023
Pollutant(s)	NH3	-	NH3,CH4	-	NH3	-	-	-	-	N,P

<i>Review per pollutant and method</i>										
Activity	Specific method									
7.(b): aquaculture facilities	C: Use of mass balance method									
	ND: No data on the method used									
	N	P	TOC	Phenols	As	Cd	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
	28	29	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	5	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Legend: C=Calculated, calculation method used E=Estimated M=Measured, analytical method used ND=No data on the method

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Partially in an email: 27/05/2025
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	No response

- For 7.(b) facilities: aquaculture facilities

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR, for the last 4 years, 100% of total reporting water emissions has been based on calculations, more specifically on the following method "Mass balance, based on fish production". We would like to get more details on this methodology and the way emissions are assessed. - If this is based on a guide or national text, could you send it to us or provide a link? - Are factor emissions used along the annual fish production to assess emissions? - If so, where do these emissions factors come from?	Regarding your question about the methodology, this is done according to The Tsapakis et al. (2006) model which is a mass balance model that is used to calculate the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus released from fish farms into the water column. It takes into account inputs from fish feed and calculates the amount harvested as fish (tonnes), as well as the amount excreted in dissolved and particulate forms. This model helps assess the impact of fish farming on water quality by quantifying the nutrient loads released from fish farms. The model is a component of a larger 3-D hydrodynamic/biogeochemical model, according to a study on modelling the impact of finfish aquaculture waste.
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No response
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	No response
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	No response
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	No response
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions	No response
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Excess nutrients - Faeces from animals - Equipment - Chemicals used (e.g. medication, treatments, antifoulants) - Other source	No response
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	No response
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	No response
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	No response

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	CZECHIA
EU member ?	EU member
Contact organization	Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	131 facilities	0 facilities	114 facilities	0 facilities	37 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2022	-	2022	-	2022	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3	-	NH3,PM10,NOx	-	NH3,SOx,NOx,CO	-	-	-	-	-

Additional informations Data from Czechia for the year 2023 is not present in the database for any sector. Only information from 2017 to 2022 is taken in account in the present study.

Review per pollutant and method

Data available on emissions into water?	
No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review	

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Yes: 08/01/2025
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	X Other reason There may be several reasons for not reporting releases to water for these activities. First of all, I would mention that facilities of this type are often located on the outskirts or completely outside the urban area – often in rural areas with poorer infrastructure. It can therefore be assumed that they have no connection to the sewage system and use drainless cesspools. In this case, there can be no releases to water at all. If they are connected to a Sewerage System, it may only be a connection to normal wastewater from social facilities etc. and not a connection from the actual operation of the installation or facility. In these cases, if the relevant thresholds are exceeded, they would be obliged to report transfers of substances in the wastewater. According to the reported data, the quantities of pollutants that would have to be reported do not appear to be generated anyway. If the facilities in this case have their own wastewater treatment plant, it is likely that the thresholds for releases to water are not exceeded. The manure and slurry produced are most likely to be reused within the facility. In any case, we will consult with the Czech Environmental Inspectorate to find out whether it should focus more on these types of releases and transfers from the activities concerned.

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	DENMARK	
EU member ?	EU member	
Contact organization	Ministry of Environment and Gender Equality	
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	67 facilities	0 facilities	135 facilities	0 facilities	44 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	-	2023	-	0 facilities (2016)	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3	-	NH3	-	NH3	-	-	-	-	-

Review per pollutant and method

Data available on emissions into water?	
No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review	

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Yes: 18/12/2024
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	X Other reason : Wastewater is usually mixed with animal manure and spread on agricultural fields as fertilizer.

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	ESTONIA
EU member ?	EU member
Contact organization	Estonian Environment Agency
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	10 facilities	0 facilities	23 facilities	0 facilities	2 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	-	2021	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3,SOx	-	NH3,CH4	-	NH3	-	-	-	-	-

Review per pollutant and method

Data available on emissions into water?
No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send?	Answer to questionnaire?
Yes: 29/10/2024	Yes: 28/11/2024

- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	X Other reason : Wastewater from farms (i.e. water from washing production premises/equipment, wastewater from utility rooms) is directed to the liquid manure storage, where it gets mixed with manure. Manure is spreaded to the fields with accordance with requirements of Estonian Water Act or used in biogas production.

- For 7.(b) facilities: aquaculture facilities

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	In Estonia permits given to aquaculture farms regulate the N and P emissions to water (no TOC or metals are regulated) according to our aquaculture regulation. In this regulation there is a calculation method: Emission of N (or P) to the water= [(Nfeed × Mfeed) – (Nfish × Mfish)] / 100%, where Nfeed – the % of N in the feed; Nfish – the % of N in the fish Mfeed – the used amount of feed (kg); Mfish – the amount of produced fish (kg) Until now in Estonia there have not been aquaculture farms big enough to exceed the E-PRTR threshold, but in coming years some of them will probably exceed the threshold.

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?	Date of interview?
No	-

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	FINLAND		
EU member ?	EU member		
Contact organization	Ministry of the Environment of Finland and Finnish Environment Institute		
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities		

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	113 facilities	0 facilities	27 facilities	0 facilities	16 facilities	0 facilities	2 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	-	2022	-	2017	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3	-	NH3	-	NH3	-	NH3	-	-	-

Review per pollutant and method

Data available on emissions into water?
No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send?	Answer to questionnaire?
Yes: 29/10/2024	Yes: 09/11/2024

- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	X Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions It is considered that animal shelters do not cause a point load on the water body. Bottom structures of animal shelters and manure storage facilities must be watertight to prevent contamination of surface and groundwater. In some cases, water samples have been analysed before and after the animal shelter, and the results support the assumption that there would be no point loading. Scattered pollution caused by manure spread on fields is not covered in the environmental permit.

- For 7.(b) facilities: aquaculture facilities

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	We would like to get details on the methodology and the way emissions are assessed for your aquaculture facilities.	In Finland, the calculation is only made on the last year's (food fish) production. Feed composition P = 0.7% N = 6% Fish composition P = 0.4% N = 2.75% Food conversion ratio 1.10 (salmon)

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?	Date of interview?
No	-

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	FRANCE		
EU member ?	EU member		
Contact organization	Ministry of Ecological Transition and Territorial Cohesion		
Group	Group 2: Countries reporting emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities but not 7.(a) facilities		

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity										
Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	338 facilities	0 facilities	492 facilities	0 facilities	39 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	1 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	-	2023	-	-	-	(2009)	2023
Pollutant(s)	NH3,CH4,N2O,PM10	-	NH3,CH4,N2O	-	NH3,CH4	-	-	-	-	N,P,TOC

Review per pollutant and method											
Activity	Specific method	Nb of facilities reporting emissions into water for this pollutant between 2017 and 2023, and according to which specific method									
		N	P	TOC	Phenols	As	Cd	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
7.(b): aquaculture facilities	M: Calculations from measurement data (flow and concentration)	1	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	ND: No data on the method used	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Legend: C=Calculated, calculation method used; E=Estimated; M=Measured, analytical method used; ND=No data on the method

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Yes: 02/12/2024
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	X Water emissions are below the threshold X Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions The threshold of 50 t of nitrogen corresponds to farms with a very large number of animals, of the order of 900,000 places for poultry or 3,000 places for sows. X Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide X Other reason: A precise and detailed methodology should be developed by the European Commission and made compulsory for all in order to standardise the declarations associated with emissions from livestock farms and fish farms.

- For 7.(b) facilities: aquaculture facilities

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR, for the last 4 years, 100% of total reporting water emissions by aquaculture facilities in your country has been based on "mass balance method", could you provide us more details on the method used? How is it done?	The mass balance involves determining the proportion of nutrients (particularly nitrogen and phosphate) that are excreted/rejected. A subtraction is made between incoming flows (feed rations) and outgoing flows (body retention associated with zootechnical performance).
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	Not concerned: no emission factors used
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	Not concerned: no emission factors used
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	No response
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	X Channelled emissions
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Excess nutrients - Faeces from animals - Equipment - Chemicals used (e.g. medication, treatments, antifoulants) - Other source	X Excess nutrients X Faeces from animals
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	No response
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	No
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	Pollutants specific to the activity.

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	GERMANY				
EU member ?	EU member				
Contact organization	German Environment Agency				
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities				

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	200 facilities	0 facilities	390 facilities	0 facilities	122 facilities	0 facilities	8 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	-	2023	-	2023	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3,N2O,PM1		NH3,CH4,N2O		NH3		NH3		-	

Review per pollutant and method	Data available on emissions into water? No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review
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Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

Legend:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 7.(a) facilities reporting water emissions 7.(a) facilities reporting air emissions 7.(b) facilities reporting water emissions 7.(b) facilities reporting air emissions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measurement Calculations Estimation No data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measurement Calculations Estimation No data
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INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Yes: 27/01/2025
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	<p>Why do facilities report no water emissions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason 	<p>X Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions</p> <p>water emissions from "intensive livestock farming" (activities according to Annex 1 under No. 7(a), 7(a)(i), 7(a)(ii) and 7(a)(iii) of the E-PRTR Regulation) have not been reported from Germany in the context of PRTR reporting since 2007 because direct discharge of waste water from intensive livestock farming is legally not permitted in Germany.</p> <p>(Side note: we see that in other MS [AT, BE, CH, CY, CZ, DK, EE, FI, FR, GB, GR, HR, IE, IT, LT, LU, LV, MT, NL, NO, PL, SK] no releases to water from activities according to No. 7(a)* of the E-PRTR Regulation were reported in the years 2007 to 2022 either)</p> <p>All liquids produced in stable, e.g. liquid manure, slurry or cleaning water, are collected in liquid manure (slurry) channels or in approved containers and then spread on agricultural land</p> <p>Regarding intensive livestock farming, the water used is combined with the slurry produced and treated as slurry, so there is no wastewater as defined by the Federal Water Act.</p> <p>However, the BAT conclusions (Best Available Technique) number 7 contain measures to reduce wastewater emissions. The term waste water refers to wash water from exhaust air purification systems. Precipitation water occurring at the sites is not production-specific wastewater and is therefore not covered by the BAT conclusions regarding wastewater emissions.</p> <p>An example of a procedure used in laying hen/grandparent stock facilities: No production-related wastewater is produced in these facilities. Any chicken droppings produced are transported out of the stables via belts on which the droppings dry and collected. The dry manure is then disposed of as required and utilised for agricultural purposes.</p>

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	GREECE
EU member ?	EU member
Contact organization	Ministry of Environment and Energy
Group	Group 2: Countries reporting emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities but not 7.(a) facilities

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	2 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	3 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2023
Pollutant(s)	NH3,N2O	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	N,P

Review per pollutant and method

Activity	Specific method	Nb of facilities reporting emissions into water for this pollutant between 2017 and 2023, and according to which specific method									
		N	P	TOC	Phenols	As	Cd	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
7.(b): aquaculture facilities	E: No further details	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	ND: No data on the method used	10	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Legend: C=Calculated, calculation method used; E=Estimated; M=Measured, analytical method used; ND=No data on the method

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send?	Answer to questionnaire?
Yes: 29/10/2024	Yes: 18/12/2024

- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	X Water emissions are below the threshold

- For 7.(b) facilities: aquaculture facilities

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on the E-PRTR, 100% of total reporting water emissions by your country has been based on estimations, could you provide us more details on the method used? How is it done? - Mass balance - Emission factors - Equations - Other	X Mass balance considering the composition of feeds and bibliographical estimations
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No there are not.
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	Not concerned: no emission factors used
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	Not concerned: no emission factors used
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	No response
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	X Diffuse emissions
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Excess nutrients - Faeces from animals - Equipment - Chemicals used (e.g. medication, treatments, antifoulants) - Other source	X Excess nutrients
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	In some farms they have automatic feeding systems for optimal use of the feed. Also, they use high-quality feed with optimal conversion rate. Therefore, the diffuse emission from the feed is as little as possible. However, they cannot estimate the percentage of reduction yet.
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	They report on their behalf.
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	The quantity of the feed in use.

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?	Date of interview?
No	-

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	HUNGARY	
EU member ?	EU member	
Contact organization	-	
Group	Group 3: Countries reporting air emissions and emissions to water from 7.(a) facilities	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	312 facilities	1 facilities	208 facilities	1 facilities	30 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	2018	2023	2017	2023	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3,CH4	Phenols	NH3,CH4	P	NH3,CH4	-	-	-	-	-
Additional informations	The last year in which 7.(a) facilities from Hungary reported emissions into water was 2018, although some of these facilities have reported air emissions since then.									

Review per pollutant and method

Activity	Specific method	Nb of facilities reporting emissions into water for this pollutant between 2017 and 2023, and according to which specific method									
		N	P	TOC	Phenols	As	Cd	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
7.(a).(i): poultry farms	M: No further details	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
7.(a).(ii): pig farms	M: No further details	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Legend: C=Calculated, calculation method used; E=Estimated; M=Measured, analytical method used; ND=No data on the method

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? No
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR data, some facilities from your country assess water emissions based on calculations, could you provide us more details on the method used? How is it done? - Mass balance - Emission factors - Equations - Other	No response
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No response
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	No response
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	No response
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	No response
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	No response
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Wash water from cleaning buildings and storages - Wastewater from exhaust air treatment - Manure run-off - Other source	No response
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	No response
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	No response
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	No response
Reporting	Why did pig and poultry farms stop reporting water emissions since 2018? - Water emissions are below the threshold since 2018 - Other reason	No response

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	ICELAND (1/2)
EU member ?	non-EU member
Contact organization	EA Iceland
Group	Group 1: Countries reporting air emissions and emissions to water from 7.(a) facilities and emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	7 facilities	0 facilities	1 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	13 facilities
Last reporting year	2022	-	2020	(2010)	-	-	-	-	-	2022
Pollutant(s)	NH3,CH4,PM10		NH3,CH4,PM10		-	-	-	-	-	N,P,Ni
Additional informations	Data from Iceland for the year 2023 is not present in the database for any sector. Only information from 2017 to 2022 is taken in account in the present study. For the last seven years, Iceland only reported air emissions from 7.(a) facilities, but before that, it had reported emissions to water from them (last reporting year: 2010).									

Review per pollutant and method

Activity	Specific method	Nb of facilities reporting emissions into water for this pollutant between 2017 and 2023, and according to which specific method									
		N	P	TOC	Phenols	As	Cd	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
7.(b): aquaculture facilities	C: Calculations based on "Discharge of nutrient wastes from salmon farms"	22	22	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	C: No further details	2	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	E: No further details	19	19	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0

Legend: C=Calculated, calculation method used E=Estimated M=Measured, analytical method used ND=No data on the method

Additional informations on methods

For some aquaculture facilities, calculations based on the Norwegian scientific study by Wang X et al., Discharge of nutrient wastes from salmon farms: environmental effects, and potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture, published in the Aquaculture Environment Interactions in 2013.

In the document, the formula used is $I = A + F = G + E + F$

Where: I is food intake, A is assimilated food (the part that is digested by fish and taken up in tissues), F is defecation, G is growth or retention in biomass and E is excretion.

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? No
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Could you provide us more details on the method used by the facilities from your country to assess water emissions? How is it done? - Mass balance - Emission factors - Equations - Other	No response
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No response
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	No response
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	No response
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results? What is the scope of the emissions?	No response
Scope	What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	No response
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Wash water from cleaning buildings and storages - Wastewater from exhaust air treatment - Manure run-off - Other source	No response
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	No response

ICELAND (2/2)

Question theme	Question	Answer
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	No response
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	No response
- For 7.(b) facilities: aquaculture facilities		
Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR, for the last 4 years, 62% of total reporting water emissions of aquaculture in your country has been based on calculations. Most of these facilities used the following document "Wang X, Olsen LM, Reitan KI, Olsen Y (2012) Discharge of nutrient wastes from salmon farms: environmental effects, and potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture. Aquacult Environ Interact 2:267-283". We would like to get more details on this methodology and the way emissions are assessed. Could you provide us more details on the other method(s) used by the other facilities using calculations? How is it done when it is not salmon farms? - Mass balance - Emission factors - Equations - Other	No response
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No response
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	No response
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	No response
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	No response
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	No response
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Excess nutrients - Faeces from animals - Equipment - Chemicals used (e.g. medication, treatments, antifoulants) - Other source	No response
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	No response
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	No response
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	No response

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?

To be done

Date of interview?

30/04/2025

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR, some aquaculture facilities from your country assessed water emissions based on the following document "Wang X, Olsen LM, Reitan KI, Olsen Y (2012) Discharge of nutrient wastes from salmon farms: environmental effects, and potential for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture. Aquacult Environ Interact 2:267-283". . could you provide us more details on the method used? How is it done?	We use the formula given in the study, but measurement can be used as well. Some operators take water samples from the outflow and compare the results from measurement with those from the formula. Some farms use both methods, some use only formula, and some only measurement. The formula uses mostly feed composition, I will send you one example of an Excel file with the formula and parameter used The formula is used for each facility.
Methods	If you use the formula from the scientific study " $I = A + F = G + E + F$ ", how do you find each parameter ? What is their source ?	Parameters come mainly from the study, for example 44% of feed P released as particles.
Methods	Are the factors dependant on the geographical location? Could the same approach be used by other countries not in the Nordic region?	Yes I suppose it can be used by other countries.
Methods	Do you apply this formula to each pollutant?	Nitrogen and phosphorus only, not TOC.
Methods	Is the formula used only for salmons or other species ?	The same formula is used for every fish species because we don't have other formula.

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	IRELAND		
EU member ?	EU member		
Contact organization	Environmental Protection Agency		
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities		

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

<i>Review per activity</i>										
Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	19 facilities	0 facilities	91 facilities	0 facilities	12 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	-	2023	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3	-	NH3,CH4	-	NH3,CH4	-	-	-	-	-

<i>Review per pollutant and method</i>	Data available on emissions into water? No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review
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Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Yes: 29/11/2024
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	<p>Why do facilities report no water emissions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason 	<p>X Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions</p> <p>At EPA-licensed pig and poultry farms in Ireland, the animals are kept in housing, and the manure / litter from the animals is either collected in tanks under the housing or the litter is removed at the end of each growing period. These organic wastes are then removed from the growing sites and spread on land as a source of nutrients / fertiliser.</p> <p>There should be no emission to water of environmental significance from these sites. The only emission to water should be run-off from roofs and external yard areas, which should not contain pollutants. These non-process releases to ground or surface water may be monitored for BOD/COD and visually inspected.</p> <p>We look forward to the EEA methodology for the calculation of top-down water emissions for activities in Annex Ia of the IED (rearing of pig and poultry) and aquaculture.</p> <p>Please can you also confirm that further guidance and calculation methods, including emission factors per abatement technology, for livestock production and aquaculture will be provided for emissions to air.</p> <p>Currently the reporters use a toolkit to estimate fugitive emissions of ammonia, methane and nitrous oxide, based on animal / bird stock numbers in the houses and fugitive emissions from any uncovered manure / slurry storage.</p>

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	ITALY	
EU member ?	EU member	
Contact organization	Italian national institute for environment protection and research	
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	222 facilities	0 facilities	457 facilities	0 facilities	59 facilities	0 facilities	690 facilities	0 facilities	2 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	-	2023	-	2023	-	2022	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3,CH4,N2O, PM10,NOx	-	NH3,CH4,N2O, NOx	-	NH3,CH4	-	NH3,CH4,N2O	-	NH3	-

Additional informations 2 facilities from Italy reported air emissions from aquaculture facilities during the last seven years, probably by mistake.

Review per pollutant and method

Data available on emissions into water?
No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Yes: 28/11/2024
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	<p>Why do facilities report no water emissions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason 	<p>X Other reason</p> <p>Based on the permitting process of the IRPPs in Italy, please note that the great majority of the Italian IRPPs have no authorised discharges/releases to water bodies, because usually the IRPPs' wastewaters are managed in compliance with the Nitrates Directive (implemented locally by regional binding acts), therefore the reporting IRPPs are required to manage manure and slurries not as wastes or wastewaters but as inputs for subsequent agricultural practices such as landspreading or to be fed to on-site anaerobic digestion. Consequently, many of the reporting IRPPs are required to manage manure through permitted storage capacities (either for solid manure or for slurries) so the manure and the slurries resulting from the cleaning operations of the stables are generally collected into basins and tanks for the subsequent usage or processing.</p> <p>Based on the historical data reported by IRPP facilities to the Italian PRTR, very few of them have been reporting below the threshold values and, in general terms, the reported values were in fact related to domestic sewage (i.e collected from houses and offices which are part of the reporting facilities) rather than releases/transfers resulting from PRTR code 7.a activity.</p> <p>Finally, even taking into consideration the case of manure temporarily stored on site on the ground before landspreading operations, the amount of leachate resulting cannot be considered as releases to water or to land because the definitions are not applicable to this case.</p>

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	LATVIA	
EU member ?	EU member	
Contact organization	SLLC "Latvian Environment, Geology and Meteorology Centre"	
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	6 facilities	0 facilities	18 facilities	0 facilities	3 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	-	2023	-	(2012)	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3,N2O,PM1	-	NH3,CH4,NOx	-	NH3	-	-	-	-	-

<i>Review per pollutant and method</i>	Data available on emissions into water? No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review
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Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

Legend:	7.(a) facilities reporting water emissions	Measurement	Measurement
	7.(a) facilities reporting air emissions	Calculations	Calculations
	7.(b) facilities reporting water emissions	Estimation	Estimation
	7.(b) facilities reporting air emissions	No data	No data

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Yes: 30/10/2024
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	X Other reason Apparently, facilities of this sector are considered as being source of low significance regarding emissions into the water. Also, wastewater from these facilities is often collected in a storage tanks and then delivered to wastewater treatment plants with a trucks, and in this case, there are no direct emissions in the surface water. If no emissions are reporting, then measuring and reporting of these emissions are not required by the permits issued for the particular facilities (integrated permits of A or B category, C category permit or permit on use of water resources), as reporting is tightly connected with the requirements of permits. In national level, some emissions in the said sector show up, but in the national scale they are insignificant and thus likely under the threshold of significance.

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	LIECHTENSTEIN	
EU member ?	non-EU member	
Contact organization	-	
Group	None	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Additional informations	Although Liechtenstein is supposed to report emissions for its facilities, no emission is present in the database, for any sector.									

<i>Review per pollutant and method</i>	<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Data available on emissions into water?</th> </tr> <tr> <td>No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review</td> </tr> </table>	Data available on emissions into water?	No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review
Data available on emissions into water?			
No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review			

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

Legend: — 7.(a) facilities reporting water emissions — 7.(a) facilities reporting air emissions — 7.(b) facilities reporting water emissions — 7.(b) facilities reporting air emissions	— Measurement — Calculations — Estimation — No data	— Measurement — Calculations — Estimation — No data
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INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Questionnaire send?</th> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	Questionnaire send?	No	<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Answer to questionnaire?</th> </tr> <tr> <td>-</td> </tr> </table>	Answer to questionnaire?	-
Questionnaire send?					
No					
Answer to questionnaire?					
-					

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Interview done?</th> </tr> <tr> <td>No</td> </tr> </table>	Interview done?	No	<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Date of interview?</th> </tr> <tr> <td>-</td> </tr> </table>	Date of interview?	-
Interview done?					
No					
Date of interview?					
-					

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	LITHUANIA									
EU member ?	EU member									
Contact organization	-									
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities									

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	34 facilities	0 facilities	41 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	2 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2022	-	2022	-	-	-	2022	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3,PM10,NM VOC	-	NH3	-	-	-	NH3	-	-	-

Additional informations Data from Lithuania for the year 2023 is not present in the database for any sector. Only information from 2017 to 2022 is taken in account in the present study.

<i>Review per pollutant and method</i>	Data available on emissions into water?
	No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? No
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	No response

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	LUXEMBOURG		
EU member ?	EU member		
Contact organization	-		
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities		

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	1 facilities	0 facilities	8 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2019	-	2023	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3	-	NH3,CH4,N2O	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Review per pollutant and method

Data available on emissions into water?
No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? No
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	No response

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	MALTA
EU member ?	EU member
Contact organization	-
Group	Group 2: Countries reporting emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities but not 7.(a) facilities

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	3 facilities
Last reporting year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2022
Pollutant(s)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	N,P,TOC,Cu,Zn
Additional informations	Data from Malta for the year 2023 is not present in the database for any sector. Only information from 2017 to 2022 is taken into account in the present study.									

Review per pollutant and method

Activity	Specific method	Nb of facilities reporting emissions into water for this pollutant between 2017 and 2023, and according to which specific method									
		N	P	TOC	Phenols	As	Cd	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
7.(b): aquaculture facilities	C: Use of food conversion rate	3	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	E: No further details	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	ND: No data on the method used	13	13	5	0	0	0	1	0	0	5

Legend: C=Calculated, calculation method used E=Estimated M=Measured, analytical method used ND=No data on the method

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send?	Answer to questionnaire?
Yes: 29/10/2024	No

- For 7.(b) facilities: aquaculture facilities

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR, for the last 4 years, 100% of total reporting water emissions has been based on calculations, more specifically on one of the 2 following equations/methodologies "P=I-(F+R)" or "FCR". We would like to get more details on these 2 methodologies and the way emissions are assessed. If this is based on a guide or report, could you send it to us or provide a link?	No response
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No response
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	No response
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	No response
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	No response
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	No response
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Excess nutrients - Faeces from animals - Equipment - Chemicals used (e.g. medication, treatments, antifoulants) - Other source	No response
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	No response
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	No response
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	No response
Reporting	Why did aquaculture facilities stop reporting water emissions since 2019? - Water emissions are below the threshold since 2019 - These facilities stopped their activity - Other reason	No response

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?	Date of interview?
To be done	-

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	NETHERLANDS		
EU member ?	EU member		
Contact organization	-		
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities		

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	88 facilities	0 facilities	33 facilities	0 facilities	7 facilities	0 facilities	2 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	-	2023	-	2017	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3	-	NH3,CH4	-	NH3,CH4	-	NH3	-	-	-

<i>Review per pollutant and method</i>	Data available on emissions into water? No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review
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Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? No
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	No response

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	NORWAY (1/3)
EU member ?	non-EU member
Contact organization	Norwegian environment Agency
Group	Group 2: Countries reporting emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities but not 7.(a) facilities

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	617 facilities
Last reporting year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2017
Pollutant(s)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	N,P,TOC,Cu,Zn
Additional informations	Data from Norway for the years 2018 to 2023 is not present in the database for any sector. Only information from 2017 is taken into account in the present study.									

Review per pollutant and method

Activity	Specific method	Nb of facilities reporting emissions into water for this pollutant between 2017 and 2023, and according to which specific method									
		N	P	TOC	Phenols	As	Cd	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
7.(b): aquaculture facilities	C: No further details	431	617	617	0	0	0	54	0	0	617
Legend:	C=Calculated, calculation method used	E=Estimated			M=Measured, analytical method used			ND=No data on the method			

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send?	Answer to questionnaire?
Yes: 29/10/2024	Yes: 30/10/2024

- For 7.(b) facilities: aquaculture facilities

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on the E-PRTR, 100% of total reporting water emissions by your country has been based on calculations, could you provide us more details on the method used? How is it done? - Mass balance - Emission factors - Equations - Other	X Emission factors We (Norwegian Environment Agency) do the calculations based on activity data (annual feed amount) reported from each aquaculture facility and (our) factors (feed composition, fish composition, food conversion ratio). (Not sure whether activity data should be ticked on "mass balance" or "emission factors".) A part of the aquaculture is land-based (and increasing), with a discharge through a pipeline. Our regulation (permits) requires that many of these have to measure some of the pollutants (nitrogen, phosphorus) and the amount of water, in particular for those who use RAS (recirculating aquaculture systems). At the moment we don't use those data (not standardized), - but we will probably use them in the future.
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	Since the facilities (only) report activity data, we only need a regulation for that. The main regulation is § 44 in "forskrift om drift av akvakulturanlegg". The reporting process is monthly: -stocks of fish: species, number of fish and fish generation -biomass, -quantity of slaughter: species, number of fish, slaughter weight and slaughter condition, -removal of live fish: species, number and quantity -loss: mortality and other cause of loss, species, number of fish and quantity, -feed consumption in kilograms and main type of feed (dry, soft, wet) The regulation/reporting concern only aquaculture (fish). Art. 44 is limited to open cages, but could in theory be changed to include on land-based as well (art. 58 has a simple reporting process for hatchery fish (smolt). The reporting system/data has been more or less the same for about 20 years (it works).
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	The formula is general and uses mass balance: Discharge = c1*Feed - c2*Feed/FCR Where: c1 = feed composition (per year) c2 = fish composition (general) FCR = food conversation ratio (depends on the fish species) It is possible til calculate the FCR for each plant (each month or year), but in reality this introduce a lot of uncertainty (for instance biomass control and moving fish between facilities). Therefore, we calculate a national FCR for each generation (per fish species) since slaughter weight is measured precisely. We use this FCR to calculate the discharge for each facility (per year). Fish species: In particular salmon, but also trout.

NORWAY (2/3)

Question theme	Question	Answer
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	X Measurement Measurement studies (fish and feed composition)
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	We don't know. The uncertainty is large and variable when we calculate for the individual facility. It is probably significantly smaller at regional and national level. The uncertainty depends on the type of substance we calculate as well, it is probably least for phosphorus and nitrogen. It's possible to improve c1 somewhat, but that requires more data to be reported.
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	X Channelled emissions for land-based X Diffuse emissions (open cages)
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Excess nutrients - Faeces from animals - Equipment - Chemicals used (e.g. medication, treatments, antifoulants) - Other source	X Faeces from animals X Other source: Feed
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	Yes, for many land-based facilities (but we don't use those data)
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	The reporting system (ref. § 44) is digital (only). Directorate of fisheries is in lead, who distribute the data to us. Most operators buy a software for everyday use. The software extracts data reports the data automatically (more or less). A reporting example is shown below (the data is for a particular month several years ago, and the facility has three open cages). This is sensitive stock exchange data.
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	See above.
Reporting	The data collected in relation to those sites is not used. Is this because they do not reach the thresholds (either capacity or pollutant) to report under the Norwegian PRTR (or the data collected to report to the E-PRTR once this happens)?	Land-based farming can be divided into two: Production of hatchery fish (smolt) and production of food fish. The former has a limited size, but development is moving towards larger facilities at the same time as the limit in the new E-PRTR has been lowered from 1,000 to 500 tonnes. These report biomass data (but not quantity) monthly, and we expect that we will use that data as digitization progresses. The latter, which include large salmon smolt (postsmolt), has increased somewhat during the years. These are greater than the limit in E-PRTR. We receive analog emissions data (pdf-reports) from several of them, but the setup is not standardized. Therefore, we currently do not digitize/calculate the discharges.

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?	Date of interview?
Yes	25/03/2025

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Where does the formula "Discharge = c1*Feed – c2*Feed/FCR" come from ? What is its source ?	<p>Discharge calculation in Norway is adjusted from a mass balance formula. Two formula can be used to calculate discharge based on a simple mass balance (input-output): - Formula 1: Discharge= c1*Feed-c2*Biomass</p> <p>Where: c1: feed composition (N, P, Zn, etc.) (source: feed production companies) c2: fish composition (N, P, Zn, etc.) (source: articles, SEPA, etc) Feed: amount of feed used that year (source: monthly reports) -> dry feed in Norway (water content is stable) Biomass: biomass production that year (source: monthly reports) -> fish production (slaughtering), adjust for starving, bleeding and byproducts -> dead fish -> fish moved into the facility from another facility -> fish moved out the facility to another facility -> fish that escape</p> <p>Problem : it is sometimes difficult to obtain information on biomass at facility level, which can led to erroneous results</p> <p>That is why Norway use the 2nd formula. Formula 2 is just a reconfiguration of formula 1. -Formula 2: Discharge= c1*Feed-c2*Feed/FCR</p> <p>Where: c1: feed composition (N, P, etc.) – default species and year c2: fish composition (N, P, etc.) – default for both salmon and trout Feed: amount of feed used on each location each year (dry feed i.e water content is stable) FCR: food conversion ratio -> calculated for each generation of fish for salmon and trout, by summing up the amount of feed and biomass in Norway as a whole, calculated on national basis for cod and halibut (small volumes, high uncertainty) -> used for all facilities -> introduces some uncertainty at facility level but less uncertainty at regional level, and none at national level.</p> <p>The formula were provided in a documents provided by the Scottish Environment Protection Agency (SEPA), from 2004.</p> <p>For c2 in TOC we have used SEPA document "Scottish pollutant release inventory (SPRI) Marine fish farm emission Calculation consultation part 2 -2004", but changed it somewhat (due to CO2). It works for adult salmon production in Norway, - but there seem to be other formulas for TOC as well (we haven't looked into them so far). Examples of c1 studies are here: https://nofima.com/results/salmon-feed-more-or-less-unchanged/</p>

NORWAY (3/3)

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Where do your factors (feed composition -> c1, fish composition -> c2 and food conversion ratio -> FCR) come from ? What is their source ?	Questionnaires were sent in 2011 to fishing companies to obtain values for feed composition and fish composition. Average C1 and C2 factors were calculated from the dataset received and from data found in studies. C2 has to be on the whole fish. This work should be carried out every year, but is not due to a lack of resources. FCR is calculated from reports received from each sea facility. It is not calculated annually, but for each generation of fish.
Methods	What are the units of the factors?	To be precised later
Methods	How many categories do you have for these factors ? According to which parameter(s): size, weight, species, etc ? Could you provide us the list of factors per category ?	C1 and C2 are different per pollutant, but the same for each fish species (salmon and trout). FCR are different per fish species but the same for each pollutant.
Methods	Are the factors dependant on the geographical location? Could the same approach be used by other countries not in the Nordic region?	<p>In Norway we use the same factors to cover all geographical aquaculture-locations. We can calculate FCR at regional level, and perhaps we will analyse this later. If it is useful (not just gilding the lily), we can change the code.</p> <p>Landbased aquaculture: The main production is still hatchery fish which constitute a small part compared to the sea based, but the interest of producing later stages like post-smolt and ready to slaughter is increasing. At the moment we are gathering some data from them, and looking into whether we should standardise things. Discharge calculations could be done in several ways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Formula 1 for those without RAS and no treatment (diluted water) b) Formula 1 adjusted for sludge (samples) for those without RAS and treatment c) Discharge samples (for instance 24 hours flow proportional) and b) (comparing two methods). Perhaps another method has to be used for rare substances. <p>Formula 1 (or 2) could be use by other countries. But it doesn't work for all kinds of aquaculture, - for instance there has to be a feeding process.</p>
Methods	Do you apply this formula to each pollutant?	It cannot be used for carbon, but for the main water pollutants: nitrogen, phosphorus, TOC, metals, etc.
Methods	Is this formula used for land-based facilities?	No, for the moment land-based facilities use measurements rather than mass balances. But it is difficult to analyse N and P in land-based facilities, so they may also have to use mass balance at some point. In fact, land-based facilities have treatment, so that there is a lot of uncertainty in analysing pollutants in sludges. We dont know the exact percentage of land-based facilities, it's not very high at the moment but it is increasing, and large land-based facilities will be built in the coming years.

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	POLAND
EU member ?	EU member
Contact organization	-
Group	Group 2: Countries reporting emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities but not 7.(a) facilities

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

<i>Review per activity</i>										
Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
Number of facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	249 facilities	0 facilities	7 facilities	1 facilities
Last reporting year	-	-	-	-	-	-	2023	-	2021	2019
Pollutant(s)	-	-	-	-	-	-	NH3,CH4,N2O,PM10,NOx	-	NH3,N2O,PM10,SOx,NOx,CO2,NMVOc,HC1,CO,HFC,HF,Benzene,As,Cr,Cu,Ni,Zn,Hg	As,Ni
Additional informations	It seems one facility from Poland classified as 7.(b) has been misclassified in the database since it has a manufacturing activity, not aquaculture. 7 facilities from Poland reported air emissions from aquaculture facilities during the last seven years, probably by mistake.									

<i>Review per pollutant and method</i>						Nb of facilities reporting emissions into water for this pollutant between 2017 and 2023, and according to which specific method									
Activity	Specific method					N	P	TOC	Phenols	As	Cd	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
7.(b): aquaculture facilities	C: Use of mass balance method					0	0	0	0	3	0	0	3	0	0
Legend:	C=Calculated, calculation method used		E=Estimated		M=Measured, analytical method used			ND=No data on the method							

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? No
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why do facilities report no water emissions? - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason	No response

- For 7.(b) facilities: aquaculture facilities

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR, for the last 4 years, 11% of total reporting water emissions by your country has been based on calculations, more specifically on the following method "Mass balance". We would like to get more details on this methodology and the way emissions are assessed. If this is based on a guide or national text, could you send it to us or provide a link?	No response
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No response
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	No response
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	No response
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	No response
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	No response
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Excess nutrients - Faeces from animals - Equipment - Chemicals used (e.g. medication, treatments, antifoulants) - Other source	No response
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	No response
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	No response
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	No response

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	PORTUGAL
EU member ?	EU member
Contact organization	-
Group	Group 3: Countries reporting air emissions and emissions to water from 7.(a) facilities

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	159 facilities	0 facilities	96 facilities	0 facilities	12 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	(2012)	2023	(2010)	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3,CH4,N2O, PM10,NOx,CO2		NH3,CH4		NH3,CH4		-	-	-	-
Additional informations	For the last seven years, Portugal only reported air emissions from 7.(a) facilities, but before that, it had reported emissions to water from them (last reporting year: 2012).									

Review per pollutant and method

Data available on emissions into water?
Yes but only before 2017 for 7.(a) so no further review

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send?	Answer to questionnaire?
Yes: 29/10/2024	No

- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR, some facilities from your country assess water emissions based on calculations, could you provide us more details on the method used? How is it done? - Mass balance - Emission factors - Equations - Other	No response
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No response
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	No response
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	No response
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	No response
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	No response
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Wash water from cleaning buildings and storages - Wastewater from exhaust air treatment - Manure run-off - Other source	No response
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	No response
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	No response
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	No response
Reporting	Why did pig and sow farms stop reporting water emissions since 2012? - Water emissions are below the threshold since 2012 – please elaborate if based on calculations - These facilities stopped their activity	No response

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?	Date of interview?
No	-

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	ROMANIA (1/2)	
EU member ?	EU member	
Contact organization	National Environmental Protection Agency and National Administration Romanian Waters	
Group	Group 3: Countries reporting air emissions and emissions to water from 7.(a) facilities	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	309 facilities	0 facilities	164 facilities	1 facilities	24 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	(2008)	2023	2020	2023	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3,PM10	-	NH3,CH4,N2O	Phenols	NH3,CH4	-	-	-	-	-

Additional informations The last year in which 7.(a) facilities from Romania reported emissions into water was 2020, although some of these facilities have reported air emissions since then.

Review per pollutant and method

Activity	Specific method	Nb of facilities reporting emissions into water for this pollutant between 2017 and 2023, and according to which specific method									
		N	P	TOC	Phenols	As	Cd	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
7.(a).(ii): pig farms	M: Exact measurement standard	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0

Legend: C=Calculated, calculation method used E=Estimated M=Measured, analytical method used ND=No data on the method

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Yes: 26/11/2024 and supplement on 15/09/2025
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR, some facilities from your country assess water emissions from pig and poultry farms based on calculations, could you provide us more details on the method used? How is it done? - Mass balance - Emission factors - Equations - Other	X Other Based on periodic monitoring of concentrations. Emissions to water are estimated by periodically measuring the concentrations of target substances in wastewater streams and the volume of wastewater. Sampling for water emissions is carried out after treatment. Several Romanian poultry and pig farms have reported exceedances of emissions into water (total N, total P, TOC and phenols) because in addition to the main activity of intensive poultry and pig farming, these farms also carry out or have carried out slaughtering activities (some slaughterhouses with IED capacity, others non-IED). The on-site wastewater treatment plants treat both the technological water from the slaughterhouse and the technological wastewater resulting from the sanitation of pig sheds. In most cases, the wastewater resulting from the activities of poultry and pig farms is mixed with manure and then spread on agricultural land.
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No response
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	X Measurement : Average annual measured concentration x volume of wastewater The real mass Mr of pollutant "i" is determined according to the following formula: $Mr(i) = Vr \times Cr(i) \times 10^{-6}$ where: Vr - Real volume of wastewater, in ml Cr(i) – real concentration of pollutant "i" in wastewater, mg/l (g/ ml).
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	The monitoring frequency is established in the integrated environmental authorization depending on the impact of the activity on the water environmental factor.
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	The economic operator is obliged to monitor the level of pollutant emissions into water and to report the monitoring data to the competent environmental protection authority. Sampling, their analysis and data processing are carried out by an accredited laboratory. The sampling will be carried out in compliance with the standards in force, and the test reports will specify the measurement uncertainty. Also, the consideration of measurement uncertainty is detailed in - JRC Reference Report on Monitoring of Emissions to Air and Water from IED Installations, 2018.
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	X Channelled emissions

ROMANIA (2/2)

Question theme	Question	Answer
Scope	<p>Which sources of water emissions are included?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Wash water from cleaning buildings and storages - Wastewater from exhaust air treatment - Manure run-off - Other source 	<p align="center">X Wash water from cleaning buildings and storages X Manure run-off X Other source: technological waters from the slaughterhouse</p> <p>In farms in Romania, wastewater from washing the rearing sheds is collected together with the manure in a sewage system (channels located under the floor of the stalls) and connected to an external sewage system of the shelter and then discharged by pumping into temporary manure storage tanks. This wastewater together with the manure are used to fertilize agricultural land.</p> <p>In the case of the EUROPIGS company, the wastewater is treated in the treatment plant located on the same site, i.e. on site and then discharged into a river.</p> <p>The discharge of slurry and washing water from the halls is done through the channel under the grills, hydraulic, waste mixture evacuation system to the sewer and then to the technological waste water treatment station where the coarse waste is separated from the liquid part. Solid manure is stored on drying platforms made of reinforced concrete and then used to fertilize agricultural land. Wastewater from the slaughterhouse is pre-treated before being discharged into the collector of the treatment plant which has an advanced treatment stage.</p> <p>The Europigs farm is a fattening pig and sow farm (IED activity 6.6 b and 6.6c) with a capacity of 32,660 places for fattening pigs and 4,908 places for sows. In addition to the IED activities mentioned above, a non-IED pig and cattle slaughterhouse (maximum slaughter capacity being 35 tons/day), a FNC, a wastewater treatment plant from the slaughterhouse and the zootechnical complex (capacity 600 m³/day) as well as a non-hazardous waste incinerator that incinerates waste from slaughterhouse and from the farm (animal carcasses) operates on the same site. Also emissions in water were also reported before the 2013 reporting year by Ventureli Farm, currently SC PREMIUM PORC SIBIU SRL - Avrig farm - fattening pig breeding farm.</p> <p>SC Ventureli operated on the basis of an integrated environmental authorization - IED activity 6.6 b and 6.6c, at that time the solid and liquid wastes were evacuated hydraulically by pumping from a collecting basin through the sewage system to the treatment plant located on the same site.</p> <p>Currently, the farm has been taken over by SC PREMIUM PORC SIBIU SRL and the sewage treatment plant is no longer working on the site, the discharge of manure into the canals and vats under the sheds is done by gravity. From under the halls, the manure reaches the pumping station and further (by pumping) to the separator for the solid and liquid fraction, and then into the lagoons and onto the solid fraction storage bed.</p> <p>The manure lagoons are closed and ensure low gas emissions from the fermentation of the liquid manure mass - the solid manure platform ensures the temporary storage of the almost dry fraction of manure (with a high % of dry matter). The liquid fraction is sent to the 4 closed lagoons made of HDPE membranes, and the almost dry solid fraction is stored on the uncovered platform. The solid manure landfill is a concrete platform waterproofed with PVC and is located in the immediate vicinity of the separator.</p>
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	<i>No response</i>
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	<i>No response</i>
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	Natural or legal persons independent of the activity holder and certified by professional associations in the field of environmental protection, according to the law, may carry out these reports on behalf of economic operators.
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	Discharge points, number of hours of operation, volumes of water discharged, type of pollutant, monitoring results, calculated pollutant quantities.

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?	Date of interview?
No	-

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	SERBIA	
EU member ?	non-EU member	
Contact organization	-	
Group	None	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	84 facilities	0 facilities	66 facilities	0 facilities	11 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	(2012)	2023	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3	-	NH3,CH4,PM10, NMVOC	-	NH3	-	-	-	-	-

Additional informations For the last seven years, Serbia only reported air emissions from 7.(a) facilities, but before that, it had reported emissions to water from them (last reporting year: 2012).

Review per pollutant and method

Data available on emissions into water?
Yes but only before 2017 for 7.(a) so no further review

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send?	Answer to questionnaire?
No	-

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?	Date of interview?
No	-

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	SLOVAKIA
EU member ?	EU member
Contact organization	Slovak Environment Agency
Group	Group 4: Countries reporting only air emissions from 7.(a) facilities

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	28 facilities	0 facilities	15 facilities	0 facilities	1 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2022	-	2022	-	2021	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3	-	NH3	-	NH3	-	-	-	-	-

Review per pollutant and method

Data available on emissions into water?
No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send?	Answer to questionnaire?
Yes: 29/10/2024	Yes: 29/11/2024

- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	<p>Why do facilities report no water emissions?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water emissions are below the threshold - Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions - Facilities don't know how to assess water emissions because of the lack of methodology / guide - Other reason 	<p>X Facilities consider they don't have any water emissions, because:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Release of wastewater into surface water or groundwater is not allowed and thereby is not monitored; - Liquid waste and sewage water is removed to a wastewater treatment plant (directly, or stored in cesspool and removed to WWTP in cistern truck); - Slurry is applied to the soil or sold according to the national law. <p>X Other reason:</p> <p>Slovak permitting body (Slovak Environment Inspectorate) determines in the integrated permit which substances discharged into the waters the operator must monitor, measure and report.</p> <p>In the case of farms, for the discharge of waste water, emission limits are often not set, nor are the substances discharged into the water, which the operator has to monitor. For this reason, the operator does not have to measure or report substances. The permit specifies often the conditions for dealing with the entire volume of wastewater only, which is transferred to the WWTP through sewer system or tanks.</p> <p>Integrated permit and conditions given in it are of a high priority; operators take into account conditions and obligations determined in the integrated permit in the first place, and they might not be aware of the fact that there are also other obligations they should follow and fulfil, which are not mentioned in the integrated permit.</p> <p>In this respect it is a problematic situation, which is partly the result of seeing the integrated permit as one big comprehensive permit. The operator would be happy to follow one permit and not have to follow other regulations. In the Slovak Republic, the idea of integration was often presented as the goal of the entire directive (first IPPC, then IED), so many operators want to perceive the integrated permit in this way.</p> <p>However, the obligation to report data on emissions is dealt with in the Slovak Republic by a different law, and therefore it may happen that some operators miss the obligation to report these emissions. Anyway, they deal with waste waters in accordance with the conditions in the integrated permit.</p> <p>The situation described may not apply to all farms, or to other facilities, it may be a combination of reasons.</p> <p>We will discuss this with the Inspectorate as the permitting body, and with the Ministry to see where the problem lies in "missing" reporting emissions data.</p>

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?	Date of interview?
No	-

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	SLOVENIA	
EU member ?	EU member	
Contact organization	-	
Group	Group 3: Countries reporting air emissions and emissions to water from 7.(a) facilities	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	16 facilities	0 facilities	1 facilities	0 facilities	1 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2022	(2007)	2023	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	NH3	-	NH3	-	NH3	-	-	-	-	-
Additional informations	For the last seven years, Slovenia only reported air emissions from 7.(a) facilities, but before that, it had reported emissions to water from them (last reporting year: 2007).									

Review per pollutant and method

Data available on emissions into water?
Yes but only before 2017 for 7.(a) so no further review

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? No
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Could you provide us more details on the method used to assess water emissions from pig and poultry farms in E-PRTR? How is it done?	No response
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No response
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	No response
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	No response
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	No response
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	No response
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Wash water from cleaning buildings and storages - Wastewater from exhaust air treatment - Manure run-off - Other source	No response
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	No response
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	No response
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	No response
Reporting	Why did pig farms stop reporting water emissions since 2007? - Water emissions are below the threshold since 2007 - Other reason	No response

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done? No	Date of interview? -
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COUNTRY DATA SHEET	SPAIN (1/2)	
EU member ?	EU member	
Contact organization	Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico	
Group	Group 1: Countries reporting air emissions and emissions to water from 7.(a) facilities and emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities	

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	491 facilities	0 facilities	2100 facilities	0 facilities	718 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	25 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	(2014)	2023	(2008)	2023	-	-	-	-	2023
Pollutant(s)	NH3,CH4,N2O	-	NH3,CH4,N2O	-	NH3,CH4,N2O, PM10	-	-	-	-	N,P,TOC

Additional informations For the last seven years, Spain only reported air emissions from 7.(a) facilities, but before that, it had reported emissions to water from them (last reporting year: 2014).

Review per pollutant and method

Activity	Specific method	Nb of facilities reporting emissions into water for this pollutant between 2017 and 2023, and according to which specific method									
		N	P	TOC	Phenols	As	Cd	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
7.(b): aquaculture facilities	C: Use of emission factors	8	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	C: Calculations from measurement data (flow and concentration)	5	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	M: Exact measurement standard	10	13	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	E: No further details	13	14	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	ND: No data on the method used	65	66	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	

Legend: C=Calculated, calculation method used E=Estimated M=Measured, analytical method used ND=No data on the method

Additional informations on methods For some facilities, calculations based on the concentration and flow measured, for others on emission factors applied to the feed supplied and the feed assimilated by the fish.

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send?	Answer to questionnaire?
Yes: 29/10/2024	Partially in an email: 15/09/25

- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR data, some facilities from your country assess water emissions based on calculations, more specifically according to the following method "Emission factors". We would like to get more details on this methodology and the way emissions are assessed. Are they tier 1, 2 or 3? Where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	No response
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No response
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	No response
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	No response
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	No response
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Wash water from cleaning buildings and storages - Wastewater from exhaust air treatment - Manure run-off - Other source	No response
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	No response
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	No response
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	No response

SPAIN (2/2)

Question theme	Question	Answer
Reporting	Why there have not been water emissions reported by pigs and poultry farms since 2014? - Water emissions are below the threshold since 2014 – Please elaborate - Other reason	<i>No response</i>

- For 7.(b) facilities: aquaculture facilities

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR data, some facilities from your country assess water emissions based on calculations, more specifically according to the following method “Emission factors”. We would like to get more details on this methodology and the way emissions are assessed. Are they tier 1, 2 or 3? Where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	Aquaculture based on pens/cages in the sea: It is not feasible to perform direct measurements, therefore N and P emissions are calculated. They used the following two models: a. Lupatsch & Kissil (1998). b. Vergara et al. (2005). Both models get similar results. They are based on feed composition and they have been used for a long time. Terrestrial aquaculture (either sea water or fresh water): Direct measurement. Operators are required to measure and notify these measurements to the competent authority. With regard to E-PRTR, these land installations should not use the models outlined above. These are estimations that are not suitable for quantifying emissions from land installations. Since the IEPB establishes that direct measurements should be the norm wherever this is possible, and considering that these installations are required to do so by law, the industrial association prefers that direct measurements are used for PRTR reporting. They only agree that direct measurements are used and not calculations. The reason for this, according to this difference between 1 and 2 is, according to this industrial association: - Aquaculture farms in land apply abatement techniques such as filters and decantation which reduce notably water emissions, to sea and freshwater. - There are over 200 land aquaculture farms which routinely perform direct measurements in Spain (again, no need for calculations). - There are land aquaculture farms in Spain with Recirculating Aquaculture Systems. These are land-based aquaculture systems in which water is reused and filtered, rather than flowing freely through the system. According to the industrial associations, this reduces water emissions to negligible. - Calculation models like those from Lupatsch and Vergara, although they use as input to the formula the composition of the feed, they do not take into account the efficiency and improvements during the manufacturing of the feed. - For land aquaculture, this industrial association is not aware of any calculation method used. - Depending on where the emissions occur, dispersion modelling should consider the impact of currents, intertidal zones and so on, which would have an impact on emissions.
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	<i>No response</i>
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	<i>No response</i>
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	<i>No response</i>
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	<i>No response</i>
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Excess nutrients - Faeces from animals - Equipment - Chemicals used (e.g. medication, treatments, antifoulants) - Other source	<i>No response</i>
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	<i>No response</i>
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	<i>No response</i>
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	<i>No response</i>
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	<i>No response</i>

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Interview done?</th> </tr> <tr> <td align="center">No</td> </tr> </table>	Interview done?	No	<table border="1"> <tr> <th>Date of interview?</th> </tr> <tr> <td align="center">-</td> </tr> </table>	Date of interview?	-
Interview done?					
No					
Date of interview?					
-					

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	SWEDEN (1/2)
EU member ?	EU member
Contact organization	Swedish Environmental Agency
Group	Group 1: Countries reporting air emissions and emissions to water from 7.(a) facilities and emissions to water from 7.(b) facilities

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE
From 2017 to 2023

<i>Review per activity</i>										
Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	68 facilities	0 facilities	48 facilities	1 facilities	8 facilities	0 facilities	1 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	3 facilities
Last reporting year	2023	-	2023	2022	2022	-	2017	-	-	2023
Pollutant(s)	NH3	-	NH3	N	NH3	-	NH3	-	-	N,P

<i>Review per pollutant and method</i>											
Activity	Specific method	Nb of facilities reporting emissions into water for this pollutant between 2017 and 2023, and according to which specific method									
		N	P	TOC	Phenols	As	Cd	Cu	Ni	Pb	Zn
7.(a).(ii): pig farms	E: No further details	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
7.(b): aquaculture facilities	C: Calculations based on "Fiskodling, Allmänna råd 93:10"	0	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	M: Calculations based on "Fiskodling, Allmänna råd 93:10"	12	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	ND: No data on the method used	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Legend:	C=Calculated, calculation method used	E=Estimated	M=Measured, analytical method used	ND=No data on the method							

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send? Yes: 29/10/2024	Answer to questionnaire? Yes: 31/01/2025
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- For 7.(a) facilities: pig and/or poultry farms

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	Based on E-PRTR, for the last 4 years, 100% of total reporting water emissions from this sector in Sweden has been based on estimations, could you provide us more details on the method used? How is it done? - Mass balance - Emission factors - Equations - Other	X Other: Expert judgement (only one facility for the last four years)
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	No
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	Not concerned: no emission factors used
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	Not concerned: no emission factors used
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	The operators don't report information about uncertainty. But bearing in mind that releases are based on expert judgement it has to be considered as very high.
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	X Diffuse emissions
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Wash water from cleaning buildings and storages - Wastewater from exhaust air treatment - Manure run-off - Other source	Handling and spreading of manure
Question theme	Question	Answer
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	No response
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	No response
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	Don't know.
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	No response

SWEDEN (2/2)

- For 7.(b) facilities: aquaculture facilities

Question theme	Question	Answer
Methods	<p>1. Based on E-PRTR, some aquaculture facilities from your country assess water emissions thanks to a report from 1987 "Rapport 3382" or another report from 1993 "Almanna Rad 93:10".</p> <p>We would like to get more details on the methodology and the way emissions are assessed.</p> <p>Could you send us this report or give us contact details of someone that could send it to us or provide a link?</p> <p>"G. Persson, 1987, Sambandet mellan föda, produktion och förorening vid odling av stor regnbåge (Salmo gairdneri), Report 3382, Natl. Swed. Environ. Prot. Board, Solna (1987), p. 76"</p> <p>This source is from the 1980s, does this mean that the sector's emissions profile is still the same or that there is no new scientific information?</p>	<p>1. The Swedish Environmental Protection Agency has repealed the general guidance on Fish Farming - Planning, Permits, Supervision (AR 93:10). The decision came into force on 1 April 2019. Existing permits for fish farming sometimes refer to the general guideline's calculation model for nutrient supply (nitrogen and phosphorus). See description and equation below. Further information is available at the Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management webpage, see: Beräkning av näringsstofförsel från en fiskodling - Vägledning - Vägledning, föreskrifter och lagar - Havs- och vattenmyndigheten - Model for calculation of nutrient discharges from aquaculture</p> <p>The discharge of nutrients from aquaculture as described in the Swedish guidelines presented at the Swedish Agency for Marine and Water Management website:</p> $L=P \times (FK \times C1 - CR)$ <p>L=Discharge (kg/10), P=Net production of fish as net growth of fish including dead fish during a period (tonnes), FK=Feed coefficient, as feed used (tonnes)/Fish production (tonnes), C1=P or N content in feed (%) CR=P or N content in fish (%).</p> <p>Additional information in the guidelines:</p> <p>If possible, the discharge of nutrients should be calculated separately for each age-category of the farmed fish. The content of phosphorus in rainbow trout is approx. 0.4%. The feed contains between 0.8 and 1.3% phosphorus. Corresponding content of nitrogen is 5-8% in feed and 2.5-3.5% in fish. The feed coefficient is normally 0.8-1.2 for small fish (< 1 kg) and 1.0-1.5 for large fish (food fish).</p> <p>Further information:</p> <p>Swedish Metrological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) has made a compilation of different calculation models for assessing the nutrient load of fish farms on lakes, watercourses, reservoirs and coastal waters, see: https://www.havochvatten.se/data-kartor-och-rapporter/rapporter-och-andra-publikationer/publikationer/2016-03-24-oversikt-av-berakningsmodeller-for-bedomning-av-fiskodlingars-naringsamnesbelastning-pa-sojar-vattendrag-magasin-och-kustvatten.html</p> <p>HELCOM Guidelines for the annual and periodical compilation and reporting of waterborne pollution inputs to the Baltic Sea (PLC-Water) page 40 table Table 5.1.a (Content of total nitrogen and total phosphorus in fish (trout) and fish feed), see: https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/HELCOM-PLC-Water-Guidelines-2022.pdf .</p> <p>Helcom guidelines in line with the methodology given in repealed guidelines from Swedish EPA. One advantage with Helcoms guideline is that they update their GL on a regular basis.</p> <p>OECD RETS for aqua culture, see: Emission Estimation Technique Manual for Aggregated Emissions from Temperate Water Finfish Aquaculture - Version 1.0 - DCEEW https://www.dceew.gov.au/environment/protection/npi/reporting/industry-reporting-materials/diffuse-emissions-manuals/emission-estimation-technique-manual-aquaculture-barramundi-prawns-crocodiles-pearl-oysters</p>
	<p>2. Other facilities use mass balance method. We would like to get more details on the methodology and the way emissions are assessed.</p>	<p>2. It is unclear what method they use. It might be possible that they use the calculation model described above but they has used MAB instead of OTH in their report.</p>
Regulatory framework	Does a national text or guide exist to help facilities calculate their water emissions? If so, does it concern only certain sectors or is it global? Could you send it to us or provide a link?	See above.
Emissions factors	If emissions are based on emission factors, where do these factors come from? - Database - Measurement - Other	See above.
Emissions factors	What kind of activity rate is used to calculate emissions?	See above.
Uncertainty	What is the uncertainty linked to the emissions results?	The operators don't report information about uncertainty
Scope	What is the scope of the emissions? What kind of water emissions are included in the results? - Channelled emissions - Diffuse emissions - Other	See above.
Scope	Which sources of water emissions are included? - Excess nutrients - Faeces from animals - Equipment - Chemicals used (e.g. medication, treatments, antifoulants) - Other source	See above.
Scope	Are wastewater treatments considered for the water emissions?	See above.
Scope	Which pathways are included in the scope?	See above.
Reporting	Do you know if operators hire other firms to calculate emissions on their behalf?	Don't know.
Reporting	What kind of information required to assess wastewater discharges have to be reported?	No response

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?	Date of interview?
No	-

COUNTRY DATA SHEET	SWITZERLAND
EU member ?	non-EU member
Contact organization	-
Group	None

DATA FROM E-PRTR DATABASE

From 2017 to 2023

Review per activity

Facilities reporting emissions 2017-2023	7.(a).(i): poultry farms		7.(a).(ii): pig farms		7.(a).(iii): sows farms		7.(a): unspecified farms		7.(b): aquaculture facilities	
	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions	Air emissions	Water emissions
Number of facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities	0 facilities
Last reporting year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Pollutant(s)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Review per pollutant and method

Data available on emissions into water?
No, neither for 7.(a) nor for 7.(b): no further review

Total statistics from 2007 to 2023

Legend:

7.(a) facilities reporting water emissions	Measurement	Measurement
7.(a) facilities reporting air emissions	Calculations	Calculations
7.(b) facilities reporting water emissions	Estimation	Estimation
7.(b) facilities reporting air emissions	No data	No data

INFORMATION FROM QUESTIONNAIRE

Questionnaire send?	Answer to questionnaire?
No	-

INFORMATION FROM INTERVIEW

Interview done?	Date of interview?
No	-

European Topic Centre
Human health and the environment
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